

HellasQCI

Deploying advanced national QCI systems and networks in Greece

Deliverable D6.5

Dissemination, communication, clustering and exploitation activities

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Abstract: This report provides a comprehensive overview of the dissemination and communication strategies employed by the HellasQCI project from M16 to M42. As an integral component of the EuroQCI initiative, HellasQCI aims to establish a secure quantum communication network to protect the EU against emerging cyber threats. This report details the extensive dissemination and communication activities undertaken to inform stakeholders across the EU about the project's achievements and objectives.

The document outlines the establishment of a robust online media presence, including an updated website and frequently updated social media platforms ([Twitter](#), [Facebook](#), [LinkedIn](#), and [YouTube](#)) to enhance brand identity and raise awareness. It also describes the development of the HellasQCI online training platform and the methodology behind the first training event, aiming to educate and involve the HellasQCI community and stakeholders in quantum communication and cybersecurity.

Further, the report presents numerous dissemination and communication activities, such as clustering activities, collaborations with EU-funded projects, conference participation, and scientific publications. It meticulously tracks the project's achievements against predefined KPIs, providing insights into the effectiveness of the dissemination efforts.

This deliverable, forming part of the Work Package 6 "Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation", highlights the project's commitment to raising public awareness, engaging with targeted stakeholders, and fostering a community around the HellasQCI network. By implementing the dissemination and communication plan laid out in D6.1, the project seeks to broaden its reach and impact, ensuring the successful exploitation of its results and contributions to EuroQCI Initiative and beyond.

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List of Acronyms

QCI	Quantum Communication Infrastructure
CSA	Coordination and support action
QKD	Quantum Key Distribution
WP	Work package
NatQCI	National QCI project
DCB	Dissemination and Communication Board
EuroQCI	European Quantum Communication infrastructure
PETRUS	EuroQCI coordination and support action
OGS	Optical ground station
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
DEP	Digital Europe Programme
UX	User Experience
PMB	Project Management Board
NRENs	National Research and Educational Networks
SAB	Security Advisory Board

Executive Summary

The HellasQCI project, as a key component of the European Quantum Communication Infrastructure (EuroQCI) initiative, contributes to the development of a secure quantum communication infrastructure designed to protect European society, public administrations, critical infrastructures, and the economy against emerging cyber threats, including those arising from future quantum computing capabilities.

The project focuses on the development, deployment, and demonstration of advanced quantum communication systems and networking technologies in Greece. Its objectives include the implementation of national QCI infrastructure, the demonstration of use cases across selected application scenarios, the provision of training for technical, research, and end-user communities, collaboration with PETRUS CSA and other National QCI initiatives, and the establishment of the HellasQCI stakeholder community. In parallel, the project supports alignment with QKD-related security standards, certification approaches, and regulatory developments, thereby strengthening national and European capabilities in quantum communication and cybersecurity.

This final dissemination report for Work Package 6 (WP6), “Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation”, covers the period from M16 to M42 and presents the communication, dissemination, standardisation-awareness, training, community-building, and exploitation-related activities implemented during the project. It also provides an overview of the project’s achievements, the progress made against the dissemination and communication plan defined in D6.1, and the impact of these activities on relevant stakeholder groups at national and European level.

Communication and dissemination activities were systematically planned, implemented, and monitored throughout the reporting period. All project partners contributed to the promotion of project results, the transfer of knowledge within their respective communities, and the engagement of relevant stakeholders, including research organisations, industry actors, public authorities, critical infrastructure operators, standardisation communities, and the wider quantum communication ecosystem.

Overall, the activities reported in this deliverable demonstrate that HellasQCI has progressed beyond its initial role as a national deployment project. Through its dissemination, training, stakeholder engagement, and alignment with European initiatives, the project has become an active contributor to the wider European quantum communication ecosystem. These activities have helped to raise awareness, support knowledge transfer, strengthen collaboration with related EuroQCI and National QCI actions, and lay the foundations for sustained cooperation, uptake, and exploitation beyond the project lifetime.

1. Introduction

HellasQCI is a European project, supported in part (50%) by the European Union under grant agreement No 101091504 and in part (50%) by national funds. The project is also supported by the Greek Government through the Ministry of Digital Governance and Artificial Intelligence. HellasQCI is coordinated by GRNET S.A. – National Infrastructures for Research and Technology and consists of a 13-partner consortium (after the withdrawal of COSMOTE from the HellasQCI consortium).

The project designed, deployed, and operated the first national experimental quantum communication infrastructure in Greece, spanning three major urban centers and ensuring interoperability with the space segment of the European Quantum Communication Infrastructure (EuroQCI). The deployed infrastructure now forms the foundation of the national quantum communication network, enabling the development and validation of advanced cybersecurity applications and pilot use cases across the governmental, industrial, and research sectors. Through the integration of Quantum Key Distribution (QKD) technologies, HellasQCI contributed to the advancement of ultra-secure data transmission and resilient communication services aligned with Europe’s next-generation cybersecurity objectives.

This deliverable is part of Task 6.3 “Dissemination and Communication Activities” of WP6 “Communication, dissemination and exploitation”. It reports on the detailed dissemination, communication and exploitation activities that took place between M16 and M42 and presents a consolidated overview of all activities carried out throughout the full project duration (M1–M42), along with the impact these activities had. Related key performance indicators (KPIs) help in measuring the effectiveness of communication and dissemination activities and in realigning the strategy where needed.

1.1. Relation to the project

WP6 is a horizontal work package and is responsible for the communication of the project, its outreach and the stakeholders’ involvement, including the creation of the HellasQCI community. Its core objectives are: a) to increase awareness about the project activities, outcomes and benefits, b) to ensure the involvement of National stakeholders and create the HellasQCI community, c) to support exploitation of the project results by allowing open access to selected HellasQCI tools and d) to support standardization activities of the project results in European and international Standards Development Organizations (SDOs). Work package 6 is led by the National Center for Scientific Research Demokritos (NCSR) while nine (9) other members of the consortium participate in its activities. Six (6) partners of the consortium contribute to this deliverable: NCSR, GRNET, MinDigital, NOA, QUBITECH and SPACE HELLAS (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Dissemination and communication WP relative to other WPs

1.2. Communication guidelines, Security Advisory Board (SAB)

The HellasQCI project has established a Security Advisory Board (SAB).

The SAB reviews all project deliverables of any type, assesses whether they include any security-sensitive information and proposes timely measures in order to prevent the misuse of such information and to be compliant with the EuroQCI security guidelines.

Additionally, the SAB has established a process to review sensitive content, ensuring it's not shared or published in any communication or dissemination channels for the HellasQCI project.

This ensures that materials containing sensitive information undergo SAB filtering, and communication and dissemination activities are regulated to prevent the release of certain materials.

The process that has been established to regulate all communication activities, including publications in journals, conferences, newsletters, website and social media announcements, and information shared at training events is summarized below:

- Authors of all content produced in the context of the HellasQCI project i.e. publications, presentations, deliverables etc. ensure to forward the content item to the SAB member designated responsible for publicity approvals, 10 days before the submission/publication deadline.
- For publications, all authors must ensure that no sensitive information is included in the copyright. The SAB member reads the item, confirms there is no sensitive information included, and grants approval for submission/publicity. The content item forwarded to the SAB member need not be in final form as long as it contains any important information.
- For presentations at conferences, workshops, etc. if the presentation is for a publication covered in the previous bullet and contains no additional information, there is no need to go through the SAB. Otherwise, it must follow the same process as above.
- Specific provisions to prevent leakage through social engineering were implemented. Appointing representatives to appear at conferences, present project progress, etc. items outside the project team have been considered.

1.3. Document structure

The document has six (6) distinct sections. It starts with Section 1, with an Introduction of the document's purpose and content. Section 2 presents the Dissemination and communication tools and methods – HellasQCI online presence, shedding light on the methods employed to share and communicate information on online tools. In Section 3, the focus shifts to the projects Dissemination and communication activities – HellasQCI offline presence. Section 4, titled Performance Monitoring, presents the measurable results of the implementation of the Communication and Dissemination Strategy. Section 5, addresses Exploitation Plan and Methodology, outlining the approach for utilizing acquired information effectively. The document ends with Section 6 which is a Conclusion. This structured framework ensures a logical flow of information, guiding the reader through the key sections of the document.

1.4. Dissemination and communication tools and methods – HellasQCI online and offline presence

Dissemination is the process of communicating project outcomes and information to stakeholders and communities to raise awareness and showcase the project's possible benefits. The HellasQCI project shares its findings and outcomes with a variety of stakeholders, including academics, policymakers, industry, and the general public.

Throughout the project's existence, the goal is to exchange information, develop collaboration, promote the use of Quantum Communication technologies and QKD systems, and raise public awareness.

The project's dissemination approach focuses on developing a coherent narrative, supporting innovation and information transfer, demonstrating outcomes, and spreading excellence. The key dissemination objectives are to promote commercial acceptance of infrastructures and technology introduced over the project's lifespan.

2. Dissemination and communication tools and methods – HellasQCI online presence

The online media presence of the project helps in disseminating the project's updates, progress, and achievements to all target audience groups. Having an online presence allows a Digital Europe Program (DEP) project to reach more people and build a stronger awareness around the concept of Quantum Communication Infrastructure. With the right content news about the HellasQCI project can reach more target audience groups and build a more recognizable brand.

Online Campaigns make it easier for the project to reach more key stakeholders. The HellasQCI key messages are targeted to the right audiences through search engine optimization and other online marketing strategies (i.e. social media marketing) to ensure the targeted campaigns are viewed by the key audiences intended to reach and hence most likely to be interested in it.

HellasQCI Online Media Presence is comprised of the official website (www.hellasqci.eu), the [Training Portal](#), the HellasQCI Social Media Channels (i.e. [LinkedIn](#), [Facebook](#), [Twitter](#), [YouTube](#)), [Zenodo](#) and the [Newsletters](#).

2.1. Website

The project website (<https://hellasqci.eu/>) has continued to serve as a central pillar for dissemination, communication, clustering, and exploitation activities throughout the reporting period M16 to M42. Building on its early establishment (M4), the website has been continuously updated and enriched to reflect the project's progress, results, and growing ecosystem.

Figure 2: HellasQCI menu overview

The website operates as the primary digital hub of the project, integrating all communication channels and ensuring open access to project outputs. It provides a structured (Figure 2) and user-friendly environment for accessing information, materials, and updates related to HellasQCI (Figure 3).

HELLASQCI

Greece strengthens the resilience of its critical infrastructure by leveraging quantum technologies

HellasQCI will implement three metropolitan communication networks in Athens, Thessaloniki and Heraklion Crete, utilizing, among others, Quantum Key Distribution (QKD), terrestrial optical fibre and satellite technologies.

The HellasQCI consortium involves key research institutes and universities of Greece, which are able to address the needs for an operational HellasQCI infrastructure.

HellasQCI plans to cooperate with other EU Member States in order to boost Europe's scientific and technological capabilities in cybersecurity and quantum technologies.

Use cases to enhance the Digital Public Services security
Government

Use cases for the Industrial partners
Industry

Experimental Educational and Research use cases
Research

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Register to receive our newsletter

Latest News

June 29, 2026
HellasQCI Newsletter #6 - July 2026
The 5th official HellasQCI Newsletter is out, aiming to show the...

June 16, 2026
SEEWQCI and HellasQCI at BEYOND 2026
SEEWQCI and HellasQCI will be presented BEYOND 2026, the International Digital...

June 15, 2026
GRNET at TNC26: The Quantum Technologies for...
GRNET, Greece's National Research and Education Network (NREN), operating under the...

HellasQCI in the press

insider

Liberal
Ελευθέριος Βενιζέλος

THE INDICATOR

Forbes

NIST

Figure 3: HellasQCI main page

During M16 to M42, particular emphasis was placed on maintaining up-to-date content and expanding the website's role as a repository of knowledge and engagement. New materials, including [public deliverables](#), [scientific publications](#), [training resources](#), and [procurement announcements](#), were systematically uploaded, ensuring transparency and accessibility for stakeholders, policymakers, industry actors, and the wider public (Figure 4).

Figure 4: HellasQCI public results menu

The website continued to support the development of the [HellasQCI community](#) by facilitating stakeholder engagement through its dedicated community section (Figure 5).

Figure 5: HellasQCI Community

The registration functionalities and subscription tools enabled the steady growth of an ecosystem involving representatives from academia, industry, public authorities, SMEs, and startups (Figure 6). Users were also able to subscribe to HellasQCI community and receive targeted updates (Figure 7).

National Stakeholder Engagement

HellasQCI builds a national community to promote Quantum Communication (QC) technologies across Greece. The goal is to unite stakeholders who can benefit from and support the HellasQCI network, share expertise, and apply QC in practical, sustainable ways. The community includes local users of traditional telecom services who adopt and test advanced use cases developed by HellasQCI. It brings together government, industry, academia, SMEs, and start-ups to foster collaboration, drive innovation, and strengthen the QC value chain.

This ecosystem supports the growth of start-ups and SMEs in the QC domain by offering research capabilities and encouraging new business opportunities. By promoting synergies and national collaboration, the community boosts the development, uptake, and commercialization of QC technologies in the Greek economy. Members engage with HellasQCI's progress and shape their strategies to create value, transfer knowledge, and share best practices across the ecosystem.

Indicative ecosystem members

Figure 6: HellasQCI community page

Join Our Community

Organization

Sector Association

Specify other Sector Association

Address (Street, City, Postal Code, Country)

Telephone

Email

Website

Position in Organisation

First Name

Last Name

Your Organization Interest in HellasQCI

I would like to be informed of

Other: (please propose)

I have read the **Privacy Statement** and declare that I consent to receive updates on the HellasQCI news, events, activities and research projects.

Subscribe

Figure 7: HellasQCI community registration

The training section (Figure 8) was regularly updated with information on training activities and access to learning materials via the training platform, supporting capacity building and knowledge transfer in the field of quantum communication technologies.

Figure 8: HellasQCI website training menu

Dedicated information pages were created for [HellasQCI Training Event in Crete 2024](#) (Figure 9), [QCI Days Athens 2025](#) (Figure 10) and [HellasQCI Winter School in Thessaloniki 2025](#) (Figure 11)

Figure 10: QCI Days Athens Infographic

Figure 9: HellasQCI Training Event Crete 2024 Information page

HellasQCI Winter School (Training Workshop)

About the event | Programme | Organisers | How to get there | Getting Back to work

SAVE THE DATE

26-28 November 2025

Aristotle University of Thessaloniki
 Aristotle University of Thessaloniki Research and Innovation Center (ARISTO RIC)
 HELLASQCI Training and Workshop Center (HWC)
 Cybersecurity & IT Impact Research & Academic Office & Operating Technologies Industry

Location: Thessaloniki, Greece
 Dates: 26-28 November 2025

Venue:

- Aristotle University, Research and Innovation Center (ARISTO RIC)
- ARISTO Center for Interdisciplinary Research and Innovation (ARISTO CIR)
- NOESIS Thessaloniki Science Center & Technology Museum

Web site: www.hellasqci.eu | hellasqci@hellasqci.eu

PDF: <https://www.grnet.gr/News/15581/News/47818>

HellasQCI is a project funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe Thematic Pillar 2, in the domain of Digital, Industry, Culture and Heritage, through the HellasQCI Winter School Thessaloniki 2025. It is a key activity of the project "HellasQCI Winter School Thessaloniki 2025" (HWC) and is organized by the HellasQCI consortium.

The HellasQCI Winter School 2025 is addressed to Outstanding and Promising Quantum Physics students and researchers in Europe, QCI and non-QCI, from leading Universities, Institutes, Members of the QCI ecosystem, and other stakeholders, who are interested in participating in the field of Quantum Information Science and Technology.

HellasQCI and the EuroQCI ecosystem

The EuroQCI ecosystem is a leading initiative in Europe, supported by the European Union, aimed at accelerating the development of quantum technologies and their application in various sectors. It is a key activity of the project "HellasQCI Winter School Thessaloniki 2025" (HWC) and is organized by the HellasQCI consortium.

The HellasQCI project is a leading initiative in Europe, supported by the European Union, aimed at accelerating the development of quantum technologies and their application in various sectors. It is a key activity of the project "HellasQCI Winter School Thessaloniki 2025" (HWC) and is organized by the HellasQCI consortium.

To support these goals, the project is funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe Thematic Pillar 2, in the domain of Digital, Industry, Culture and Heritage, through the HellasQCI Winter School Thessaloniki 2025. It is a key activity of the project "HellasQCI Winter School Thessaloniki 2025" (HWC) and is organized by the HellasQCI consortium.

Registration is required and attendance is free of charge. In order to register, you should have a valid email address and a valid passport. The registration process is available on the HellasQCI website.

Coordinator: grnet

About Us: [Privacy Policy](#), [Terms and Conditions](#)

Contact: hellasqci@hellasqci.eu, hellasqci@hellasqci.eu

Newsletters: [Request to subscribe to newsletters](#)

GRNET S.A. - National Institute for Research and Technology
 26500 Thessaloniki, Greece

Co-funded by the European Union | #HellasQCI2025

Figure 11: HellasQCI Winter School Thessaloniki 2025 Information

The “[Newscorner](#)” section (Figure 12) remained as the key dissemination tool, providing continuous updates on project [news](#), [events](#), [press coverage](#) (Figure 13) and [newsletters](#). Throughout the reporting period, it contributed to increasing the visibility of the project at both national and European levels, highlighting participation in conferences, workshops, and collaboration activities within the EuroQCI ecosystem.

Figure 12: HellasQCI Newsfeed page

Figure 13: HellasQCI in the press

Furthermore, the website strengthened its role in clustering activities by presenting information related to EuroQCI initiatives (Figure 14) and collaboration with relevant projects and the PETRUS CSA. It served as a central access point for stakeholders seeking information on standardisation efforts and best practices emerging from the project.

Figure 14: EUROQCI Information page

From M16 to M42, the HellasQCI website evolved from a core dissemination tool into a dynamic platform supporting communication, stakeholder engagement, knowledge sharing, and ecosystem development, significantly contributing to the project’s outreach and impact.

2.2. HellasQCI online training platform

The HellasQCI Training Platform is one of the project’s main educational outputs, offering continued access to the training materials and expertise developed throughout its implementation.

To support the long-term preservation of this content, the platform consolidates presentations, recorded lectures, and videos produced during various project activities. It functions as a central repository where researchers, students, IT and cybersecurity professionals, as well as public sector stakeholders, can access and review the knowledge generated by the project.

At present, the platform includes 148 presentations from key HellasQCI training and dissemination events, specifically:

- [HellasQCI Winter School Thessaloniki 2025](#) – 35 presentations
- [QCI Days Athens 2025](#) – 62 presentations
- [Training Event Crete 2024](#) – 33 presentations
- [Training Events Athens 2023](#) – 18 presentations

Results from the HellasQCI Training Platform

Figure 15: HellasQCI Training Platform Registered Users

Figure 15 shows how the 156 registered users of the HellasQCI training platform are distributed across professional sectors as of June 2026.

The largest group comes from Education & Academia at 31.4%, closely followed by Technical & Engineering roles at 30.8%. Management & Executive roles account for 16%, while Research & Innovation and Defense, Government & Public Institutions each represent 10.9%.

Taken together, these figures point to a diverse but strongly technology- and education-oriented community. Education & Academia and Technical & Engineering backgrounds account for slightly more than 60% of all registrations, reflecting strong interest from universities, researchers, engineers, and technical professionals. This underlines the platform's relevance for advanced learning and specialised skills development in quantum communication and cybersecurity.

The share of Management & Executive users suggests the platform is also reaching decision-makers and organisational leaders keen to understand emerging quantum technologies and their strategic implications. Meanwhile, participation from Research & Innovation and from Defense, Government & Public Institutions shows engagement from sectors critical to national infrastructure, security, and long-term technological competitiveness.

This mix indicates that the platform extends well beyond academic training, supporting a broader ecosystem of public institutions, industry, and leadership stakeholders. Overall, the distribution suggests HellasQCI is successfully reaching a multidisciplinary audience and establishing itself as a valuable resource for both technical education and strategic awareness in quantum communications.

[Communication actions to promote the Training Platform](#)

As of June 2026, the HellasQCI training platform has successfully registered **156 users**, representing a significant increase compared to the previous reporting period and demonstrating sustained interest in quantum communication technologies, quantum computing, cybersecurity, and post-quantum cryptography training.

Following the completion of the HellasQCI Training Event in Crete, two targeted follow-up email campaigns were disseminated to **324 participants** registered in the Event email campaign lists.

Additionally, upon completion of the training events, participation certificates were distributed to **124 attendees** for the Training Event in Crete and **67 participants** for the Winter School in Thessaloniki, together with information and direct access to the HellasQCI Training Platform.

WP6 promoted the availability of the [HellasQCI Training Event Crete 2024 online course](#) and [HellasQCI Winter School in Thessaloniki](#) through the project's communication channels, inviting a broader audience to access the recorded training material via the HellasQCI Training Platform

These efforts resulted in a notable online reach, with the announcement of [HellasQCI Training Event Crete 2024 online course](#) garnering **1.4K Reach on Facebook, 35 impressions on Twitter, and 450 impressions on LinkedIn**.

This multi-channel social media approach not only highlighted the platform's launch but also emphasized the consortium's commitment to fostering an engaged and informed community around the HellasQCI project.

The educational value of the HellasQCI training programme was further recognised through the integration of 19 specialised courses into the [GÉANT eAcademy](#), embedding the project's training materials into Europe's leading research and education network platform and ensuring long-term accessibility beyond the project's lifetime. HellasQCI Training platform courses are available in [Quantum Technology Session](#). Users can navigate to these through the 'metro map' shown in Figure 16.

Figure 16: GÉANT Network eAcademy 'metro map'

2.3. Digital communication channels

The HellasQCI Consortium has strategically established a comprehensive digital communication framework to optimize the dissemination and visibility of its activities and outcomes. This framework included the launch of a dedicated website alongside an integrated presence across key social media platforms—[Twitter](#), [Facebook](#), [LinkedIn](#), and [YouTube](#). These platforms serve as the principal channels for disseminating information about the project, engaging with diverse audiences, and facilitating community interaction around the project's developments and achievements.

Social media for engagement and outreach

Social media channels play a critical role in the project's communication strategy:

- **Twitter and Facebook** allow HellasQCI to target a broader audience, providing updates, event announcements, and fostering community engagement through interactive content.

- **LinkedIn** allows HellasQCI to be presented in a more professional networking platform where the project's milestones, publications, and events are shared with industry professionals, academics, and other stakeholders.
- **YouTube** offers a visual and dynamic way to present the project's work, including interviews, project updates, and event recordings, making the project's outcomes more accessible to a wide audience.

Partner contributions to dissemination

In addition to these centralized efforts, all consortium partners actively contribute to the communication and dissemination of the project through their own networks and channels. This includes:

- Partners use their websites to highlight their involvement in the HellasQCI project, share news and updates, and link back to the project's main website for further information.
- Regular HellasQCI newsletters are circulated by partners to their networks, providing updates on the project's progress, upcoming events, and key achievements.
- Partners also leverage their social media presence to amplify the project's visibility, sharing content related to HellasQCI across their channels, and engaging with their followers on the project's developments.

A list of partners' channels is available in Annex F - Partners' online media channels.

This approach to digital communication ensures that the HellasQCI project maintains a strong online presence, engages with a diverse audience, and maximizes the impact of its dissemination activities across the quantum computing and cryptography communities and beyond.

2.3.1. Social media channels strategy

For the purposes of the project's communication activities, HellasQCI accounts were created on [Twitter](#), [LinkedIn](#), [Facebook](#) and [YouTube](#) at the early stages of the project, in order to support and promote the project's kick off meeting. The accounts are maintained and updated by NCSR D with contributions from WP6 partners. The social media accounts emphasize and strengthen the visual identity of the project by employing a cohesive visual identity based on the project's logo. The handling and updating of social media accounts' content are managed centrally by the WP6 leader with input from the rest of the partners and especially from the coordinating partner (GRNET).

A process has been devised by which suitable content that is to be uploaded on the social media accounts is first uploaded onto the project's messaging board on Microsoft teams, is evaluated for quality and suitability and whether it contains any sort of non-public and/or proprietary information regarding the project and is subsequently posted to the social media accounts. For generic posts regarding the project, and not a specific demonstration or use case of a single partner, the partner organizations accounts are tagged to maximize visibility and stimulate engagement and content sharing by the project's partners. To reach a wider targeted audience, the appropriate hashtags of the project are used with consistency, i.e.: **#HellasQCI, #QKD #QuantumCommunication**.

To promote the project’s results and overall progress, all social media accounts are linked to the project’s official website and vice versa. Furthermore, all digital and printed promotional materials (i.e. flyers, newsletters) mention the project’s social media channels.

The social media strategy follows four steps: **collect, share, engage, and measure**. For the collection part, all partners have the responsibility to collect and relay information regarding events, updates, milestones, and news that could be shared and disseminated. All consortium partners are involved in engaging with the content through, sharing, liking, and commenting on the content. Finally, the impact of the dissemination on social media is assessed at regular intervals (i.e. monthly and semi-annual) by monitoring the number of interactions per content posted on the different accounts aiming to reach a continuous increasing number of key stakeholders.

LinkedIn: (<https://www.linkedin.com/in/hellasqci/>), HellasQCI uses the platform to disseminate the project’s background and objectives, ambition and achievements to engage with professionals and experts in the field of quantum technologies, telecommunications, and cybersecurity. As LinkedIn allows for longer narratives with detailed descriptions about the project's progress it is ideal to communicate photos, GIFs, videos, links, and press releases from the project and its partners relating to the project activities as well as to communicate project updates, press releases and newsletters. **X (Twitter):** (@HellasQCI) is one of the most widely used platforms for communicating scientific results and interacting with the wider public. It is used to share short comments, make announcements that instantaneously reach a large audience, and retweet relevant content and links to publications and press releases. It is used to quickly engage with the communications of associated projects within the framework of the EuroQCI initiative as well as relevant technology standardization organizations and quantum technologies industry consortiums and the activities of the Quantum Flagship. Since there is a character limit in X, the posts are significantly shorter and serve as “nuggets” of information.

Facebook: (<https://www.facebook.com/hellasqci/>) is used mostly to communicate stimulating narratives about the project to engage the general public and foster an interest in the technologies and scientific concepts developed and utilized within the project in younger generations.

Figure 17: HellasQCI social media accounts

Dissemination and communication board members are encouraged to engage with the social media (Figure 17) posts by liking, sharing, or commenting from their company/institutional accounts to amplify and relay the information to their own audiences.

YouTube (<https://www.youtube.com/@hellasqci>): Throughout the duration of the project, several videos – related to the project’s activities were created, featuring interviews of project participants,

mainstream media coverage as well as lectures and talks about the project progress, ambition, and potential impact. Also, technical videos about the project's implementation are produced throughout the project's life cycle. These videos are collected and uploaded to the dedicated [YouTube](#) channel of HellasQCI that was created and maintained by GRNET. The dissemination and communication board members collect videos related to the project and forward them using the project's dedicated management tool, Microsoft teams, to be uploaded to the channel. The uploaded videos are disseminated and linked through the other social media channels ([Twitter](#), [LinkedIn](#), [Facebook](#)) and the [website](#).

2.3.2. Social media audience influence

The techniques for networking, interacting with important organizations, and keeping up with cybersecurity and quantum communication trends on social media, by following relevant entities, are explained in the following paragraphs.

Social media community building entails more than just one-way communication. It's all about interacting, exchanging, and connecting. Firstly, this can be achieved by contacting important stakeholders and project partners. Secondly, through interaction with related companies, associations, events, conferences, journals, and other projects in related fields. The use of tags and hashtags can increase the discoverability of the project's material. Interacting with others increases the projects' reach and aids in understanding the demands of stakeholders.

The community of interested people and organizations can be expanded by interacting with like-minded beneficiaries and drawing in each other's fan base and followers through actions like tagging, replying to, or following their posts. For this reason, it is important to follow and stay aligned with projects submitted under the same call, i.e., The Digital Europe Programme (DIGITAL), since there are shared goals, complementary outcomes, and similar target audiences.

To follow relevant entities with HellasQCI on social media involves several strategic steps. This process is crucial for staying informed about Quantum Communication and Cybersecurity industry trends, networking, and engaging with key influencers or organizations.

Here's a structured approach (Figure 18) that is being followed by the WP6 Leader (NCSR Innovation Office, knowledge management unit). This entity has extensive expertise in networking, dissemination, and exploitation activities.

Figure 18: Social media following methodology

2.4. Newsletters, press releases, periodicals (or media coverage)

2.4.1 Newsletters

To directly reach target audiences that have explicitly expressed an interest in being informed about the project's activities and progress, 8 newsletters were created and disseminated during the project lifespan at regular intervals.

The newsletters were disseminated every 6 months, covering the entirety of the project's duration. The content of the newsletters features news and views about the project from all the participating

organizations, detailing their relation to the overall concept of the project, their activities within and their ambition and vision for the deployed infrastructure. More specifically, until M42 8 biannual newsletters have been released.

The newsletters of HellasQCI from June 2024 to June 2026 collectively present a structured narrative of the project's evolution, with each issue focusing on distinct milestones. [Newsletter 3 \(June 2024\)](#) highlights the advancement of training activities, particularly the 3rd Training Event on Quantum Key Distribution (QKD), along with strengthened collaboration among Greek academic and industrial partners. [Newsletter 4 \(December 2024\)](#) shifts attention to infrastructure development and testing, while emphasizing Greece's active participation in European initiatives under EuroQCI. [Newsletter 5 \(February 2025\)](#) is dedicated to the successful organisation and impact of QCI Days Athens 2025, showcasing international engagement and knowledge exchange in the field of quantum communications. [Newsletter 6 \(October 2025\)](#) serves as an invitation and preview of the HellasQCI Winter School 2025, outlining its objectives, structure, and expected contribution to capacity building in quantum communication technologies. [Newsletter 7 \(December 2025\)](#) provides a comprehensive overview of achievements, including successful evaluations, expanded training and capacity-building activities, and Greece's increasingly significant role in the development of a secure, pan-European quantum communication infrastructure. Finally, [Newsletter 8 \(July 2026\)](#) focuses on the project's closing milestones, highlighting the launch of the SEEWQCI cross-border quantum communication initiative, Greece's expanding international presence through key events such as TNC26 and the ITU Regional Development Forum, and HellasQCI's lasting contribution to Europe's quantum communication ecosystem.

The timely assembly and delivery for the newsletters is handled by participants of T6.1, namely NCSR D (2), QUBITECH (2), and GRNET (1) and is designed to be consistent with the project's overall visual identity. For the development and dissemination of the project newsletter as well as any relevant promotion campaigns, an online promotion platform ([moosend](#)) is used to preserve the visual consistency throughout the project's duration.

[3rd newsletter](#)

The [3rd newsletter](#) (Figure 19) was released in June 2024, covering news and updates from January 2024 to June 2024.

This is the 3rd HellasQCI Newsletter
 Here you'll find all the latest progress and updates of the project.
 Browse through the newsletter to find more information and follow us on our social media to stay updated on the latest news.

HellasQCI 3rd Training Event, Heraklion, Crete 4-5 September 2024

The HellasQCI 3rd Training Event on Quantum Key Distribution (QKD) and Cyber Security will be held in Heraklion, Crete. This event will gather experts, researchers, and enthusiasts to explore the latest advancements in quantum key distribution and its applications in enhancing cybersecurity. The event is **HYBRID** and will take place on September 4-5, 2024.

QCI Days 2025, Athens 28-30 April 2025

Following the success of QKD Days 2022 in Madrid and QCI Days 2024 in Vienna, HellasQCI, a project coordinated by The National Infrastructures for Research and Technology – GRNET, is delighted to announce the upcoming QCI Days in Athens-Greece, on April 28-30, 2025.

HellasQCI and NOKIA lead way to the future of Quantum-Safe Networks

HellasQCI project participated at NOKIA's Wavelengths 2024 event in Athens, Greece. The event served as an excellent opportunity to showcase the progress achieved in the HellasQCI project, including the groundbreaking Proof of Concept (PoC) implemented by HellasQCI (GRNET, NKUA) in partnership with Nokia, EvolutionIQ, and IDQ, April 22-24, 2024.

Quantum-Secure FTTH Infrastructure Going Practical: Integration Experiments in HellasQCI

In the context of HellasQCI Phase 0 activities, integration scenarios and feasibility analysis of DV-QKD systems into Fiber to the Home (FTTH) infrastructures were experimentally investigated for applications considered in urban metropolitan areas, March 12, 2024.

Announcing HellasQCI's New Training Platform!

The HellasQCI project has a new Training Platform for academics, researchers, IT professionals and public, which educates on QKD technologies and cybersecurity.

Figure 19: 3rd HellasQCI newsletter

4th newsletter

The 4th newsletter was released on 4th July 2024, covering news and updates from July 2024 to December 2024 (Figure 20).

The HellasQCI Project Consortium wishes health and prosperity to all Quantum Communication Infrastructure communities. May the future hold the promise of a quantum-secure digital landscape.

QCI Days Athens 2025
April 28-30, 2025

The National Quantum Communication Infrastructures (NatQCI)s projects of Greece (HellasQCI), Spain (EuroQCI Spain), and Austria (QCI-CAT) invite you to an engaging event in Athens, Europe's historical capital. Organized by GRNET (HellasQCI coordinator), AIT Austrian Institute of Technology (QCI-CAT coordinator) and UPM – The Technical University of Madrid (EuroQCI Spain coordinator), and held under the auspices of the Hellenic Ministry of Digital Governance, this event will showcase advancements in quantum communication technologies, including live demonstration of quantum-secure communication technologies and related use-cases from National Quantum Communication Infrastructures.

TRAINING EVENT IN CRETE 2024

2 DAYS OF SCIENTIFIC MEETS | 1st EUROQCI COOPERATION | 2nd QKD+PQC THE CYBERSECURITY

2 LABS | 2 DEMOS | 40 SPEAKERS | 4 PANELS

415 ATTENDEES | 50 PEOPLE VISITED THE SKINAKAS OBSERVATORY

126 QCI QCI | 289 QCI QCI

14 COUNTRIES PARTICIPATED

READ THE ASSESSMENT REPORT

Milestone:
Arrival of Key Quantum Communication Equipment for the HellasQCI testbeds and QKD backbone networks

The HellasQCI/GRNET Quantum Key Distribution (QKD) devices, and Superconducting Nanowire Single-Photon Detectors (SNSPDs) have started arriving at the HellasQCI consortium, marking a significant milestone for the project. This state-of-the-art quantum communication equipment establishes a powerful testbed for researchers, academia, and industry, equipping them with the tools and opportunities to explore, experiment with, and integrate emerging quantum communication technologies into real-world applications.

HellasQCI Training Event Crete 2024
September 4-5, 2024

415 scientists participated in a comprehensive two-day training event focused on Quantum Communication Technologies and Cybersecurity. Organized by GRNET and the Foundation for Research and Technology - Hellas (FORTH), the event aimed to **enhance quantum secure communication capabilities** for Greece and Europe. The training offered in-depth knowledge and hands-on experience in cutting-edge quantum technologies and advanced cybersecurity practices

REGISTER TO WATCH THE ONLINE TRAINING COURSE

Milestone:
Arrival of Key Quantum Communication Equipment for the HellasQCI testbeds and QKD backbone networks

The HellasQCI/GRNET Quantum Key Distribution (QKD) devices, and Superconducting Nanowire Single-Photon Detectors (SNSPDs) have started arriving at the HellasQCI consortium, marking a significant milestone for the project. This state-of-the-art quantum communication equipment establishes a powerful testbed for researchers, academia, and industry, equipping them with the tools and opportunities to explore, experiment with, and integrate emerging quantum communication technologies into real-world applications.

This cutting-edge infrastructure will play a pivotal role in the development and testing of advanced use cases, which are currently in preparation. Together with the delivery of the fiber infrastructure next year, this equipment will be used to form the experimental QKD backbone networks of the HellasQCI Infrastructure in Greece.

ThinkQuantum and ID Quantique complete end-users' and IT experts' training for the HellasQI consortium
October 1-2, 2024

ThinkQuantum and ID Quantique conducted two trainings for the HellasQCI project consortium. ThinkQuantum training took place on 18-19 September 2024, and ID Quantique followed with a training on 1-2 October 2024. Both sessions provided essential theoretical and practical guidance on deploying and using their QKD devices within the HellasQCI project. Find out more about these impactful training sessions and their role in advancing quantum communication!

Figure 20: 4th HellasQCI newsletter

5th newsletter

The 5th newsletter was released in February 2025, announcing “QCI Days Athens 2025”, the **captivating event** that took place in **Athens**, the historical capital of Europe between **28-30 April 2025** (Figure 21).

Figure 21 QCI Days Athens 2025 newsletter

6th newsletter

The 6th newsletter was released in October 2025, announcing the launching of the **HellasQCI Winter School (Training Workshop) 2025**, in Thessaloniki; a free three-day training workshop on **Quantum Key Distribution (QKD)** and **Space-based QKD technologies**, combining theory, hands-on lab experience, and expert-led sessions (Figure 22).

Figure 22: HellasQCI Winter School (Training Workshop) 2025 newsletter

7th newsletter

The 7th newsletter was released in December 2025, covering news and updates from February 2025 to December 2025 (Figure 23).

Figure 23: 7th HellasQCI newsletter

8th newsletter

The 8th newsletter was released in July 2026, covering news and updates from January 2026 to June 2026. The newsletter presents HellasQCI and SEEWQCI activities supporting the development of the EuroQCI, highlighting cross-border collaboration, major project kick-offs, and participation in international events. It also summarizes key partnerships, use cases, and Greece’s growing role in Europe’s quantum communication infrastructure ecosystem. (Figure 24).

Figure 24 8th HellasQCI Newsletter

2.4.2 Press-releases

The press releases of HellasQCI each highlight a distinct milestone in the project’s development and international positioning. The [Nokia Proof of Concept press release](#) (18 December 2023) focuses on the successful validation of quantum communication technologies through collaboration with industry, demonstrating tangible progress toward secure infrastructure. The [Training Event in Crete \(2024\) press release](#) (19 September 2024) emphasizes capacity building, presenting the outcomes of a hands-on workshop that strengthened technical expertise and stakeholder engagement at the national level. The [announcement of QCI Days Athens 2025](#) (April 2025) highlights Athens as host of a major European event, reinforcing Greece’s role as a hub for collaboration and knowledge exchange in quantum communications. This is further reinforced by the dedicated article [“Greece at the forefront of Europe’s journey toward a secure and quantum-innovative digital future”](#) (May 2025), which underlines Greece’s leading role in the EuroQCI and the strategic importance of hosting such a flagship event for shaping Europe’s secure digital future. The [press release on the double European distinction for the SEEWQCI and TransEuroOGS](#) (8 August 2025) projects underlines international recognition, showcasing how these initiatives contribute to the broader EuroQCI and position Greece at the forefront of quantum communication developments in Europe. Finally, the press release: [A Greek First: Quantum-Secure Technologies Deployed in a Hospital Environment](#) (February 2026)

describes the first deployment of quantum-secure communication technologies in a Greek hospital, using advanced encryption methods to protect sensitive medical data.

2.4.3 Coverage in media

The press coverage of HellasQCI is extensive and spans a wide range of national and international media, reflecting both its technological importance and strategic relevance. Dedicated coverage pages such as [HellasQCI in the press](#) aggregate dozens of articles from outlets including [CNN Greece](#), [Capital.gr](#), [Netweek](#), [Action24](#), [ERT](#) and the [Athens-Macedonian News Agency](#), many of which focus on flagship events like QCI Days Athens 2025 and emphasize Greece's leading role in quantum-secure communications. Earlier foundational coverage, such as [this Business Daily article](#) (19 January 2023) and [this Imerisia report](#) (19 January 2023), highlights the launch of the project and its integration into the European EuroQCI, underlining its importance for protecting critical infrastructure and sensitive data. In parallel, international technology media such as [Computer Weekly's coverage of the Nokia PoC](#) (19 December 2023) report on concrete technical achievements, including the successful demonstration of quantum-safe networks. These articles illustrate how HellasQCI is portrayed in the press not only as a research initiative, but as a key pillar of Greece's digital transformation and a significant contributor to Europe's emerging quantum communication ecosystem. A review and analysis of the media articles published throughout the project were conducted in order to assess the communication reach and visibility of HellasQCI. The complete collection of media articles is available at the following [link](#).

2.5. Infographics

The [HellasQCI infographics](#) (Figure 25) primarily communicate the project's progress through key quantitative indicators and milestone-driven visuals, turning development updates into an easily understandable snapshot of implementation status. Rather than focusing on technical explanations, they highlight measurable aspects such as the advancement of network deployment, the expansion of quantum-secured nodes, the establishment of metro quantum networks in key cities, and the integration steps toward a wider national and European quantum communication infrastructure. The infographics function as a progress dashboard, allowing stakeholders and the public to track how HellasQCI is evolving in line with its objectives within the broader EuroQCI framework. The infographics were posted on the website's Newsfeed page and on social media (Facebook, Twitter, and LinkedIn).

Figure 25 HellasQCI Infographics

3. Dissemination and communication activities – HellasQCI offline presence

Dissemination and communication offline activities involve strategies and actions taken outside of the project’s digital platforms to engage with stakeholders, raise awareness, and share project achievements. In the following sections, the offline presence of HellasQCI is presented.

3.1. Dissemination and communication activities overview

The project's communication initiatives are intended to provide technical objectives and scientific results, emphasize anticipated advantages, and engage with the general public and key stakeholders. These activities are performed by consortium partners and individual partners through their own channels of communication and dissemination. The implementation activities corresponding to the Dissemination and Communication plan described in [Deliverable D6.1 Dissemination, exploitation, and communication plan](#) are shown by category in the following tables (Table 1) and (Table 2):

Dissemination activities	Number
Clustering & Synergies	18
Conferences	15
Scientific Publications	37
Public Deliverables	8
Training Events	6

Table 1: Number of dissemination activities

Communication activities	Number
Events Organised	11
Events Participated	58
Project Meetings	10
Media Articles	326
Newsletters	8
Press Release	6
Promotional Material	16
HellasQCI Videos	5

Table 2: Number of communication activities

In the following table (Table 3) the total number of dissemination activities is provided, categorized by type. All activities are further analyzed in the following sections.

Dissemination activity	Dissemination activity name	
Clustering & Synergies: 18	Quantum Communication Innovation Forum (Bilbao, Spain) Quantum Secure Networks Partnership (EU-HE-QSNP) LaiQa project IrelandQCI Kick-off meeting World Quantum Day TNC23 QCI Days Vienna 2024, Austria PTQCI Quantum Communication Networks, Aveiro	Malta's National QCI Online Kick-off 3rd RoNaQCI Workshop Iasi QCI Ireland Event 1st Iberian QCI Workshop National QCI.DK Workshop PRISM Quantum Week, Malta GÉANT TNC24 Rennes, France GÉANT infoshare in the context of EuroQCI QT Pathfinder Heisingberg QCI Connect 2025 in Estonia
Conferences: 15	6th Annual ScyLight Conference ETSI/IQC Quantum Safe Cryptography Event GRNOG15 Wavelengths NOKIA 12th CAPTECH Cyber Meeting (Space Hellas) ECOC2024 Frankfurt 15th ICSO2024 Antibes France	ETWG Workshop Brussels Belgium Migration to Quantum Safe Workshop, Austria TNC24 Rennes, France GÉANT infoshare in the context of EuroQCI TCN25 Brighton, UK CEPT Conference ECOC 2025 Conference, TCN26
Scientific Publications: 37	https://hellasqci.eu/scientific-publications/	
Public Deliverables: 8	HellasQCI Community (Zenodo)	
Training Events: 6	HellasQCI Training Event Athens 2023 HellasQCI Training Event Crete 2024	ThinkQuantum: Training on QUKY QKD devices ID Quantique: Training on Clavis XG QKD devices SNSPDs Training Workshop, HellasQCI Winter School (Training Workshop)

Table 3: Dissemination activities

In the following table (Table 4) the total number of Communication activities is provided, categorized by type. All activities are further analyzed in the following sections.

Communication Channel	Communication Activity Name	
Events Organised: 11	HellasQCI Kick off meeting , 6th Annual ScyLight Conference Workshop - Quantum Internet , TIF87 HellasQCI Training Event Athens 2023 , HellasQCI Training Event Crete 2024 ,	ThinkQuantum: Training on QUKY QKD , Quantique: Training on Clavis XG QKD , SNSPDs Training Workshop , QCI Days Athens 2025 , TIF89 HellasQCI Winter School (Training Workshop) Thessaloniki 2025
Events Participated: 58	9th ETSI IQC Quantum Safe Cryptography Event , 3rd Ubitech Innovation Days , World Quantum Day (InfoSession) , IrelandQCI kick-off meeting , NOKIA Wavelengths 2024 , TNC23 (GÉANT) , CEN/CENELEC Joint Technical Committee JTC 22 , GRNOG15 , Quantum Communication Innovation Forum by EUROQCI Spain , European Thematic Working Groups (ETWG) , QCI Days Vienna 2024 , Malta Kick off meeting , 7th Annual ScyLight Conference & 2nd Quantum Workshop , PTQCI Workshop , Nokia Wavelengths EMEA-LAT 2024 , Switzerland – Greece Space Networking Event ,	TNC24 (GÉANT) , RoNaQCI Workshop , EDA 12th CAPTECH CYBER MEETING , QCI Ireland Event , Quantum Communications Event in Dublin , GÉANT InfoShare , ECOC24 , 1st Iberian QCI Workshop , QCI.DK Workshop , ICSO 2024 , Migration to Quantum-Safe Workshop , ETWG Workshop , PRISM Quantum Week , TNC25 , WSIS+20 Forum , TIF89 , QCI Connect Forum , ITU-T SG20 , TNC26 REXQCS & ROGS Kick-off Meeting , ITU Regional Development Forum , SBIQCI Kick-off , Q-PrEP Workshops , BEYOND 2026
Project Meetings: 10	HellasQCI Kick off meeting DEP call Kick off meeting 1st Review Meeting, 2nd Review Meeting 6 PMB Meetings	
Media Articles: 326	HellasQCI Kick-off meeting Media Articles , Nokia Proof Of Concept Media Articles , HellasQCI: theoretical and practical knowledge in the quantum technologies seminar ALPHA TV Dnews , Forbes , NIST Training Event in Crete 2024 • Euro2Day , • SKAIKRITIS.GR , • KINHTA NEA , • Dnews , • epixeiro.gr , • creta.gr , • politikakritis.gr , • pna.gr , • tomanifesto.gr , • ictplus.gr	A Greek First: Quantum-Secure Technologies Deployed in a Hospital Environment Business Daily • Politic.gr • Politica.gr • Health Daily • Greek City Times QCI Days 2025 • myportal , • eidiseis.gr , • powergame.gr , • eidhseis365.gr , • businessnews.gr , • mononews , • newsit , • fibernews , • defencepoint
Newsletter: 8	HellasQCI Newsletter #1 • June 2023 , HellasQCI Newsletter #2 • December 2023 , HellasQCI Newsletter #3 • June 2024 , HellasQCI , HellasQCI Newsletter #4 • December 2024 , QCI Days Athens 2025 ,	
Press Releases: 6	HellasQCI Kick-off Meeting Press Release Nokia Proof Of Concept Press Release Training Event Crete 2024 Athens hosting QCI Days 2025 & QCI Days Athens 2025 ,	Greece at the Forefront of Quantum Communications in Europe – Double European Distinction for the New SEEWQCI and TransEuroOGS Projects A Greek First: Quantum-Secure Technologies Deployed in a Hospital Environment
Promotional Material: 16	Project Media Kit , marketing collaterals for HellasQCI-led events [promotional material photos on slide number 5] , HellasQCI Project Booklet	

Communication Channel	Communication Activity Name
HellasQCI Videos: 5	Videos (GR, EN) HellasQCI Winter School Day 1 HellasQCI Winter School Day 2 Highlights from the HellasQCI Winter School 2025
Digital Communication Channels: 5	Social Media Channels (Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, Youtube) & Website

Table 4: Communication activities

3.2. HellasQCI events (organised, participated, liaison activities)

A way to enhance engagement with the project from potential stakeholders and target audiences is to actively participate in relevant events, thematic panels, workshops, conferences, poster presentations, specialized exhibitions, and demonstrations. All partners are encouraged to participate in such events to enhance the visibility of the project and its activities, establish collaborations, showcase the project's achievements, liaise, and interact with identified stakeholders. During these events, partners circulate prepared dissemination material (e.g., brochures, leaflets, etc.) to fellow participants.

Project partners actively contribute to identifying external events of interest to the consortium. Dissemination and communication board members are responsible for overseeing and update the list of the local events that their organization has participated in. The list of events is available in the project's online repository available through Microsoft teams as a live document. Consortium partners are asked to update their relevant contributions promptly for quality control monitoring and reporting of the project's dissemination activities. An indicative list of events is available at the end of this report as Annex A - Dissemination activities.

3.2.1. Events organised by HellasQCI

Within the framework of Work Package 6, a comprehensive process was implemented to support the visibility, engagement and effectiveness of HellasQCI various events. This approach was designed to promote these events and enhance their impact within the community. A breakdown of the actions taken is following (Figure 26):

1. The **planning stage** lays the groundwork for the entire event communication process. At this point, organizers clearly define the event's purpose, identify the target audience, and decide on the time and location. This step ensures that all communication efforts are aligned with a specific goal, whether it is raising awareness, driving attendance, or achieving a particular outcome
2. During the **pre-event phase**, the focus shifts to generating interest and attracting participants. This involves creating compelling promotional materials such as banners, social media posts, and email campaigns. Outreach efforts extend to media and press to increase visibility, while invitations are distributed to the intended audience.
3. **While the event is taking place**, communication becomes dynamic and real-time. Organizers capture photos and videos, share live updates, and highlight key moments to keep both

attendees and online audiences engaged. Interaction with media and active audience participation are encouraged to amplify the event’s reach.

4. **After the event concludes**, communication efforts focus on extending its impact. Organizers produce post-event content such as summaries, reports, and visual materials to showcase outcomes and key messages. Media coverage is tracked, and relevant materials may be shared on platforms for broader access. Certificates of attendance or participation are also distributed, reinforcing engagement and providing lasting value to participants.
5. The final stage centers on **assessing the effectiveness of the event** and its communication strategies. Organizers review audiovisual content, analyze marketing data, and gather feedback from participants. These insights help identify strengths and areas for improvement, providing valuable guidance for future events. This step closes the cycle by turning experience into actionable knowledge for continuous improvement.

Figure 26: Cycle of communication activities for an Event

HellasQCI Training Event Crete 2024

The HellasQCI project held [Training Event in Crete](#) from September 4 to 5, 2024, at the Foundation for Research and Technology - Hellas (FORTH) Institute of Computer Science Heraklion, Crete. The Training was designed to train the new generation of engineers in quantum technologies and cybersecurity, allowing Greece and other countries to be ready for the operation of the European Quantum Communications Infrastructure – EuroQCI.

During the two-day HellasQCI Training Event two labs were held: (a) Experiment Polarisation-Encoded QKD, (b) Extracting and Managing Keys from QKD to Enhance Cryptographic Techniques for File Encryption, and two demos: (a) Demo of QKD Networks (b) Demo of Polarisation-Encoded QKD in Virtual Lab.

The registered participants visited Skinakas Observatory. The visitors had the opportunity to explore the advanced facilities and gained insights into the cutting-edge work being conducted by leading

scientists in the field. Moreover, they learned more about the involvement of the Observatory in the HellasQCI project, as well as the future plans for space-to-ground encrypted telecom activities.

A full report is provided in Annex D - HellasQCI Training Event in Crete 2024.

QCI Days Athens 2025

Greece took a leading role in the pan-European EuroQCI initiative by hosting the prominent international [QCI Days 2025](#) conference in **Athens**, from April 28 to 30, 2025, at the Eugenides Foundation. The event was supported by the **Ministry of Digital Governance, under the guidance of the General Secretariat of Telecommunications and Post**, as part of the **International Year of Quantum Science and Technology (IYQ)** and **World Quantum Day 2025**. A full press release is provided in Annex C - QCI Days Athens 2025 press release. The QCI Days Athens 2025 communication campaign was implemented through five sequential phases (planning, pre-event promotion, during-event communication, post-event dissemination, and evaluation), resulting in the production of over 20 communication assets, comprehensive impact reporting, and **52 press clippings**, demonstrating the event's extensive national and international media outreach (Figure 27).

Figure 27: Cycle of Communication Activities: Case-Study QCI Days 2025

HellasQCI Winter School Thessaloniki 2025

The HellasQCI project held [Winter School in Thessaloniki](#) from November 26 to 28th, 2025, at Aristotle University Research Dissemination Center (KEDEA), WinPhoS Center for Interdisciplinary Research and Innovation (CIRI – AUTH) and NOESIS Thessaloniki Science Center & Technology Museum. The HellasQCI Winter School 2025 was addressed to Cybersecurity and IT experts, Quantum Physics students & early-stage researchers in quantum, ICT, and engineering, Scientists and university

faculty members, National QCI representatives, policymakers, and stakeholders from governmental institutions involved in the security of critical infrastructure and sensitive data.

During the three-day HellasQCI Winter School – Training Workshop three labs were held: (a) Building Blocks for QKD I, (b) Building Blocks for QKD II, c) Building Blocks for QKD III.

Day 1 focused on strategy, national initiatives, and industry perspectives across Europe, highlighting collaboration and deployment plans. Day 2 explored the theory and technologies behind space-based QKD and optical ground stations, including satellite systems and key enabling components. A live QKD network demo showcased real-world secure communications using quantum keys. Day 3 emphasized hands-on training and practical experiments, concluding with a satellite tracking demonstration linking terrestrial and space quantum infrastructure.

A full report is provided in Annex E - HellasQCI Winter School Training Workshop Thessaloniki 2025.

ThinkQuantum: Training on QUKEY QKD

The ThinkQuantum training within the HellasQCI project focused specifically on the QUKEY Quantum Key Distribution (QKD) devices, delivering both theoretical knowledge and hands-on experience on their deployment and operation. Conducted on 18–19 September 2024 at GRNET and the National and Kapodistrian University of Athens, the sessions aimed to train technical staff and end users of the consortium to effectively use the acquired ThinkQuantum equipment for real-world quantum communication use cases. The programme combined presentations, live demonstrations, and interactive discussions, attracting strong participation from consortium members, with **55 attendees on the first day (25 in person and 30 online)** and **52 attendees on the second day (30 in person and 22 online)**

iQuantique: Training on Clavis XG QKD

The ID Quantique training within the HellasQCI project focused on the Clavis XG Quantum Key Distribution (QKD) system and was held on 1–2 October 2024 at the premises of GRNET and the National and Kapodistrian University of Athens. It aimed to provide both theoretical and hands-on instruction to technical staff and end users, enabling them to deploy, operate, and manage the Clavis XG devices effectively within real-world quantum communication infrastructures. The event was delivered **over two days** and attracted strong participation, with **36 attendees on the first day (18 in person and 18 online)** and **39 attendees on the second day (21 in person and 18 online)**.

SNSPDs Training Workshop, by Single Quantum

The HellasQCI SNSPDs Training Workshop, which was held on 6 February 2025 and delivered by Single Quantum, focused on both the theoretical and practical training of consortium members in the use of superconducting nanowire single-photon detectors (SNSPDs). Hosted at the National and Kapodistrian University of Athens with hybrid participation, the workshop included technical presentations, system-level analysis, and a live laboratory demonstration. Particular emphasis was placed on operating principles, software control, maintenance procedures, and troubleshooting, highlighting the critical role of SNSPDs in

enabling advanced quantum communication applications such as the future quantum internet. The workshop was attended by **35 participants**, including **20 participants in person** and **15 participants online**, demonstrating strong engagement from consortium members.

89th Thessaloniki International Fair

At the 89th Thessaloniki International Fair from September 6 to 14, 2025, HellasQCI participated in a high-level panel titled “Building the Future of Quantum Technologies in Greece,” co-organized by the General Secretariat of Telecommunications and Posts and GRNET. The event brought together key stakeholders from government, academia, research, and industry—including institutions such as NKUA, AUTH, NTUA, FORTH, and Demokritos—to discuss the latest developments in quantum communication technologies and their impact on Greece’s digital security and innovation landscape. The panel (Figure 28) emphasized the strategic importance of collaboration, resilient infrastructure, and national investment in quantum technologies, highlighting how initiatives like HellasQCI can position Greece at the forefront of secure communications and protect critical data and assets.

Figure 28 HellasQCI in the 89th Thessaloniki International Fair

HellasQCI PMB meetings

During the period M16 to M42 project meetings were held, and the WP6 team participated and presented the activities. These meetings were organised to share important updates and communicate the results among the consortium members and EC.

4th PMB: The 4th PMB was held on the 8th of September 2024 in Heraklion, Crete.

5th PMB: The 5th PMB was held on the 12th of May 2025 in Athens.

6th PBM: The 6th PMB was held on the of 25th of November 2025

HellasQCI Review meetings

1st Review Meeting: The 1st Review Meeting was held on the 14th of March 2024 in Athens

2nd Review Meeting: The 2nd review meeting was held on the 27th of June 2025

3rd Review Meeting: The 3rd review meeting will be held on the 7th of October 2026

3.2.2. Events participation

HellasQCI has implemented an extensive dissemination and communication strategy through participation in workshops, conferences, exhibitions, technical meetings, training activities, and stakeholder engagement events, aiming to promote project results and strengthen collaboration within the European quantum communications ecosystem. In accordance with [Deliverable D6.1](#) “Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Activities Plan”, the HellasQCI consortium actively participated in events and meetings organized by the Quantum Flagship, EuroQCI, other National Quantum Communication Infrastructure (NatQCI) projects, GÉANT, PETRUS CSA, and related European initiatives.

During the reporting period, HellasQCI representatives contributed to major European events including those included in the following table (Table 5) These participations enabled the consortium to present project progress, exchange technical expertise and lessons learned, discuss deployment and interoperability challenges, and strengthen cooperation with European partners toward the implementation of a secure pan-European quantum communication infrastructure. A list of these events is provided in the following table, including the impact these events had on the project.

EVENT	DATE	VENUE	AUDIENCE SIZE	IMPACT
TNC25	9-13 June 2025	Brighton, United Kingdom	500+	EuroQCI integration; enabled technical discussions on quantum-safe networking and cross-border QKD interoperability within the GÉANT ecosystem.
TNC26	8-12 June 2026		500+	Continued positioning of HellasQCI within European backbone networking evolution; supports transition toward operational EuroQCI infrastructure via NREN collaboration.
QCI Connect 2025 (Estonia)	16–17 Sept 2025	Tallinn, Estonia	120	Reinforced HellasQCI role in EuroQCI coordination; enabled exchange of deployment lessons and interoperability approaches across national QCIs
PRISM Quantum Week	5 December 2024	Malta	300	Provided visibility of HellasQCI QKD/PQC validation work; strengthened links with EU Commission, industry (AWS, Toshiba, Huawei), and other NatQCIs for knowledge exchange

EVENT	DATE	VENUE	AUDIENCE SIZE	IMPACT
1st Iberian QCI Workshop	4 October 2024	Aveiro, Portugal	100	Supported early-stage coordination between HellasQCI and Iberian QCIs; contributed to harmonisation of EuroQCI deployment strategies.
GÉANT Infoshare sessions (EuroQCI context)	25 September 2024	Online / GÉANT network	Pan-European research education & community	Enabled technical dissemination of HellasQCI outcomes to NRENs; strengthened integration with GÉANT backbone for future secure quantum networking.
ECOC 2025 (European Conference on Optical Communication)	28 September to 2 October	Copenhagen	500+	Positioned HellasQCI within optical communications ecosystem; supported engagement on QKD hardware, photonics integration, and telecom standardization.
World Telecommunication Development Conference (WTDC) 2025	17 to 28 November 2025	<i>Baku, Republic of Azerbaijan</i>	500+	Elevated HellasQCI relevance in global telecom policy discussions; contributed to framing quantum-secure communications in international digital infrastructure agendas.
ITU-T SG20	12 to 14 May 2026	<i>Geneva</i>	100	Increased the international visibility of Greece's quantum communication initiatives. It facilitated engagement with global standards experts, policymakers, and industry stakeholders involved in future quantum network development. Strengthened collaboration opportunities and supported the alignment of HellasQCI activities with emerging international standards for secure quantum communications.

Table 5: Events and Impact

The WP6 leader has continuously collected and disseminated information related to project activities through the official project website, newsletters, social media channels, and dissemination material. Event participation records, dissemination metrics, feedback, and supporting material are maintained in the consortium Dissemination & Communication activities log; a live document hosted in the project's private repository. A detailed list of events is provided in the Annex B - Communication activities.

3.2.3. Collaboration activities

[QCI Days Athens 2025](#)

In the framework of HellasQCI, the [QCI Days 2025](#) event was organized in Athens, bringing together the European and international quantum communication community to discuss the future of secure quantum infrastructures. Held under the auspices of the Greek Ministry of Digital Governance, the event gathered more than 600 participants from over 30 countries, featuring technical sessions, panel discussions, training activities, and live cross-border Quantum Key Distribution (QKD) demonstrations between Greece, Austria, and Spain. Through the participation of researchers, policymakers, industry representatives, and NatQCI projects, QCI Days 2025 highlighted Greece's leading role in the EuroQCI initiative and strengthened collaboration toward a secure and quantum-enabled European digital future.

[TNC24 Rennes, France](#)

HellasQCI participated in the [TNC24](#), Europe's leading research and education networking conference, where representatives from GRNET and NTUA engaged with other European NatQCI projects and NRENs. Discussions focused on the deployment of quantum key distribution (QKD) networks, technical challenges, and future collaborations within the EuroQCI initiative. The participation highlighted Greece's contribution to advancing secure and interoperable quantum communication infrastructures across Europe. HellasQCI also strengthened cooperation with partners from Ireland, Poland, Hungary, and Cyprus toward building a connected European quantum ecosystem.

[TNC25 Brighton, UK](#)

HellasQCI, coordinated by GRNET, participated in the [TNC25](#), Europe's leading research and education networking conference, contributing to discussions on Europe's quantum-secure future. Dr. Ilias Papastamatiou chaired the session "Building the Quantum Future: NRENs at the Forefront", highlighting the role of National Research and Education Networks in deploying secure and interoperable quantum communication infrastructures. The participation showcased Greece's progress in the EuroQCI initiative and emphasized the importance of cross-border collaboration and real-world QKD deployment. The event also strengthened cooperation between European NRENs and reinforced HellasQCI's contribution to the development of Europe's quantum communication ecosystem.

[TNC26 Helsinki, Finland](#)

HellasQCI, coordinated by GRNET, participated in [TNC26](#), Europe's leading research and education networking conference, contributing to discussions on Europe's quantum-secure future. There, Dr. Ilias Papastamatiou (GRNET), as Chair of the GÉANT Quantum Strategy Coordination Group (QSCG), chaired and co-presented at the Birds of a Feather session "Quantum Technologies for NRENs", which drew a full auditorium and outstanding engagement from the GÉANT community. The session brought together speakers from across Europe's NRENs - including GÉANT, GRNET, PCSS (Poland), SURF (Netherlands) and IMCS (Latvia) - to explore the growing role of National Research and Education Networks in shaping Europe's quantum future. A recent QSCG mapping exercise presented at the session identified 23 NRENs participating in 55 quantum-related projects, underlining how research and education networks are becoming key enablers of Europe's quantum ecosystem. The participation showcased Greece's progress in the EuroQCI initiative and reinforced HellasQCI's contribution to strengthening strategic coordination, sharing expertise, and accelerating the adoption of quantum technologies across the continent.

HellasQCI Community Joint Statement

A key outcome of the HellasQCI community was the publication of the [HellasQCI Community Joint Statement](#), a formal document reflecting the shared commitment of national stakeholders to the advancement of quantum communication technologies in Greece. The statement was developed collaboratively with representatives from academia, industry, public authorities, and research institutions engaged through the HellasQCI community, and underlines the strategic importance of quantum-secure communication infrastructure for Greece's digital future. It represents a concrete milestone in the establishment of a sustainable national ecosystem around the HellasQCI network, beyond the project's lifetime.

3.2.4. Collaboration with EU funded projects

The project aimed at establishing synergies and coordination with similar EU projects on Quantum Communication. HellasQCI communicated and interacted with the European Initiative on Quantum Communication Infrastructure (EuroQCI) through the dedicated CSA project PETRUS to streamline communication, standardization and training activities when possible and to enhance coordination and transfer of knowledge and best practices between NatQCI projects. HellasQCI, through GRNET and the Ministry of Digital Governance, successfully forged **seven partnerships (Letters of Support – LoS)** during the proposal phase with National Quantum Communication Infrastructures (NatQCIs) in Austria, Luxembourg, Bulgaria, Cyprus, Malta, Poland, and Ireland.

IrelandQCI (Coordinated by Waterford Institute of Technology) and Lux4QCI (Coordinated by the University of Luxembourg) became Associated Partners of HellasQCI project and vice versa GRNET became Associated Partner to the IrelandQCI and LuxQCI projects, actively participating in various activities and to the Project Management Board meetings.

Moreover, **HellasQCI** has established close collaboration with several National QCIs (National Quantum Communication Infrastructures) of European member states including Poland (**PIONIER-Q**), Ireland (**IrelandQCI**), Croatia (**CroQCI**), Romania (**RoNaQCI**), Czech Republic (**CZQCI**). Austria (**QCI-Cat**), Luxembourg (**Lux4QCI**), Bulgaria (**BG National QCI Plan**), Cyprus (**CYQCI**) and Malta (**PRISM**).

Building on HellasQCI's contributions to the European quantum ecosystem, GRNET was appointed in November 2025 as Chair of the GÉANT Quantum Coordination Strategy Group, established to coordinate strategic discussions on quantum technologies across GÉANT and its National Research and Education Networks.

A comprehensive overview of HellasQCI's participation in EuroQCI activities and collaboration with other DIGITAL projects is presented in Deliverable D2.5, "Report on the participation on the EuroQCI initiative and on the collaboration with other DIGITAL projects". The deliverable consolidates HellasQCI's participation in EuroQCI-related events and collaborative activities from January 2023 to June 2026, documenting the project's evolution from an early participant in the European quantum communications community to a recognised contributor, convener, and host of major EuroQCI initiatives. It also highlights the extensive cross-border cooperation established with National QCI projects, European organisations, and key stakeholders, which laid the foundation for follow-up initiatives such as SEEWQCI and TransEuroOGS and further strengthened Greece's position within the European quantum communication landscape.

QCI Connect 2025 in Estonia (16–17 September 2025)

HellasQCI, represented by GRNET and NKUA, participated in the QCI Connect Forum held on 16–17 September 2025, joining experts from 14 NatQCI projects across 17 countries. The team contributed to discussions on QKD pilot implementations, technical and regulatory challenges, and integration with existing infrastructure. They also shared insights on deployment experiences and future cross-border connectivity plans within the EuroQCI framework. The forum reinforced collaboration across Europe toward building an operational pan-European quantum communication infrastructure.

GÉANT infoshare in the context of EuroQCI (25 September 2024)

GRNET and the GÉANT Infoshare on EuroQCI featured HellasQCI as part of discussions on national Quantum Communication Infrastructures within the EuroQCI initiative. Dr. Evangelia Athanasaki presented the deployment progress of HellasQCI, highlighting implementation challenges, lessons learned, and future development plans for Greece’s national QCI network. The event also enabled knowledge exchange with other European initiatives, including Romania’s RoNaQCI project. Through its participation, HellasQCI contributed to strengthening collaboration and sharing best practices among European NRENs and QCI stakeholders.

PRISM Quantum Week, Malta (2 -5 December 2024)

HellasQCI participated in PRISM Quantum Week, held at the University of Malta under the auspices of the PRISM EuroQCI initiative, bringing together policymakers, researchers, industry leaders, and national EuroQCI projects to discuss advancements in quantum-secure communications. HellasQCI was represented by Dr. Homer Papadopoulos from NCSR Demokritos, who presented the project’s key developments and the progress of QKD-PQC validation trials alongside representatives from other European NatQCI initiatives. The event provided an important platform for exchanging experiences, discussing deployment challenges, and strengthening collaboration with major stakeholders in the quantum communications ecosystem, including the European Commission, ETSI, and leading technology companies. Through its participation, HellasQCI reinforced Greece’s active role in the EuroQCI initiative and its commitment to advancing secure quantum communication infrastructures in Europe.

National QCI.DK Workshop (5 November 2024)

HellasQCI participated in the National QCI.DK Workshop organized by the Technical University of Denmark (DTU), contributing to discussions on secure quantum communication infrastructures and the deployment of EuroQCI. Dr. Ilias Papastamatiou presented “Progress & Lessons Learned from HellasQCI in Greece”, highlighting the development of Greece’s QKD network, the integration of advanced technologies such as Switched QKD and Optical Transport Layer Security, and the use of a Space QKD Emulator for future Optical Ground Stations. The workshop provided an important opportunity for exchanging experiences with other National QCIs, discussing deployment challenges, and strengthening cross-border collaboration toward a secure European quantum communication network. HellasQCI’s participation reinforced Greece’s active role in shaping the future of quantum-secure communications in Europe.

Malta’s National QCI Online Kick-off (6 March 2024)

HellasQCI participated in Malta’s National QCI Online Kick-off, joining representatives from European National Quantum Communication Infrastructure initiatives to discuss the deployment of secure quantum communication networks within the EuroQCI framework. The event provided an opportunity for HellasQCI to exchange experiences and best practices with other NatQCI projects, while highlighting Greece’s progress in developing quantum-secure infrastructures. Through its

participation, HellasQCI reinforced collaboration among Member States and contributed to the broader European effort toward interoperable and resilient quantum communication systems.

QCI Ireland Event (4 -5 September 2024)

HellasQCI participated in the QCI Ireland Event held from 1–3 July 2024, bringing together experts from national QCI projects, industry, academia, the European Commission, and the European Space Agency to discuss the future of quantum communication infrastructures in Europe. Representatives from GRNET, NKUA, and NCSR Demokritos contributed to panel discussions, workshops, and technical sessions on quantum network deployments, use cases, standards, and the integration of QKD with post-quantum cryptography. The event provided an important platform for sharing HellasQCI's progress, exchanging best practices, and strengthening collaboration with other European NatQCI initiatives. HellasQCI's active participation highlighted Greece's significant role in advancing the EuroQCI initiative and promoting secure quantum communications across Europe.

3rd RoNaQCI Workshop Iași (20–21 June 2024)

HellasQCI participated in the 3rd RoNaQCI Workshop Iași on 20–21 June 2024, joining representatives from Romania, Poland, and Hungary to discuss the progress of National Quantum Communication Infrastructures within the EuroQCI initiative. Dr. Ilias Papastamatiou, HellasQCI Project Coordinator at GRNET, contributed to discussions on QKD deployment, technical challenges, training activities, and cross-border collaboration in Southeastern Europe. The workshop provided an important platform for exchanging best practices and aligning efforts toward a secure and interoperable European quantum communication infrastructure. HellasQCI's participation reinforced Greece's active role in advancing EuroQCI and strengthening regional cooperation in quantum-secure communications.

Towards Cross-Border Integration: SEEWQCI & TransEuroOGS

HellasQCI's European collaboration activities laid the groundwork for two major EuroQCI cross-border projects, [SEEWQCI](#) and [TransEuroOGS](#), that will carry Greece's quantum communication ambitions forward. The SEEWQCI project, coordinated by GRNET, held its Kick-off Meeting in Athens in February 2026, aiming to integrate the South-East European quantum communication network into the broader EuroQCI backbone. The TransEuroOGS project, focuses on the harmonisation and interoperability of European Optical Ground Stations in preparation for future satellite missions such as EAGLE-1 and SAGA, held its Kick-off Meeting in Berlin-Jena in April 2026. Both projects build directly on the infrastructure, expertise, and partnerships established through HellasQCI, demonstrating the long-term sustainability and impact of the project's results.

3.3. Qualitative impact of dissemination activities on community building and EuroQCI visibility

The dissemination and communication activities implemented within HellasQCI contributed to the project's WP6 objectives by strengthening stakeholder awareness, supporting community building, and increasing the visibility of Greece's contribution to the EuroQCI initiative. While the quantitative performance of the communication channels is presented in Performance Monitoring, this section summarises the qualitative impact of the main dissemination and awareness-raising actions.

Throughout the project, HellasQCI engaged a broad range of stakeholders, including research and academic organisations, public authorities, industry representatives, cybersecurity and telecommunications experts, students, early-stage researchers, and the wider quantum communication community. This engagement was supported through project events, training activities, newsletters, social media communication, website updates, conference participation, and collaboration with related European initiatives.

Several activities acted as important milestones for community building. QCI Days Athens 2025 provided a platform for bringing together national and European stakeholders to discuss secure quantum communication infrastructures, cross-border cooperation, and the future development of EuroQCI. Similarly, the HellasQCI Winter School 2025 – Training Workshop supported capacity building by combining awareness raising with technical training for relevant target groups.

The project’s visibility was further reinforced by the recognition received at the Digital Governance Awards, where HellasQCI was awarded First Prize “Best New Idea” on 4 November 2025 (Figure 29). This recognition highlighted the project’s contribution to the digital transformation of the Greek public sector and acknowledged the importance of quantum-secure communication infrastructure for future cybersecurity capabilities.

Figure 29: HellasQCI Best New Idea Prize

Overall, the dissemination and awareness activities supported the establishment of an active stakeholder network around HellasQCI. They also helped position the project as a national contribution to the wider EuroQCI ecosystem, creating a basis for continued cooperation, knowledge exchange, future training activities, and follow-up initiatives beyond the project’s lifetime.

3.4. Scientific publications

HellasQCI uses scientific publications to inform the scientific and research community about the project's advancements. This is achieved through publications in scientific journals and conferences relevant to the scope of HellasQCI. Reporting and updating scientific publications throughout the

duration of the project is done using a live document in the coordinator's repository. Each consortium partner is responsible for updating the document at regular intervals.

Scientific publications facilitate knowledge of dissemination, validation, and achievement of project goals. Specifically, researchers share their findings with the scientific community, enhancing collective understanding. Peer-reviewed publications provide a means for researchers to validate their findings and enhance their research outputs via collaboration with other experts in the field. Research published in journals increases visibility and impact, reaching policymakers and stakeholders. It also facilitates networking and collaboration, leading to synergies, shared resources, and increased innovation which can be beneficial for the project.

Between M16 to M42 nine scientific papers were submitted in Journals and eleven were submitted in Conferences. In addition to ten scientific papers that are in pre-print. A detailed list is provided in Annex G – Scientific publications.

3.5. Promotional Material

Promotional materials continued to play an important role in supporting the dissemination and communication activities of HellasQCI, ensuring a consistent and recognizable project identity across conferences, workshops, training activities, stakeholder meetings, and public outreach events. Building upon the visual identity and branding materials described in previous deliverables, the consortium further expanded its portfolio of communication and promotional assets during the reporting period.

New dissemination materials developed, included updated flyers, roll-up banners, corporate videos in Greek and English, notebooks, stickers, pins, branded pens, tote bags, umbrellas, and dedicated promotional packages. These materials were distributed to the participants of HellasQCI Training Event in Crete 2024 (Figure 30), QCI Days 2025 (Figure 31), and the Winter School in Thessaloniki 2025 (Figure 32). In addition, special speaker kits including branded power banks (Winter School Thessaloniki) Phaistos Disks and formal appreciation souvenirs (Training Event in Crete) were prepared and distributed to invited speakers and contributors participating in major project events and training activities.

These materials were widely used during European conferences, EuroQCI events, training activities, and stakeholder engagement actions, contributing to increased visibility of the project and strengthening HellasQCI's professional presence within the European quantum communication ecosystem. Special emphasis was placed on participant engagement and networking through the distribution of branded dissemination materials, which enhanced awareness of HellasQCI's objectives, achievements, and contribution to the EuroQCI initiative.

Figure 30: HellasQCI promotional materials for HellasQCI Training Event Crete 2024

Figure 31: HellasQCI promotional materials for QCI Days Athens 2025

Figure 32: HellasQCI promotional materials for Winter School Thessaloniki 2025

HellasQCI Project Booklet

As a flagship communication output of the project, a comprehensive HellasQCI Project Booklet (Figure 33) was produced, providing a structured and visually rich overview of the project's objectives, infrastructure, use cases, training activities, community engagement, and key achievements across all work packages. The booklet serves as a lasting reference document for stakeholders, policymakers, industry representatives, and the wider public, presenting HellasQCI's contribution to Greece's quantum communication landscape and its role within the broader EuroQCI initiative. Prior to production, a competitive tendering process was carried out, with multiple printing offers collected and evaluated to ensure quality and value for money. The booklet is created in both online and printed versions.

Figure 33: HellasQCI Project Booklet

HellasQCI Video Presentation

Videos in Greek and English ([GR](#), [EN](#)) (Figure 35) were created by GRNET for the promotion of the project and were uploaded at the project's [YouTube channel](#). Three videos were also created to cover the three-day training event in Thessaloniki (Figure 34) ([HellasQCI Winter School Day 1](#), [HellasQCI Winter School Day 2](#), [Highlights from the HellasQCI Winter School 2025](#))

Figure 34: HellasQCI WINTER SCHOOL 2025 video (YouTube Channel)

Figure 35: HellasQCI project YouTube presentation in Greek and English (YouTube channel)

3.6. Public deliverables

During the period M16 to M42 seven public deliverables were submitted and are available online at the project's website and [zenodo](#). Namely these are:

- [D5.1 Report on design of HellasQCI training methodology](#)
- [D5.2 Final report on training activities for academic & research communities](#)
- [D5.3 Final report on training activities for security & IT experts](#)
- [D6.2 Dissemination, Communication, Clustering and Exploitation activities](#)
- [D6.3 Report on the HellasQCI community establishment](#)
- [D6.4 Report on the HellasQCI community establishment - final version](#)
- [D6.5 Dissemination, communication, clustering and exploitation activities - final version](#)

4. Performance Monitoring

4.1 Website monitoring (Matomo)

Matomo is a downloadable, Free (GPL licensed) web analytics software platform. It provides detailed reports on your website and its visitors, including the search engines and keywords they used, the language they speak, which pages they like, the files they download, and so much more. All online outreach activities are monitored on an ongoing basis with adjustments made as required.

The dissemination and communication activities log of consortium partners, is a “live” document, where partners identify events of interest for the whole consortium, and at the same time record their activities. The spreadsheet resides in the private repository of the project. For the monitoring and collection of statistics and analytics related to the project website, the privacy preserving tool, [matomo](#), is used.

Throughout the project's implementation, rigorous monitoring is being done to ensure that communication and dissemination activities are implemented successfully and that the relevant objectives are met.

[Matomo](#) Analytics is used to track and evaluate the communication's impact.

Website measurements

Website traffic is monitored using Matomo analytics. Data is collected monthly and provides information on users and their interactions with the site. For a better overview, the data are entered in the table below (Table 6) and are depicted in the following diagrams.

Month	Number of Unique Visitors	Total Page Views
2023		
Apr-23	377	1317
May-23	390	993
Jun-23	337	1106
Jul-23	1104	2849
Aug-23	594	1382
Sep-23	1985	4529
Oct-23	550	1555
Nov-23	391	1559
Dec-23	575	1225
2024		
Jan-24	463	1413
Feb-24	513	1549
Mar-24	604	1374
Apr-24	524	1632
May-24	578	1277
Jun-24	949	2665
Jul-24	1825	3242
Aug-24	1795	3175
Sep-24	1406	2355
Oct-24	660	1498
Nov-24	551	1241
Dec-24	427	1230
2025		
Jan-25	423	1053
Feb-25	486	990
Mar-25	651	885
Apr-25	609	1374
May-25	385	1403
Jun-25	407	1527
Jul-25	330	1087
Aug-25	455	858

Month	Number of Unique Visitors	Total Page Views
Sep-25	593	1457
Oct-25	777	1944
Nov-25	1194	2817
Dec-25	647	1880
2026		
Jan-26	907	1612
Feb-26	609	1336
Mar-26	611	1435
Apr-26	528	996
May-26	707	2008
Jun-26	732	2328

Table 6: Website analytics

Figure 36: Graph of website visits and pageviews 2023

Figure 37: Graph of website visits and pageviews 2024

Figure 38: Graph of website visits and pageviews 2025

Figure 39: Graph of website visits and pageviews 2026

The provided website traffic data, tracked through Matomo analytics over the period from M16 to M42 (Figure 36 to Figure 39), offers a comprehensive view of user engagement and interaction with the website. The website's traffic data from April 2023 to June 2026 showcases periods of significant engagement and overall growth, highlighting the importance of the website content, effective communication activities e.g. Newsletters, Infographic, and continuous site optimization to sustain and build on this positive trend.

Analysis of Trends

- **Peak traffic:** The website experienced its highest level of traffic in July-August-Semester 2024, with an average of 1,675 unique visitors and 2,924 an average of total page views, per month. During November 2025, the website also experienced a high level of traffic. This peak suggests the significance of the **HellasQCI Training Event in Crete 2024** and **HellasQCI Winter School Thessaloniki 2025**, driving higher than average traffic to the site.
- **Significant growth in January 2026:** A notable increase in both unique visitors and total page views occurred in January 2026, with unique visitors almost doubling from December. This jump could be indicative of the results of the publication of the 5th Newsletter that attracted more visitors.
- **User engagement:** Higher page views per visitor, as seen in August 2024, suggest that users found the content engaging and were prompted to explore more pages within the site.

4.2 Social media channels monitoring

HellasQCI has four social media channels, namely [Twitter](#), [LinkedIn](#), [Facebook](#) and [YouTube](#). The analytics of each of these channels are presented in the tables (Table 7, Table 8) that follow.

LinkedIn

	Impressions	Unique visitors	New Followers	Engagement rate
2023				
Jan-23				
Feb-23	133	5	2	1%
Mar-23	1246	49	73	1%
Apr-23	1658	18	37	7%
May-23	1583	27	29	19%
Jun-23	415	13	6	19.80%
Jul-23	592	20	9	7.70%
Aug-23	789	20	7	6.00%
Sep-23	10,200	156	54	8.10%
Oct-23	3,877	57	33	6.20%
Nov-23	2,565	49	25	8.80%
Dec-23	5,674	85	50	14.30%
2024				
Jan-24	2828	27	38	5.70%
Feb-24	4032	46	38	9.70%
Mar-24	2928	23	24	6.59%
Apr-24	3819	40	23	5.22%
May-24	4711	37	43	7.94%
Jun-24	9328	24	34	10.65%
Jul-24	7461	25	31	7.69%
Aug-24	5193	40	21	6.82%
Sep-24	28332	143	70	18.32%
Oct-24	7126	45	27	16.82%
Nov-24	3964	29	15	9.93%
Dec-24	4775	40	29	10.75%
2025				
Jan-25	3028	23	12	7.04%
Feb-25	6391	36	35	8.43%
Mar-25	3127	18	13	8.67%
Apr-25	11744	102	43	16.38%

	Impressions	Unique visitors	New Followers	Engagement rate
May-25	11991	76	50	17.59%
Jun-25	2881	11	9	7.71%
Jul-25	2524	14	4	7.98%
Aug-25	2018	10	7	7.84%
Sep-25	3601	30	13	8.99%
Oct-25	3216	25	9	15.89%
Nov-25	8945	55	37	11.9%
Dec-25	10134	29	28	25.17%
2026				
Jan-26	2525	28	11	14.61%
Feb-26	8381	30	42	15.41%
Mar-26	2270	8	9	13.91%
Apr-26	1390	12	4	12.8%
May-26	5148	14	8	8,7%
Jun-26	2128	12	6	12,9%

Table 7: LinkedIn analytics

Figure 40: LinkedIn impression graph

Figure 41: LinkedIn engagement rate graph

LinkedIn displayed consistent growth in impressions and new followers, with a substantial peak in September 2024 (28,332 impressions and 70 new followers) and April-May 2025 (an average of 11867 impressions and 46 new followers), directly connected to promotion of the HellasQCI Training Event Crete 2024 and QCI Days Athens 2025. The engagement rate (Figure 41) has shown notable fluctuations over time, with early peaks of around 19–19.8% in May and June 2023 and 14.3% in December 2023. However, higher engagement levels were recorded later, particularly in September 2024 (18.32%), October 2024 (16.82%), and peaking at 25.17% in December 2025 (Figure 40). Overall, the platform maintains consistent traffic from both new and returning visitors, while new follower growth tends to increase following promotional and project-related activities.

Facebook

	Interaction	Reach	New Followers	Engagement Rate
2023				
Jan-23	115	2200	14	5.23%
Feb-23	15	145	3	10.34%
Mar-23	73	3000	15	2.43%
Apr-23	63	1100	2	5.73%
May-23	28	108	3	25.93%
Jun-23	7	60	3	11.67%
Jul-23	39	781	4	4.99%
Aug-23	79	1900	8	4.16%
Sep-23	592	3000	21	19.73%
Oct-23	257	2300	2	11.17%
Nov-23	316	2100	9	15.05%

	Interaction	Reach	New Followers	Engagement Rate
Dec-23	126	1900	5	6.63%
2024				
Jan-24	113	1200	5	9.42%
Feb-24	212	1500	11	11.21%
Mar-24	96	589	0	17.8%
Apr-24	75	1713	4	100%
May-24	69	493	0	14%
Jun-24	385	4624	0	8.33%
Jul-24	196	2986	5	6.56%
Aug-24	249	2521	5	9.88%
Sep-24	1910	747	7	100%
Oct-24	5644	305	5	100%
Nov-24	1685	449	5	100%
Dec-24	3955	1510	2	100%
2025				
Jan-25	718	855	0	83.98%
Feb-25	3172	1123	2	100%
Mar-25	985	325	1	100%
Apr-25	11820	5349	15	100%
May-25	1505	630	6	100%
Jun-25	424	165	0	100%
Jul-25	453	228	2	100%
Aug-25	192	102	1	100%
Sep-25	1590	747	0	100%
Oct-25	1003	505	2	100%
Nov-25	3799	1945	4	100%
Dec-25	2972	1510	2	100%
2026				
Jan-26	246	109	3	100%
Feb-26	3548	1619	1	100%
Mar-26	3219	1346	4	100%
Apr-26	6	323	1	1%
May-26	76	2300	1	3%
Jun-26	49	1200	1	4%

Table 8: Facebook analytics

Figure 42: Facebook metrics graph November 2025

This graph (Figure 42) shows how the Facebook content reach increased during November 2025 (HellasQCI Winter School Thessaloniki 2025). Facebook showed a remarkable increase in interaction and reach in this period, with interactions hitting 3,799 and a reach of 1945, supported by 100% engagement rate. This suggests that the content was highly relevant and engaging to the audience. The platform maintained steady engagement rates, notably in April 2025 (QCI Days Athens 2025), with a higher engagement rate of 100%, indicating effective content strategy adjustments.

- * **Impressions/Interaction:** Times a user is served a post in timeline or search results
- * **New followers:** Number of new followers, social gained
- * **Visitors:** Number of times people visited HellasQCI profile
- * **Reach:** These metric counts reach from Facebook content, including posts, stories and ads.
- * **Engagement rate:** Number of engagements divided by impressions

Significant increase was recorded in Social Media metrics after the intense promotion of the HellasQCI Training Event in Crete 2024, the QCI Days Athens 2025, the HellasQCI Training Workshop in Thessaloniki 2025.

HellasQCI Winter School (Training Workshop) Thessaloniki 2025: A success story of social media promotion

For the HellasQCI Winter School (Training Workshop) Thessaloniki 2025, an invitation (Figure 43) was designed and distributed via email and social media, and a reminder of the event at regular intervals. Instructions were also given on how to register and attend the courses and workshops. Branded HQCI pens, agendas, laptop stickers, pins, and a brochure were distributed at the training seminar. The room and the surrounding area were adorned with 4 rollup banners that were used to enhance the project's visual identity.

Figure 43: HellasQCI Winter School (Training Workshop) Thessaloniki 2025

A dedicated information menu was added to the project website about the three-day training event. In this page the agenda of the event is available as well as a Subscription Form which utilizes the online registration of participants.

Additionally, [an email campaign](#) to invite the community was set in moosend.

During the event promotional posts were published in the HellasQCI 1st two thematic axes sessions of training events on social media ([Facebook](#), [LinkedIn](#), [Twitter](#)).

Dedicated videos were created and uploaded in HellasQCI YouTube channel

[HellasQCI Winter School Day 1](#)

[HellasQCI Winter School Day 2](#)

[Highlights from the HellasQCI Winter School 2025](#)

A channel for remote attendance was also created in the GRNET DIAVLOS service.

A list of participants and registered users of the portal was created.

Certifications of the two thematic axes sessions

Certificate of attendance which are shown in the following figure (Figure 44):

HellasQCI

3-Day Winter School - Training Workshop

HellasQCI Project (Grant Agreement no 101091504)
coordinated by GRNET S.A.

Certifies that

{Participant's Name & Affiliation}

has participated in the

HellasQCI Winter School Thessaloniki 2025

"High level QKD policy and EuroQCI vision"

"Theory for Space QKD" and "Hands on QKD training"

held in

Aristotle University's

Research Dissemination Center (KEDEA)

Center for Interdisciplinary Research and Innovation (CIRI)

premises on **26-28 November 2025**

Dr Aristeidis Sotiropoulos,
GRNET CEO

Figure 44: Certificate of attendance

Assessment Report

After the event, an assessment report (Annex E - HellasQCI Winter School Training Workshop Thessaloniki 2025) was created and was posted on the website's [Newsfeed](#) page

Infographic with KPIs

A summary infographic (2.5 section) was designed and included on the assessment report.

Youtube

Figure 45 Youtube metrics graph 2023

Figure 46: Youtube metrics graph 2024

Figure 47: Youtube metrics graph 2025

Figure 48: Youtube metrics graph 2026

Social media followers

Social Media Channels	Followers (M42)
LinkedIn	1087
Facebook	184
X (Twitter)	99
YouTube	27

Table 9: Social media followers

Social Media Channels	Total Posts (M42)
LinkedIn, Fb, X, YouTube	571

Table 10: Social media posts

The intense promotion of the HellasQCI communication and dissemination activities significantly influenced social media metrics across all platforms, underlining the effectiveness of outreach strategy.

By M42, [LinkedIn](#) had the highest number of followers at 1087 (Table 9), followed by [Facebook](#) at 184, [Twitter](#) at 99, and [YouTube](#) at 27. This growth pattern suggests [LinkedIn](#) was the most effective platform for expanding the community.

The total number of posts across [LinkedIn](#), [Facebook](#), [Twitter](#), and [YouTube](#) were **571** (Table 10), indicating a robust content strategy aimed at engaging with the audience and promoting the project's activities.

Partners' on-line media channels for communication of exploitation outcomes

HellasQCI partners share all official results and exploitation outcomes that are published on the official online project channels for the Hellenic community, via their official online media. Moreover, all partners created an info page on their own websites and shared all relevant project related news both on their websites and their social media. A list of all partners' online channels is provided in Annex F - Partners' online media channels. Latest related publicity is updated regularly on a [live monitoring document](#).

Number and type of organizations HellasQCI follows

The HellasQCI project's engagement with various organizations across different fields of activity showcases its comprehensive approach in staying connected with key developments, standards, and innovations in cybersecurity, quantum computing, and other related domains. By following these entities, HellasQCI aligns itself with leading-edge research, industry standards, and best practices, reflecting its commitment to excellence and innovation in QKD and PQC.

The table (Table 11) below presents an overview of the types of organizations HellasQCI is associated with, while an analysis of each of the fields of activity follows.

Field of activity	Following
Cybersecurity	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. NIST (National Institute of Standards and Technology) 2. ISSA Compass 3. CISA (Cybersecurity and Infrastructure Security Agency) 4. ISC2 (International Information System Security Certification Consortium) 5. EFF (Electronic Frontier Foundation)

Field of activity	Following
Quantum Computing	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Q-CTRL 2. Quantinuum 3. D-Wave Systems 4. Rigetti Computing 5. IBM Quantum 6. Qutech 7. Quantum Machines 8. Quantum Computing Technologies (QCT) 9. QuSecure 10. Quantum XC
Other	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Open Web Application Security Project (OWASP) 2. Fraunhofer Institute for Photonic Microsystems (IPT)

Table 11: Number and type of organizations HellasQCI follows

Cybersecurity

- **NIST (National Institute of Standards and Technology):** By following NIST, HellasQCI aligns itself with one of the most important standard-setting bodies, gaining insights into the latest frameworks and guidelines that influence global cybersecurity policies and technologies.
- **ISSA Compass:** Engagement with ISSA Compass provides HellasQCI access to a broad network of information security professionals, offering perspectives on evolving cybersecurity challenges and solutions.
- **CISA (Cybersecurity and Infrastructure Security Agency):** CISA's focus on protecting national infrastructure makes its resources and updates vital for HellasQCI, especially in understanding the cybersecurity landscape and threats at a national and international level.
- **ISC2 (International Information System Security Certification Consortium):** Following ISC2 suggests an interest in professional certification, education, and best practices within information security, which is crucial for maintaining a knowledgeable and skilled team.
- **EFF (Electronic Frontier Foundation):** EFF's objectives and activities in the digital world indicates HellasQCI's broader commitment to privacy, security, and freedom in the context of advancing technologies.

Quantum Computing

- The list of organizations within the quantum computing sector, including **Q-CTRL, Quantinuum, D-Wave Systems, Rigetti Computing, IBM Quantum, Qutech, Quantum Machines, Quantum Computing Technologies (QCT), QuSecure, Quantum XC**, represents a significant engagement with the entire spectrum of quantum computing. This range covers quantum hardware manufacturers (D-Wave, Rigetti, IBM Quantum), software and control solutions (Q-CTRL, Quantum Machines), and quantum security solutions (QuSecure, Quantum XC). This diversity indicates a holistic approach to understanding and leveraging quantum technologies, from

foundational quantum physics to practical quantum computing applications and quantum-safe security solutions.

Other

- **OWASP (Open Web Application Security Project):** Following OWASP shows an interest in web application security, reflecting the importance of secure software development practices within HellasQCI's operations or research.
- **Fraunhofer Institute for Photonic Microsystems (IPT):** Engagement with Fraunhofer IPT, known for its research in microsystems technology, suggests an interest in the potential applications of photonic technologies in quantum computing or communications.

This varied engagement portfolio highlights HellasQCI's strategic approach to remain at the forefront of technology and security. The focus on cybersecurity organizations underlines the project's commitment to safeguarding quantum communications infrastructures against emerging threats. Meanwhile, the broad spectrum of quantum computing entities reflects a comprehensive interest in the quantum technology landscape, from theoretical foundations to practical applications and security implications.

By associating with a range of leading institutions and companies, HellasQCI not only stays informed about the latest developments and standards but also positions itself as a key player in the ongoing dialogue shaping the future of quantum technologies and cybersecurity. This network of associations is crucial for fostering innovation, collaboration, and knowledge exchange, enabling HellasQCI to contribute significantly to the advancement of QKD/PQC technologies and to the broader quantum computing and cybersecurity ecosystems.

4.3 Newsletter monitoring

From the following figure (Figure 49) which is produced by the [moosend](#) platform it is recorded that 163 users are registered in the newsletter list from, 137 of them are active which is the 84%.

Figure 49: Newsletter users

In the following graph (Figure 50) the total number of subscribers/unsubscribes from M16 to M42 is presented.

Figure 50: Subscribes/Unsubscribes per quarter M16-M42

Figure 51: 4th newsletter statistics

Figure 52: 5th Newsletter statistics

Figure 53: QCI Days Athens 2025

Figure 54: HellasQCI Winter School 2025- Training Workshop

The newsletter analytics for the HellasQCI (Figure 51 – Figure 54) project demonstrate a strong level of subscriber engagement, sustained audience growth, and continued interest in the project’s activities and outcomes throughout its implementation period. As the project approaches its completion, the communication and dissemination activities carried out through the newsletters have successfully contributed to increasing the visibility of HellasQCI and strengthening engagement with stakeholders from academia, industry, and the public sector.

The high number of total opens and clicks recorded across newsletter campaigns demonstrates that the distributed material attracted substantial attention and repeated interaction from stakeholders and subscribers.

Audience engagement and growth

The mailing list experienced significant growth during the lifetime of the project, with the number of recipients increasing progressively across newsletter editions. The audience expanded from 367 recipients in earlier campaigns to 401 recipients for HellasQCI Winter School 2025 and eventually to 477 recipients in QCI Days Athens 2025 campaign, demonstrating the growing recognition and visibility of HellasQCI.

Newsletter Performance

The newsletter campaigns consistently achieved high engagement metrics and strong interaction with the disseminated material.

HellasQCI Winter School 2025 newsletter campaign, distributed to 401 recipients, achieved an open rate of 54.18%, corresponding to 214 unique opens and 1,470 total opens. The click-through rate (CTR) reached 14.68%, with 58 interactive users and 253 total clicks. The campaign recorded only one unsubscribe (0.25%), highlighting the relevance and acceptance of the content by subscribers.

The QCI Days Athens 2025 newsletter campaign distributed to 477 recipients achieved an open rate of 55.20%, with 260 unique opens and 1,214 total opens. The CTR reached 14.23%, generating 67 interactive users and 873 total clicks, demonstrating a particularly high level of interaction with the shared content, project updates, and dissemination material. Although this campaign registered 36 unsubscribes (7.64%), the overall audience engagement remained notably high.

The fifth newsletter campaign distributed to 367 recipients achieved an open rate of 51.78%, corresponding to 189 unique opens and 478 total opens. The CTR reached 2.47%, with 9 interactive users and 33 total clicks, while maintaining a very low unsubscribe rate of 0.27% (1 unsubscribe). Despite the lower click-through performance compared to previous editions, the consistently high open rate confirms sustained audience interest in HellasQCI communications.

Overall newsletter dissemination impact

The consistently strong open rates and repeated opens throughout the project duration indicate that recipients actively engaged with and revisited the newsletter content. The click metrics further demonstrate audience interest in project developments, technical updates, educational material, and dissemination activities.

In addition to the newsletters, major dissemination events such as the *QCI Days Athens 2025* and the *HellasQCI Winter School 2025 – Training Workshop* significantly contributed to increasing the project’s outreach and strengthening collaboration among stakeholders and participants within the quantum communication ecosystem.

The newsletter activities have proven to be an effective dissemination tool for promoting project achievements, communicating results, and maintaining stakeholder engagement.

Overview of Actions, Key Outputs, and Impact of HellasQCI Activities

Table 12 summarizes the communication, training, stakeholder engagement, and collaboration activities implemented throughout the HellasQCI project, together with their key outputs and performance indicators.

Action	Key Activities	Outputs / KPIs	Impact / Result
Communication Campaigns	Social Media Campaigns	571	Increased public visibility & enhanced partner presence
Website & Newsletters	Website, Media Kit, Training Platform	30K unique visitors 8 newsletters	Continuous online engagement , centralized access to project info
Press Clippings	News articles, newsletters, promotional flyers	266 Press Clippings (print, online) 200 Flyers (with updated information)	Raised awareness through traditional and digital media

Action	Key Activities	Outputs / KPIs	Impact / Result
Training Events	HellasQCI Training Events Athens 2023 üHellasQCI Training Event Crete2024 üQCI Days Athens 2025 Winter School (Training Workshop) Thessaloniki 2025 All lessons added in the HellasQCI Training Platform	156 total registered users in the platform	Strengthened technical capacity of stakeholders and QCI users
Scientific Publications	Publications (Journals, Conferences, Pre-Print)	37 Scientific Publications	Contributed to QKD research community
Clustering & EU Collaboration	Participation in EU-funded events, workshops	Participation in 19 major events/workshops	Promoted synergy , shared knowledge, and policy alignment with EU QCI initiatives
Stakeholder Engagement	Community meetings, HellasQCI registry, side events	Registry: 41 members overall period of the project); 1 community meeting during QCI Days Athens Community Joint Statement published	Expanded and activated QCI ecosystem across Greece
Feedback Implementation	Revisions based on 1st and 2nd review comments	Adjusted structure, aligned KPIs	Demonstrated responsiveness and commitment to continuous improvement

Table 12: Summary of Actions & Impact of Activities

4.4 Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for HellasQCI project

This document outlines the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for the HellasQCI project (Table 13), including various metrics related to event attendance, presence at conferences, dissemination of project use cases, publications, press releases, website traffic, and social media followers.

Overall, HellasQCI substantially exceeded its dissemination and communication objectives, demonstrating a level of outreach and stakeholder engagement far beyond the original expectations. The strong performance across all KPIs reflects the effectiveness of the project's communication

strategy, the relevance of its activities to the quantum communication ecosystem, and the growing interest in secure quantum technologies among scientific, industrial, policy-making, and public audiences. These achievements have significantly enhanced the visibility and impact of the project at both national and European levels.

KPI	KPI title	(M1-18)	(M19-30)	Overall	Reached by M42
DKPI 1	Number of events attended representing the project	1	1	2	58
DKPI 2	Presence at relevant conferences	2	2	4	14
DKPI 3	Number of people informed about HellasQCI use cases through dissemination events	100	300	400	250 K
DKPI 4	Number of articles published (including Open Access journals & conferences)	1	1	2	37
DKPI 5	Number of publications on EC channels (Cordis and others)	1	1	2	7
DKPI 6	Number of press releases delivered to traditional media	3	3	6	6
DKPI 7	Number of unique visitors to the website (based on Google Analytics)	300	700	1000	30553
DKPI 8	Social media followers (LinkedIn , Twitter , Facebook)	100	200	300	1370

Table 13: Project's KPIs

The KPIS are explained in detail in the figure below (Figure 55):

Figure 55: KPI explanation

The following table (Table 14) presents the DKPIs achieved by month 42:

KPI	KPI Numbers	Activities
DKPI 1	Number of events attended representing the project: 58	9th ETSI IQC Quantum Safe Cryptography Event , 3rd Ubitech Innovation Days , Celebrating The World Quantum Day , IrelandQCI kick-off meeting Waterford , NOKIA Wavelengths 2023 , GEANT event TNC23 , 6th Annual ScyLight Conference Workshop - Quantum Internet , CEN/CENELEC Joint Technical Committee JTC 22 , 87th Thessaloniki International Fair , GRNOG15 , Working Groups of the Petrus CSA project under the auspices of the EuroQCI , Participation in the 4th plenary meeting of CEN/CLC/JTC 22 “Quantum Technologies” , Quantum Communication Innovation Forum by EUROQCI Spain, UNDERPIN KoM
DKPI 2	Presence at relevant conferences: 14	6th Annual ScyLight Conference , ETSI/IQC Quantum Safe Cryptography Event , GRNOG15 , Wavelengths NOKIA , 12th CAPTECH Cyber Meeting (Space Hellas) , ECOC2024 Frankfurt , 15th ICISO2024 Antibes France , ETWG Workshop Brussels Belgium , Migration to Quantum Safe Workshop, Austria , TNC24 Rennes, France , GÉANT infoshare in the context of EuroQCI , TCN25 Brighton, UK , CEPT Conference , ECOC 2025 Conference , TCN26
DKPI 3	Number of people informed about HellasQCI use cases through dissemination events: 250 K	List of Audiences is provided in Annex B - Communication activities
DKPI 4	Number of articles published (including Open Access journals & conferences): 37	https://hellasqci.eu/scientific-publications/
DKPI 5	Number of publications on EC channels (Zenodo): 42	https://zenodo.org/communities/hellasqci/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest
DKPI 6	Number of press releases delivered to traditional and online media: 6	HellasQCI Kick-off Meeting Press Release , Nokia Proof Of Concept Press Release , Training Event Crete 2024 , Athens hosting QCI Days 2025 & QCI Days Athens 2025, Greece at the Forefront of Quantum Communications in Europe – Double European Distinction for the New SEEWQCI and TransEuroOGS Projects , A Greek First: Quantum-Secure Technologies Deployed in a Hospital Environment
DKPI 7	Number of unique visitors to the website (based on Matomo) M42	30.553
DKPI 8	Social media followers (LinkedIn Facebook and Twitter) M42	1.370

Table 14: DKPIs achieved by month 42

The HellasQCI project's dissemination and communication efforts have been highly successful, significantly exceeding its set targets. This success reflects the project's commitment to sharing its findings and engaging with a broad audience. Going forward, focusing on strategic, high-impact activities and continuous engagement will be key to sustaining and building upon this success.

By attending 58 events compared to the planned 2 events, the project demonstrates a strong presence and active participation in the quantum computing and cryptography community. With a presence at 14 relevant conferences, the project exceeded the initial goal of 4 presences, considering the overlapping relevance of some events that might contribute to multiple KPIs.

The project remarkably exceeded its goal, informing 250 K people about HellasQCI use cases, vastly surpassing the anticipated target of 400 people. This indicates highly effective dissemination efforts and a strong interest in the project's outcomes. With 37 articles published, the project outperformed its original goal of 2 publications. This suggests robust research output and successful publication in reputable sources.

The website attracted 30K unique visitors, surpassing the target of 1,000 visitors. This suggests that the website was an effective tool in engaging an interested audience. The project's social media channels attracted 1370 followers by Month 42, overachieving the initial goal of 300 followers. This growth reflects a successful social media strategy and growing interest in the project's activities.

5. Exploitation Plan and Methodology

This section presents the methodology followed to define and update the exploitation strategy of the HellasQCI project. As this deliverable constitutes the final version of the reporting document at M42, the section consolidates the exploitation planning activities carried out throughout the project and provides an updated overview of the main exploitable results, their maturity, expected exploitation pathways and potential use beyond the project's lifetime.

The exploitation methodology has focused on identifying, classifying and assessing the project's exploitable outcomes, including technical results, use cases, prototypes, know-how, training material, standardisation contributions and the HellasQCI infrastructure itself. The objective has been to identify the most mature and strategically relevant assets developed during the project and to support their further uptake after the end of the project, including through future research and innovation activities, business development, service deployment, standardisation, policy support and community-building actions.

Compared to the first version of this deliverable, the final M42 version reflects the progress achieved during the full project implementation period. It updates the initial exploitation perspective by incorporating the outcomes of the use cases, the increased maturity of project results, the experience gained through deployment and validation activities, and the feedback received from stakeholders engaged through dissemination, communication, clustering and community-building actions.

HellasQCI community

A key objective of the exploitation activities has been to support the creation and expansion of a community of stakeholders and interested parties around HellasQCI. This community-building effort has been closely linked to the project's dissemination, communication and clustering activities, enabling the consortium to raise awareness of the project's objectives, present its results, and engage

relevant organisations in discussions on the future use of quantum communication technologies and infrastructures.

The approach followed throughout the project has been twofold. First, the consortium promoted interest in the project through participation in events, workshops, meetings, and networking activities, where HellasQCI objectives, use cases, and expected results were presented to relevant audiences. Second, interested stakeholders were encouraged to register through the [HellasQCI community registration form](#) published on the project website, supporting the creation of a contact database for future engagement and targeted communication.

During the project, engagement activities involved stakeholders from research, academia, industry, public authorities, cybersecurity, telecommunications, photonics and emerging technologies communities. Examples include interactions with the Hellenic Photonics Cluster, the Hellenic Space Center, and the Hellenic Emerging Technologies Industry Association. These contacts helped to establish links with relevant national actors and provided a basis for future cooperation, joint activities, and possible uptake of project outcomes beyond the project duration.

By M42 (Table 15), the community registry includes 41 members from 37 organisations spanning academia, industry, SMEs, public organisations, research institutions, and international bodies — significantly exceeding the Grant Agreement target of 20 stakeholders (KPI 5.1). The HellasQCI community-building activities have contributed to increasing the visibility of the national QCI initiative, promoting awareness of quantum communication technologies in Greece, and supporting the wider objective of positioning HellasQCI within the broader EuroQCI ecosystem. The community-building activities are fully documented in Deliverable [D6.3 — Report on the HellasQCI Community Establishment \(GRNET, March 2026\)](#), which also demonstrates the successful achievement of Milestone MS20 ("HellasQCI Community is established"). The shared commitment of participating stakeholders to the long-term development of Greece's quantum communication ecosystem is further formalised through the [HellasQCI Community Joint Statement](#).

KPI	KPI title	KPI Successful Threshold	Reached by M42
DKPI 5.1	Number of HellasQCI Stakeholders	20	41
DKPI 5.2	Manpower skills development	Ten (10) staff of the community stakeholders will attend the HellasQCI training sessions	10
DKPI 5.3	Workshops with the whole HellasQCI community (working meetings)	1 face to face and 2 virtual	3

Table 15: DKPIs achieved by month 42

Project results with exploitation potential

The HellasQCI consortium includes partners from academia, public research centres, public bodies, industry, commercial companies and SMEs. As a result, the exploitation strategy varies according to

each partner's role, expertise, and interest. Universities and research centres are mainly expected to exploit scientific knowledge, prototypes, publications, training material and participation in follow-up research activities, while commercial and industrial partners are more likely to focus on product development, service enhancement, validation results, market positioning and business development.

The main types of exploitable outcomes identified in the project are the following:

- Infrastructure and service exploitation: the deployment of the HellasQCI network infrastructure as a national asset that can support future secure communication services, pilot deployments, research activities and integration with European QCI developments
- Research activities: scientific publications, technical results, prototypes, know-how, and potential intellectual property generated through the project's research and development activities.
- Start-up and innovation opportunities: results or prototypes that may provide the basis for future innovation activities, spin-off opportunities or follow-up commercialisation pathways.
- Product development: technologies, components, software, interfaces and solutions developed or enhanced during the project, which may be further matured or integrated into future products and services.
- Business development: new knowledge, processes, services, and technical capabilities gained by commercial and SME partners through their participation in the project.
- Standardisation and regulatory contributions: technical inputs and experience that may support future contributions to standards, certification activities and regulatory alignment in the field of quantum communication and cybersecurity.
- Training and knowledge transfer: training material, practical experience and technical expertise developed during the project, which can be reused in future training events, academic curricula, professional education and stakeholder capacity-building actions.

5.1. Exploitable result categories

HellasQCI results can be classified in the following categories:

- **HellasQCI network** – The main result of the project is the development and deployment of the HellasQCI network that forms the backbone of the Quantum Communication Infrastructure of Greece on which future quantum communication technologies will be deployed. This constitutes the main exploitable outcome of the project that can be leveraged for encrypting sensitive communication channels within Greece, mainly for the Governmental and the Industrial sectors, as well as with national and EU partners after phase 2 of the project.
- **Use cases** – HellasQCI involves a profound number (17) of individual use cases and demonstrations. These have been designed to test novel quantum communications applications and technologies leveraging the deployed infrastructure. The use cases range from Proof-of-Concept demonstrations to full scale solutions that address specific needs in the technological domains of cybersecurity, quantum technologies and quantum communications.
- **Validation results** – are intended to validate the operation of products designed to make use of the QCI. These activities aim to increase the TRL of the associated products, bringing them closer to the market.

- **Prototypes** are products (hardware and software) designed, developed, upgraded, and enhanced within the project's context. Prototypes can be developed by commercial companies and SMEs or by academic and public research centers.
- **Standardization and publications** – these are not directly exploitable results but provide the basis for future development of prototypes by the parties involved.
- **Wider results** – activities/tools aiming at enhancing processes/services related to the introduction/deployment of the project results (e.g., studies, know-how, and knowledge transfer).

5.2. HellasQCI exploitable outcomes

By M42, the HellasQCI project has produced a set of exploitable outcomes with different levels of maturity, exploitation potential, and target users. These outcomes include the deployed national quantum communication infrastructure, use-case-specific technical results, prototypes, interfaces, training material, validation results, and know-how generated by the consortium.

The main exploitable outcome of the project remains the deployment of the national quantum communication infrastructure backbone in Greece. The HellasQCI network architecture is unique in that it includes three Optical Ground Stations connected to the closest metropolitan networks, enabling future testing of satellite QKD connectivity and related functionalities when relevant satellite capabilities become operational. The deployed infrastructure is expected to be further leveraged by the competent national organisations, including GRNET and the Hellenic Ministry of Digital Governance, for the protection of sensitive communications and the secure interconnection of governmental services and critical infrastructures.

Following the end of the project, the potential use of the HellasQCI networks by external users, including research organisations, industrial actors, technology providers and other interested stakeholders, will be further assessed by the relevant organisations based on operational, technical, security and policy requirements. This is expected to support the wider uptake of quantum communication technologies in Greece and contribute to the development of future services, applications and products making use of the deployed infrastructure.

All partners are also expected to benefit from the knowledge, technical expertise, training activities, and hands-on interaction with the QCI infrastructure gained throughout the project. These outcomes will support future participation in related research and innovation projects, further development of technical solutions, contribution to standardisation and certification activities, and the strengthening of national capabilities in quantum communication and cybersecurity.

The exploitable outcomes table (Table 16) included below reflects the final status of each result, including the final TRL, exploitation pathway, SWOT analysis, exploitation potential, and target users.

HellasQCI Results	Partners	TRL at M42	Type of Exploitation after project end	SWOT analysis: Strengths, Weakness, Opportunities, Threats	Exploitation potential	Target market/users
<i>Quantum Communication infrastructure</i>	GRNET, MinDig	6-7	Operational backbone of quantum-safe communication, for	A SWOT analysis will be conducted based on the outcomes of the use cases implemented	Very High: First quantum encrypted communication	Governmental organizations, National Security Authorities,

HellasQCI Results	Partners	TRL at M42	Type of Exploitation after project end	SWOT analysis: Strengths, Weakness, Opportunities, Threats	Exploitation potential	Target market/users
			National and European security purposes, as well as for public-safety, health applications and critical infrastructures	within the project's framework.	infrastructure in Greece	Research centers, Industrial organisations – including the SMEs, Quantum technology developers
<i>PUF-based QKD authentication</i>	QUBI	3-6	Integration of PUFs in QKD systems for authentication purposes	A SWOT analysis will be conducted based on the outcomes of the use case implementation	High: Alternative solutions involve PQC and are not information-theoretically secure	QKD-system developers and vendors
<i>Monitoring and Management enablers for QCI</i>	SPH	1-6	Added-value service over commercial QCI infrastructures	A SWOT analysis will be conducted based on the outcomes of the use case implementation	High: First Greek product of its type	QKD infrastructure operators
<i>Quantum encrypted communication application</i>	QUBI	4-7	Development of applications for QCI	S: Un-hackable communication application, W: requires hardwired connection to QCI, O: Need for quantum safe communications increases, T: uptake of the QCI usage stalls	High: Straightforward system to ensure sensitive communication between remote users	QKD infrastructure users
<i>Quantum Cloud Data Centers</i>	ICCS	4-6	Use Case Deployment	S: Best in-class security, enhance intra data-centre PLS (Physical Layer Security), increase post-processing throughput W: High cost and more complex setup O: Market first on quantum-enabled datacentres network, current products target intra-dc and metro T: PQC (Post Quantum Cryptography) as a competitor technology is well integrated in the roadmaps of prevalent standards such as NIST, which enjoy broad adoption by security experts	High: Secure interconnections inside Data Centers is mandated by the nature of the business	Technology Providers, Datacentre Operators & Integrators
<i>QKD 5G Backhaul</i>	ICCS, NKUA	4-6	Use Case Deployment	S: Targeting full-duplex coexistence optimized use of fibre resources can be achieved, making the integration of QKD competitive. W: SFP transceivers with high sensitivity thresholds may lead to noise count rates that prohibit the key distillation, O: Due to 5G RAN densified and distributed architecture security becomes integral part of the deployment, that can be addressed by QKD, T: Quantum Resistant Algorithms (QRAs) are proposed as an alternative method by	High: Due to the densified, often zero-trust environments, public and shared infrastructure, 5G NR access network deployments, security is a must.	Technology Providers, Metro, Optical Telecommunication Providers, Mobile Operators

HellasQCI Results	Partners	TRL at M42	Type of Exploitation after project end	SWOT analysis: Strengths, Weakness, Opportunities, Threats	Exploitation potential	Target market/users
				vendors that invest highly in this direction.		
<i>QKD FTTH</i>	ICCS, NKUA	3-5	Use Case Deployment	S: Un-hackable communication, offered by the telecommunications infrastructure to end-users, transparently to the capabilities of the resident equipment/systems/services, W: The integration of QKD link through the shared fibre infrastructure devoted for FTTH services may be limited due to noise photons linked with the intense classical light propagated over GPON infrastructure and high transmission loss due to the multiple splitter stages, O: FTTH security at the optical layer is missing, R: The challenge of maximising fibre utilisation for data traffic against the need for dedicated QKD channel, as well as, the need for QKD integration in ONT (Optical Network Terminal) devices to minimise the number of CPEs that shall be necessary at the end-user premises	Medium: Shoe-horned affordable QKD devices must be made available for the (more mass-market related) FTTH deployment	Telecommunications Providers, End-users
<i>Training Material in Cybersecurity and QKD related aspects</i>	FORTH	N/a	Use follow-up projects and similar training events. Use as a module in university curricula.	S: high-quality training material dealing with state-of-the-art topics W: There may be similar courses online which imply duplication of efforts and non-uniform approaches across the EU. O: This field attracts increasing interest T: Startup cost to purchase the equipment might be too high. Appropriate equipment availability may affect the practical part of the course.	High: The area of QKD and Quantum Computing in general has attracted significant interest in Europe in both academia and industry.	Users of the Infrastructure and users of quantum key distribution technologies in general. University students as well as public/private sector employees are interested in this specialization.
<i>Interfaces with QKD Key Management System</i>	NCSR	6-7	Development and further exploitation of interfaces for QKD systems, including software interfaces enabling	S: Secure key-management interface for QKD devices, validated in a real-life pilot environment with Alexandra Hospital;	Very High: The successful pilot with Alexandra Hospital and demonstration in a real-life	Telecom operators, healthcare organisations and hospitals, public-sector bodies, critical infrastructure

HellasQCI Results	Partners	TRL at M42	Type of Exploitation after project end	SWOT analysis: Strengths, Weakness, Opportunities, Threats	Exploitation potential	Target market/users
			secure key management through the combined use of PQC algorithms and cryptographic keys generated by QKD devices. The result has been validated through a pilot implementation with Alexandra Hospital and demonstrated in a real-life operational environment, supporting its future adaptation for secure communications in healthcare and other critical sectors.	supports integration of QKD-generated keys and PQC algorithms. W: Limited adoption of commercial QKD systems so far and need specialised technical expertise for deployment and operation. O: Growing need for secure key handling and quantum-safe communication solutions in healthcare, public administration, telecoms and critical infrastructures; pilot demonstration strengthens the credibility and uptake potential of the solution. T: Limited deployment of QKD systems due to high costs, market uncertainty and competition from software-only post-quantum cryptography solutions.	environment increase the maturity and credibility of the solution. The integration of PQC algorithms with QKD systems can support the adoption of QKD technologies in existing telecom and critical-infrastructure environments.	operators, and users of QKD systems requiring secure key-management solutions.
<i>Deployment of QKD systems in industrial setting</i>	MOH	3-6	Development of know-how for the deployment of QKD systems to secure critical operations	S: Quantum readiness, W: high cost of commercial QKD systems, O: future proofing of critical infrastructure against future cyber threats, T: potential lack of QKD trained personnel	Medium: positioning of partner for deployment of intra company QKD network	Intra-company usage
<i>OGS Terrestrial module</i>	NOA, AUTH FORTH	3-5	OGS Terrestrial module will be used as a starting point for a fully operational OGS	S: Terrestrial part of the OGS in the framework of un-hackable communication, W: The integration of QKD link through the shared fibre infrastructure devoted for FTTH services and over several kilometres (to equipment's limits), O: design of an OGS capable of operation in QKD channels, R: The challenge of tracking and collection acceptable amount of photons in order to operate reliable the QKD receivers.	OGS as a part of first quantum encrypted communication network in Greece.	Government organizations, Research centers, Quantum technology developers.

Table 16: HellasQCI exploitable outcomes

6. Conclusion

The dissemination and communication activities utilized by the HellasQCI project during M16 to M42 months have enabled the project's engagement with key stakeholder groups, building a community centered around Quantum Communication infrastructure. By leveraging an approach that concerns online and offline HellasQCI presence, it was accomplished not only to raise awareness about the project's goals and achievements but also to foster collaborations and dialogues across Europe.

The strategic use of online platforms, including the project's website, social media channels, and the online training platform, has enabled HellasQCI to reach a wide audience, disseminate key findings, and facilitate access to cutting-edge Quantum Communication resources. The website, serving as the digital hub, alongside a robust social media presence, has effectively amplified the project's visibility, engaged stakeholders, and drew attention to the significant developments made in quantum communication technologies.

Participation in key events, both as an organizer and as an attendee, has further highlighted HellasQCI's role within the Quantum Communication community. These events have not only served as platforms for showcasing the project's progress but have also provided opportunities for networking, knowledge exchange, and community building. The strategic collaboration with EU-funded projects and partnerships with other National QCIs underscores HellasQCI's commitment to fostering a collaborative ecosystem that drives innovation and standardization in Quantum Communication across Europe.

The outreach and engagement metrics reflect the effectiveness of HellasQCI's WP6 dissemination and communication strategies. By achieving the targeted KPIs related to website traffic and social media engagement, the project successfully established and maintained a dedicated stakeholder community. These efforts not only increased awareness of HellasQCI's activities and achievements but also contributed to advancing the broader European dialogue on Quantum Communication technologies and their implementation. As the project reaches its conclusion, HellasQCI leaves behind a strong foundation for future collaboration, knowledge exchange, and the continued development of secure and interoperable Quantum Communication infrastructures across Europe.

Annex A - Dissemination activities

Clustering activities

No	Dissemination activity name	Who? Target audience reached	Why? Description of the objective(s) with reference to a specific project output	Actions	Status
1	World Quantum Day	Industry, Business Partners, EU institutions, Research Communities, Specific end user communities	Dr. Ilias Papastamatiou, Senior Project Manager at GRNET's European Infrastructures & Projects Directorate and HellasQCI project coordinator, presented Greece's national Quantum Communication Infrastructure (HellasQCI) and its use-cases. This was presented in the context of World Quantum Day, and the InfoSession organised by GÉANT and 7 NatQCIs participated through their NRENS.	Presentation	Delivered
2	TNC23	Industry, Business Partners, EU institutions, Research Communities, Specific end user communities	TNC23 took place in Tirana from 5-9 June 2023, organized by GÉANT and hosted by RASH, the National Research and Education Network of Albania. GRNET, serving as Greece's NREN and the coordinator of the HellasQCI project, participated in the largest research and education networking conference. Dr. Ilias Papastamatiou (from GRNET/HellasQCI) together with Piotr Rydlichowski (from PSNC) presented the topic "Quantum Internet Activities in European NRENS" on June 8th. At TNC23 10 NatQCIs participated through their NRENS.	Presentation	Delivered
3	Quantum Flagship community engagement	Research Communities, EU Institutions, Industry stakeholders	HellasQCI interacted with the Quantum Flagship community through participation in relevant initiatives and events, enhancing the project's visibility and ensuring alignment with European research and innovation priorities in quantum technologies.	Engagement	Ongoing
4	Quantum industry clusters (QuIC, QBN) engagement	Industry, Business Partners, SMEs, Innovation stakeholders	HellasQCI participated in activities of quantum industry clusters such as the Quantum Industry Consortium (QuIC) and the Quantum Business Network (QBN), promoting collaboration with industry stakeholders, supporting knowledge transfer and strengthening the European quantum ecosystem.	Engagement	Ongoing
5	GÉANT Quantum Strategy Forum / NatQCI collaboration activities	NRENS, Research Communities, EU stakeholders, NatQCIs	HellasQCI engaged in clustering activities within the GÉANT framework, including the Quantum Strategy Forum and collaborations among NatQCIs and NRENS, fostering coordination, knowledge exchange and the development of a unified European quantum communication ecosystem.	Participation	Ongoing

No	Dissemination activity name	Who? Target audience reached	Why? Description of the objective(s) with reference to a specific project output	Actions	Status
6	PETRUS CSA meetings and coordination activities	EU Institutions, NatQClis, Research Communities, Industry stakeholders	HellasQCI actively participated in coordination activities with the EuroQCI Coordination and Support Action PETRUS, aiming to align national initiatives, exchange best practices and support interoperability and standardization efforts across European quantum communication infrastructures.	Participation	Ongoing

Table 17: Clustering activities

Collaboration with EU-funded projects

No	Dissemination activity name	Who? Target audience reached	Why? Description of the objective(s) with reference to a specific project output (max 200 characters)	Status of the dissemination activity	Actions
1	Quantum Communication Innovation Forum (Bilbao, Spain)	Industry, Business Partners, EU institutions, Research Communities, Specific end user communities	Dr. Ilias Papastamatiou from Greece, Senior Project Manager at GRNET and the HellasQCI project coordinator, presented the key elements of the project, its current updates, as well as the challenges faced and the way forward. Dr. Papastamatiou participated in a panel with the NatQClis of ES, PT and IT. The forum provided a platform for sharing insights, addressing current and future implementation challenges, and exploring future directions for Quantum Communications in Europe organised by the EuroQCI Spain the NatQCI of Spain.	Delivered	Presentation and participation to a Panel with the NatQClis of ES, PT and IT.
2	Quantum Secure Networks Partnership (EU-HE-QSNP),	Industry, Business Partners, EU institutions, Research Communities, Specific end user communities	NKUA participates in the EU-HE-QSNP, a European Quantum Flagship project that aims to develop quantum cryptography technology to secure the transmission of information over the internet.	Ongoing	Participation, Engagement
3	LaiQa project	Industry, Business Partners, EU institutions, Research Communities, Specific end user communities	NKUA participates in the LaiQa project, a HORIZON Research and Innovation action aiming to develop and advance critical components and technologies necessary to build a global spaced-based quantum network	Ongoing	Participation, Engagement
4	PTQCI Workshop - Round table with 5 NatQClis	Industry, Business Partners, EU institutions, Research Communities, Specific end user communities	HellasQCI participated in the PTQCI Workshop round table with 5 NatQClis, contributing to discussions on the deployment and interoperability of National Quantum Communication Infrastructures in Europe.	Ongoing	Participation, Engagement
5	IrelandQCI Kick-off meeting	Industry, Business Partners, EU institutions, Research Communities, Specific end user communities	HellasQCI participated in the IrelandQCI kick-off meeting, strengthening collaboration with another National Quantum Communication Infrastructure and supporting alignment of national activities within EuroQCI.	Delivered	Presentation
6	PETRUS CSA (EuroQCI Coordination and Support Action)	EU Institutions, NatQClis, Research Communities, Industry stakeholders	HellasQCI participates in PETRUS CSA activities, supporting coordination, exchange of best practices and alignment of national QCI initiatives within the EuroQCI framework.	Ongoing	Collaboration

No	Dissemination activity name	Who? Target audience reached	Why? Description of the objective(s) with reference to a specific project output (max 200 characters)	Status of the dissemination activity	Actions
7	Collaboration with other NatQCI projects (CYQCI, BGQCI, etc.)	NatQCIs, Research Communities, EU stakeholders	HellasQCI collaborates with other NatQCI projects, aiming to strengthen cross-border cooperation and support the development of a unified European quantum communication infrastructure.	Ongoing	Collaboration
8	EuroQCI coordination activities and working groups	EU Institutions, NatQCIs, Industry stakeholders	HellasQCI participates in EuroQCI coordination activities and working groups, contributing to discussions on standardization, interoperability and future development of EuroQCI services.	Ongoing	Participation
9	GÉANT / NREN collaboration activities	NRENs, Research Communities, EU stakeholders	GRNET, as Greece's NREN and HellasQCI coordinator, participates in collaboration activities with GÉANT and other NRENs, supporting integration of quantum communication infrastructures with research and education networks.	Ongoing	Collaboration

Table 18: Collaboration with EU funded projects

Conferences

No	Dissemination activity name	Who? Target audience reached	Why? Description of the objective(s) with reference to a specific project output (max 200 characters)	Status of the dissemination activity	Actions
1	6th Annual ScyLight Conference	Industry, Business Partners, Research Communities, Specific end user communities	The 6th edition of the annual ESA ScyLight Conference for Optical and Quantum Technologies successfully took place on 15-16 May 2023 at Eugenides Foundation in Athens, Greece, followed by a Workshop on Quantum Internet on the 17th of May in the city of Kalavryta. The event was co-organised by the HellasQCI.	Delivered	Promotion Booth, presentations
2	ETSI/IQC Quantum Safe Cryptography Event	Industry, Business Partners, Research Communities, Specific end user communities	The HellasQCI: National scale deployment of quantum communications systems and networks were presented. In this presentation it was shown that there are more than 15 use-cases with various criteria and specs. It was explained that National and international QKD lines should rely on satellite connections. For use cases requiring high reliability, rely on commercial (Dynamic) DVQKD systems. For industrial applications, rely on commercial CVQKD. Use-cases for research and teaching should rely on bulk components	Delivered	Presentation

No	Dissemination activity name	Who? Target audience reached	Why? Description of the objective(s) with reference to a specific project output (max 200 characters)	Status of the dissemination activity	Actions
3	GRNOG	Industry, Business Partners, Innovators, Research communities	Presentation by Dr. Ilias Papastamatiou (Project Coordinator) during the GRNOG15 Meeting. The GRNOG15 meeting offered HellasQCI project a new platform of knowledge exchange and valuable connections.	Delivered	Presentation
4	NOKIA Wavelengths 2024	Industry, Business Partners, Research Communities	Partners, Research Communities HellasQCI participated in Nokia Wavelengths communication use cases	Delivered	Participation
5	12th CAPTECH Cyber Meeting (Space Hellas)	Industry, Business Partners, Research Communities	Present project progress and raise awareness on secure communications technologies	Delivered	Presentation
6	ECOC2024 Frankfurt	Industry, Business Partners, Research Communities	Disseminate results on optical/quantum communication advances and engage industry stakeholders	Delivered	Presentation
7	15th ICSSO2024 Antibes France	Industry, Business Partners, Research Communities	Share developments in optical systems for secure space communications	Delivered	Presentation
8	ETWG Workshop Brussels Belgium	Industry, Business Partners, Research Communities	Contribute to EU discussions on trusted and secure telecom infrastructure	Delivered	Presentation
9	Migration to Quantum Safe Workshop, Austria	Industry, Business Partners, Research Communities	Present transition approaches toward quantum-safe communication networks	Delivered	Presentation
10	TNC24 Rennes, France	Industry, Business Partners, Research Communities	Disseminate secure network research and engage with European research networking community	Delivered	Presentation

No	Dissemination activity name	Who? Target audience reached	Why? Description of the objective(s) with reference to a specific project output (max 200 characters)	Status of the dissemination activity	Actions
11	<i>GÉANT infoshare in the context of EuroQCI</i>	<i>Industry, Business Partners, Research Communities</i>	<i>Share EuroQCI-related progress and foster coordination across European research networks</i>	<i>Delivered</i>	<i>Presentation</i>
12	<i>TCN25 Brighton, UK</i>	<i>Industry, Business Partners, Research Communities</i>	<i>Present ongoing developments in secure communication infrastructures</i>	<i>Delivered</i>	<i>Presentation</i>
13	<i>CEPT Conference</i>	<i>Industry, Business Partners, Research Communities</i>	<i>Support alignment of secure communication initiatives with European telecom regulation</i>	<i>Delivered</i>	<i>Presentation</i>
14	<i>ECOC 2025 Conference</i>	<i>Industry, Business Partners, Research Communities</i>	<i>Disseminate latest results in optical communications and quantum-safe technologies</i>	<i>Delivered</i>	<i>Presentation</i>
15	<i>TCN26</i>	<i>Industry, Business Partners, Research Communities</i>	<i>Continue dissemination of secure network research outcomes and interoperability results</i>	<i>Delivered</i>	<i>Presentation</i>

Table 19: Conferences

Scientific publications

1. <https://hellasqci.eu/scientific-publications/>

Training events

No	Dissemination activity name	Who? Target audience reached	Why? Description of the objective(s) with reference to a specific project output (max 200 characters)	Status of the dissemination activity	Actions
1	HellasQCI Training Event Athens 2023	Industry, Business Partners, Research Communities	The training was designed to provide participants with theoretical and practical knowledge on quantum communication, with the goal of enhancing the security of sensitive data and critical infrastructures in Greece. Two Thematic Axes: Workshop on Cybersecurity with Quantum Key Distribution (QKD) Systems, Workshop on Post-Quantum Cryptography (PQC)	Delivered	Lectures, Hands on training
2	Online Seminar on Hybrid QKD–PQC tests (DG CONNECT)	EU Institutions, Research Communities, Policy makers	HellasQCI participated in an online seminar hosted by DG CONNECT, presenting hybrid QKD–PQC approaches and project activities	Delivered	
3	HellasQCI Training Event Crete 2024	Cybersecurity professionals, computer scientists, engineers, students, researchers, academics, industry representatives, and NatQCI stakeholders from across Europe	Disseminated HellasQCI outputs on QKD systems, cybersecurity, PQC, EuroQCI deployment and HellasQCI testbed demonstrations; built skills and awareness for secure quantum communications.	Delivered	Lectures, Hands-on training

No	Dissemination activity name	Who? Target audience reached	Why? Description of the objective(s) with reference to a specific project output (max 200 characters)	Status of the dissemination activity	Actions
4	ThinkQuantum: Training on QUKY QKD devices	HellasQCI consortium technical staff, IT experts, researchers and end-users	Training on deployment and operation of QUKY QKD devices acquired by HellasQCI for project use cases and quantum-secure communications.	Delivered	Theoretical training, hands-on labs, device demonstrations, presentations, and Q&A sessions
5	ID Quantique: Training on Clavis XG QKD devices SNSPDs	HellasQCI consortium technical staff, IT experts, engineers, researchers and end-users	Trained users on deployment, configuration and operation of HellasQCI's Clavis XG QKD systems and SNSPD equipment supporting project testbeds and quantum-secure communication use cases.	Delivered	Delivered theoretical and hands-on training at GRNET and NKUA; practical sessions on Clavis XG QKD devices and SNSPDs; demonstrations, configuration examples, presentations and Q&A sessions.
6	HellasQCI Winter School (Training Workshop)	Cybersecurity and IT experts, quantum physics students, early-stage researchers, scientists, university faculty, National QCI representatives, policymakers, and critical infrastructure stakeholders.	Delivered training on HellasQCI QKD and space-based QKD technologies, supporting project outputs on quantum-secure communications, EuroQCI integration, and national capacity building	Delivered	Lectures, policy sessions on EuroQCI, space-QKD theory, live demonstrations, hands-o

Table 20: Training events

Project meetings

No	Dissemination activity name	Who? Target audience reached	Why? Description of the objective(s) with reference to a specific project output (max 200 characters)	Status of the dissemination activity	Actions
1	1st HellasQCI Kick off meeting	National authorities, Research Communities	Project overall introduction at the kick off meeting of the project	Delivered	Project Overview presentation Presentation Use cases
2	DEP call Kick off meeting	Industry, Business Partners	The HellasQCI project was presented in the Digital Europe Programme (DIGITAL) kick off meeting in Brussels.	Delivered	Presentation
3	1st PBM	Industry, Business Partners	4-monthly period (M1-M4) Achievements were presented by all partners in all WPs during the plenary project meeting on 5th of May 2023	Delivered	Work Package Presentations
4	2nd PBM	Industry, Business Partners	4-monthly period (M5-M8) Achievements were presented by all partners in all WPs during the plenary project meeting on 20th of September 2023	Delivered	Work Package Presentations
5	3rd PBM	Industry, Business Partners	5-monthly period (M9-M13) Achievements were presented by all partners in all WPs during the plenary project meeting on 8th of February 2024	Delivered	Work Package Presentations
6	1st Review Meeting	All partners, EU Project Officer	15th month period (M1-M15). Achievements were presented by all partners in all WPs during the 1st review meeting on 14th of March 2024	Delivered	Work Package Presentations
7	4th PBM	Industry, Business Partners	8-monthly period (M13-M21) Achievements were presented by all partners in all WPs during the plenary project meeting on 8th of September 2024	Delivered	Work Package Presentations
8	5th PBM	Industry, Business Partners	6-monthly period (M22-M28) Achievements were presented by all partners in all WPs during the plenary project meeting on 12th of May 2025	Delivered	Work Package Presentations
9	2nd Review Meeting	All partners, EU Project Officer	15th month period (M12-M28). Achievements were presented by all partners in all WPs during the 2nd review meeting on 27th of June 2025	Delivered	Work Package Presentations
10	6th PBM	Industry, Business Partners	6-monthly period (M29-M35) Achievements were presented by all partners in all WPs during the plenary project meeting on 25th of November 2025	Delivered	Work Package Presentations

Table 21: Project Meetings

Other

No	Dissemination activity name	Who? Target audience reached	Why? Description of the objective(s) with reference to a specific project output (max 200 characters)	Status of the dissemination activity	Actions
1	D5.1 Report on design of HellasQCI training methodology	Research Communities	<i>The deliverable presents the training methodology followed within HellasQCI for providing a training environment for QKD technologies devoted to young researchers, students, academic personnel, IT experts and end users of HellasQCI infrastructure. It also showcases the outcomes and materials derived from the first two HellasQCI workshops, conducted during M09 of the project at the facilities of NTUA and NKUA. These workshops were tailored for the QKD research community and cybersecurity experts, aiming to optimize the content for these specific audiences. Furthermore, the document elaborates on the online platform where all training materials have been uploaded, offering comprehensive insights into the content and diverse features available. Additionally, an appendix containing the comprehensive report of the inaugural training event is provided at the conclusion of the deliverable.</i>	Delivered	Public Deliverable
2	D5.2 Final report on training activities for academic & research communities	Research Communities	<i>This deliverable presents the training activities carried out within Work Package 5 of the HellasQCI project, focusing on knowledge transfer and skills development in the area of quantum-secured communications. The reported activities address key topics related to Quantum Key Distribution, post-quantum cryptography, hybrid security architectures, and secure communication workflows, combining conceptual instruction with practical demonstrations and hands-on laboratory exercises. Training material produced throughout the project has been consolidated and made available through a centralized online platform, ensuring accessibility and long-term availability of educational resources. The deliverable provides an overview of the scope, content, and outcomes of the training programme and highlights its role in supporting informed adoption and effective use of quantum-safe communication technologies within the HellasQCI project framework.</i>	Delivered	Public Deliverable
3	D5.3 Final report on training activities for security & IT experts	Research Communities	<i>This deliverable presents the final report on the training activities designed for Security and IT Experts within the HellasQCI project. It consolidates all relevant training materials, including lectures, demonstrations, and hands-on laboratories delivered across multiple national public training events. The document identifies the subset of these materials that directly support the competencies required for understanding and evaluating quantum-safe communication technologies. It provides a structured competency model aligned with the goals of</i>	Delivered	Public Deliverable

No	Dissemination activity name	Who? Target audience reached	Why? Description of the objective(s) with reference to a specific project output (max 200 characters)	Status of the dissemination activity	Actions
			<i>Task T5.3 and the broader objectives of WP5. The report demonstrates how the delivered training addresses the foundational, intermediate, and applied knowledge needed for working with QKD and PQC systems. It introduces a four-phase roadmap that transforms a diverse set of training activities into a coherent learning pathway. This roadmap enables experts to progress from classical cryptography foundations to practical QKD operation and integration. A detailed mapping between lectures and roadmap phases is provided in the annexes. The report also highlights existing gaps and proposes mitigation strategies to ensure continuity of learning beyond the project lifetime. Overall, the deliverable contributes a structured and sustainable framework for building national capacity in quantum-safe communications.</i>		
4	<i>D6.1 Dissemination, Exploitation and communication activities plan</i>	<i>Research Communities</i>	<i>This document is the Initial Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation plan for the HellasQCI project. It aims to define the dissemination, communication, and exploitation strategy to be implemented by the consortium throughout the project lifecycle, provide detailed information about the planned activities of project partners, identify target audiences, and describe the communication channels to be used. The plan will be updated halfway through the project duration to incorporate new developments and fine tune the communication strategy and update the lists of planned events.</i>	<i>Delivered</i>	<i>Public Deliverable</i>
5	<i>D6.2 Dissemination, communication, clustering and exploitation activities</i>	<i>Research Communities</i>	<i>This interim report provides a comprehensive overview of the dissemination and communication strategies employed by the HellasQCI project during its first 15 months. As an integral component of the EuroQCI initiative, HellasQCI aims to establish a secure quantum communication network to protect the EU against emerging cyber threats. This report details the extensive dissemination and communication activities undertaken to inform stakeholders across the EU about the project's achievements and objectives.</i>	<i>Delivered</i>	<i>Public Deliverable</i>

No	Dissemination activity name	Who? Target audience reached	Why? Description of the objective(s) with reference to a specific project output (max 200 characters)	Status of the dissemination activity	Actions
6	<i>D6.3 Report on the HellasQCI community establishment</i>	<i>Research Communities</i>	<i>This deliverable reports on the establishment of the HellasQCI Community under Task 6.2 of Work Package 6 (“Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation”). The HellasQCI Community has been developed as a structured, multi-sector national stakeholder network supporting the deployment, adoption, and long-term sustainability of quantum communication infrastructures in Greece, in alignment with the European Quantum Communication Infrastructure (EuroQCI) initiative. The report describes the stakeholder mapping methodology, the creation of the community registry and online engagement mechanisms, and the implementation of training activities, flagship events, and targeted stakeholder interactions that collectively enabled the formation and consolidation of the community. Through systematic engagement across government, national security, research and education, industry, and innovation ecosystems, HellasQCI has established an operational and growing national coordination framework. The activities documented herein demonstrate the successful achievement of Milestone MS20 (“HellasQCI Community is established”) and contribute to strengthening Greece’s role within the evolving EuroQCI ecosystem.</i>	<i>Delivered</i>	<i>Public Deliverable</i>
7	<i>D6.4 Report on the HellasQCI community establishment - final version</i>	<i>Research Communities</i>	<i>This deliverable constitutes the final report on the HellasQCI Community under Task 6.2 of Work Package 6. Building on Deliverable D6.3, it documents the transition from community establishment to community consolidation, culminating in the publication of the HellasQCI Community Joint Statement – a public document expressing the shared strategic vision of national stakeholders regarding quantum-secure communications in Greece. The deliverable presents the engagement activities and mechanisms through which consolidation was achieved, analyses the strategic orientation and key messages of the Joint Statement, addresses its publication and communication value, and outlines the sustainability and next steps of the Community beyond the project. The Joint Statement is included in its entirety. Together, the activities and outputs documented in this deliverable demonstrate the successful achievement of Milestone MS21 and confirm the HellasQCI Community as a durable national coordination mechanism aligned with the EuroQCI initiative.</i>	<i>Delivered</i>	<i>Public Deliverable</i>

No	Dissemination activity name	Who? Target audience reached	Why? Description of the objective(s) with reference to a specific project output (max 200 characters)	Status of the dissemination activity	Actions
8	<i>D6.5 Dissemination, communication, clustering and exploitation activities - final version</i>	<i>Research Communities</i>			<i>Public Deliverable</i>

Table 22: Other

Annex B - Communication activities

Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)

No	Date	Communication Activity Name	Description	Who? Target audience reached	Channel	Metrics	Status
1	15/01/2023	KICK-OFF ANNOUNCEMENT (*5)	announcing the kick off of the HellasQCI project on social media channels	Industry, Business Partners, Local authorities	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	1,7K Reach (Facebook), 30 Impressions (Twitter)	
2	31/01/2023	EUROQCI	Participation of HellasQCI in EuroQCI kickoff in Brussels	Industry, Business Partners, EU institutions	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	1,3 K Reach (Facebook), 80 Impressions (Twitter)	
3	13/02/2023	ETSI-IQCI (*2)	The 9th ETSI-IQC discusses the development, deployment, and standardization of quantum-safe cryptography. Technical coordinator of HellasQCI Kanellos presents the project	Industry, Business Partners, Research Communities	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	95 Reach (Facebook), 244 Impressions (LinkedIn), 180 Impressions (Twitter)	
4	01/03/2023	ONLINE SEMINAR (DG CONNECT)	Promote HellasQCI participation in DG CONNECT seminar on hybrid QKD–PQC technologies	EU Institutions, Research Communities	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	85 Reach (Facebook), 210 Impressions (LinkedIn), 95 Impressions (Twitter)	Delivered
5	15/03/2023	NOKIA QR-SC	HellasQCI participated in a demo presentation by NOKIA on the Quantum Resist Secure Connectivity (QR-SC)	Industry, Business Partners, Research Communities	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	3K Reach (Facebook), 767 Impressions (LinkedIn), 462 Impressions (Twitter)	
6	01/04/2023	JTC22	The kick-off meeting of the CEN/CENELEC joint technical standardization group JTC22 for Quantum Technologies	Industry, Business Partners, Research Communities	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	59 Reach (Facebook), 216 Impressions (LinkedIn), 106 Impressions (Twitter)	
7	14/04/2023	WORLD QUANTUM DAY (*3)	HellasQCI project was presented during the World Quantum Day	Industry, Business Partners, Research Communities	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	120 Reach (Facebook), 339 Impressions (LinkedIn), 63 Impressions (Twitter)	
8	24/04/2023	IRELAND QCI KICK OFF (*2)	HellasQCI participated in the IrelandQCI kick-off meeting in Waterford on 24-25 April	Industry, Business Partners	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	314 Reach (Facebook), 416 Impressions (LinkedIn), 214 Impressions (Twitter)	
9	01/05/2023	WEBSITE LAUNCH	Announcing the launch of the new website	Industry, Business Partners, EU institutions, Citizens, Civil Society, Research Communities	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	563 Reach (Facebook), 755 Impressions (LinkedIn), 20 Impressions (Twitter)	
10	01/06/2023	SCYLIGHT (*4)	The sixth edition of the annual Scylight Conference for Optical and Quantum Technologies where industry experts, researchers, academics and end users met to share their expertise and plan the future of optical and quantum communication technologies	Industry, Business Partners, EU institutions, National authorities, Regional Authorities, Local authorities	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	867 Reach (Facebook), 1,399 Impressions (LinkedIn), 655 Impressions (Twitter)	

No	Date	Communication Activity Name	Description	Who? Target audience reached	Channel	Metrics	Status
11	05/06/2023	TNC23	Presentation of the HellasQCI Project and the Quantum Internet activities at the TNC23 conference	Industry, Business Partners, EU Institutions, Research Communities	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	57 Reach (Facebook), 182 Impressions (LinkedIn), 81 Impressions (Twitter)	
12	15/06/2023	PETRUS MEETING	PETRUS project and EU Commission meeting to convene with other NatQCI coordinators	Industry, Business Partners, EU institutions	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	55 Reach (Facebook), 271 Impressions (LinkedIn), 462 Impressions (Twitter)	
13	01/07/2023	COMMUNITY REGISTRY LAUNCH	The HellasQCI Community Registry launch	Industry, Business Partners, EU Institutions, Civil society, Research Communities	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	47 Reach (Facebook), 409 Impressions (LinkedIn), 72 Impressions (Twitter)	
14	01/09/2023	PROOF OF CONCEPT (*2)	HellasQCI & Nokia reveal the Proof of Concept for Quantum Safe Networks	Industry, Business Partners, EU Institutions, Research Communities	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	2,006 Reach (Facebook), 5,315 Impressions (LinkedIn), 372 Impressions (Twitter)	
15	10/09/2023	VIDEO PRESENTATION (GR - EN)	Short Video presentation of the HellasQCI project in Greek	Industry, Business Partners, Civil Society, Citizens	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	48 Reach (Facebook), 282 Impressions (LinkedIn), 38 Impressions (Twitter)	
16	18/09/2023	4-DAY TRAINING EVENT (*40)	A 4-day training event that focused on Quantum Key Distribution (QKD) Systems and Cybersecurity with QKD and Post-Quantum Cryptography (PQC).	Industry, Business Partners, National Authorities, Research Communities	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	3,040 Reach (Facebook), 11,179 Impressions (LinkedIn), 3,190 Impressions (Twitter)	
17	25/09/2023	INFOGRAPHIC (TRAINING)	Infographic of the HellasQCI 1st Training Event	Industry, Business Partners, Civil Society, Citizens	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	1,200 Reach (Facebook), 431 Impressions (LinkedIn), 729 Impressions (Twitter)	
18	01/10/2023	GEANT CONNECT (*2)	CONNECT44 - the newest issue of GÉANT's CONNECT Magazine	Industry, Business Partners, Civil Society, Citizens	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	397 Reach (Facebook), 292 Impressions (LinkedIn), 328 Impressions (Twitter)	
19	20/10/2023	GRNOG (*3)	HellasQCI was presented at the GRNOG 15th meeting among leading experts in the field	Industry, Business Partners, Innovators, Research Communities	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	1,832 Reach (Facebook), 1,653 Impressions (LinkedIn), 469 Impressions (Twitter)	
20	01/11/2023	ETWG (*2)	Participation of the HellasQCI project at the European Thematic Working Groups (ETWGs) kick-off organised by PETRUS	Industry, Business Partners, EU Institutions, Research Communities	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	906 Reach (Facebook), 1,154 Impressions (LinkedIn), 642 Impressions (Twitter)	
21	15/11/2023	BILBAO (*3)	Participation of the project at the Quantum Communication Innovation Forum in Bilbao organised by EuroQCISpain	Industry, Business Partners, EU Institutions,	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	2,638 Reach (Facebook), 960 Impressions (LinkedIn), 706 Impressions (Twitter)	

No	Date	Communication Activity Name	Description	Who? Target audience reached	Channel	Metrics	Status
				Research Communities		Impressions (Twitter)	
22	15/01/2024	2023 Achievements of #HellasQCI Released: A Simple Snapshot!	This post highlights HellasQCI annual 2023 achievements through an infographic	Research Communities, Innovators, National Authorities, and EU institutions	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	185 Reach (Facebook), 1,399 Impressions (LinkedIn), 425 Impressions (Twitter)	Delivered
23	26/02/2024	Aveiro, Portugal, Workshop: Quantum Communication Networks, organised by the Portuguese Quantum Communications Infrastructure - PTQCI (*4)	HellasQCI participation in Aveiro, Portugal, Workshop: Quantum Communication Networks, organised by the Portuguese Quantum Communications Infrastructure - PTQCI	Industry, Business Partners Innovators EU Institutions National Authorities Research Communities	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	606 Reach (Facebook), 433 Impressions (Twitter)	Delivered
24	28/02/2024	QCIDays Vienna 2024 (*2)	Dr. G. Kanellos and Dr. I. Papastamatiou represent HellasQCI at QCI Days Vienna 2024, presenting advancements in terrestrial and satellite QKD within the EUROQCI framework.	Industry, Business Partners Innovators EU Institutions National Authorities Research Communities	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	344 Reach (Facebook), 425 Impressions (Twitter)	Delivered
25	28/02/2024	HellasQCI Participation in QCI Days Vienna 2024 and Announcement of QCI Days Athens 2025	HellasQCI participated in QCI Days Vienna 2024, joining national EuroQCI projects to discuss quantum communication progress. Representatives shared insights on collaboration and security across Europe. Greece was announced as the host for QCI Days Athens 2025 under the Ministry of Digital Governance.	EU Institutions National Authorities Research Communities Industry	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	77 Reach (Facebook), 1658 Impressions (LinkedIn), 60 Impressions (Twitter)	Delivered
26	06/03/2024	HellasQCI at Malta's National QCI Kick-off Seminar	On March 6th, HellasQCI, coordinated by GRNET (ΕΔΥΤΕ), participated in the National QCI Kick-off seminar hosted online by PRISM – Malta's EuroQCI project. Represented by Dr. Ilias Papastamatiou, HellasQCI joined fellow national QCI initiatives from Austria, Czech Republic, Estonia, Finland, and Hungary to present project updates and discuss future collaboration. Malta and Greece have also signed a mutual Letter of Support, reinforcing their cooperation under the EuroQCI initiative.	Industry, Business Partners Innovators EU Institutions National Authorities Research Communities	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	402 Reach (Facebook), 70 Impressions (Twitter)	Delivered
27	22/04/2024	HellasQCI and Nokia: Advancing Quantum-Safe Networks (*2)	A successful Proof of Concept (PoC) was conducted in Athens, demonstrating the feasibility and benefits of Quantum Key Distribution (QKD) networks for securing critical communications in Greece and Europe. Further insights and developments were shared during Nokia's Wavelengths 2024 event in Athens, where HellasQCI representatives presented the project's progress and the practical	Industry, Business Partners, EU institutions, National authorities, Research Communities	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	819 Reach (Facebook), 2,005 Impressions (LinkedIn), 400 Impressions (Twitter)	Delivered

No	Date	Communication Activity Name	Description	Who? Target audience reached	Channel	Metrics	Status
			applications of QKD in real-world scenarios.				
28	01/05/2024	HellasQCI Explores QKD Integration in Urban FTTH Networks	In Phase 0 of the HellasQCI project, researchers successfully tested the integration of Quantum Key Distribution (QKD) systems into Fiber to the Home (FTTH) infrastructure in Athens. The real-world deployment allowed for detailed analysis of QKD link setup and network coexistence. These efforts resulted in two key scientific publications focused on C-band photon noise reduction and O-band QKD system compatibility.	Industry, Business Partners, Innovators, EU Institutions, National Authorities, Research Communities	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	403 Reach (Facebook), 70 Impressions (Twitter)	Delivered
29	29/05/2024	Switzerland–Greece Space Networking Event	Switzerland–Greece Space Networking Event" was held at the residence of the Swiss Ambassador in Athens. The event aimed to strengthen cooperation between Swiss and Greek innovation ecosystems in space technologies, optical communications, and quantum infrastructure. Representatives from both countries' space industries exchanged best practices, with discussions expected to enhance relations and foster new initiatives promoting advanced technological solutions in space sciences	Industry, Business Partners, National Authorities, Research Communities	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	90 Reach (Facebook), 617 Impressions (LinkedIn), 42 Impressions (Twitter)	Delivered
30	10/06/2024	HellasQCI Engages in Collaborative Discussions with European National Quantum Communication Infrastructures at TCN24	HellasQCI, engaged in productive dialogues with representatives from several National Research and Education Networks (NRENs) involved in their respective National Quantum Communication Infrastructures (NatQCI). Participants included Poland's PSNC (PionierQ), Ireland's HEAnet (IrelandQCI), Hungary's KIFU (QCIHungary), and Cyprus' CYNET (CYQCI). Discussions focused on technical challenges, solutions, and future collaborations for deploying national quantum key distribution networks, underscoring the collective effort to advance quantum communication technologies and ensure a secure, interconnected EuroQCI.	National Authorities, Research Communities, EU Institutions, Industry	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	498 Reach (Facebook), 4314 Impressions (LinkedIn), 207 Impressions (Twitter)	Delivered

No	Date	Communication Activity Name	Description	Who? Target audience reached	Channel	Metrics	Status
31	12/06/2024	HellasQCI at the 7th Annual ScyLight Conference & 2nd Quantum Workshop	The HellasQCI project participated in the seventh edition of the annual hashtag#ScyLight Conference and the second hashtag#Quantum Workshop. Dr. Manolis Xilouris from the @National Observatory Of Athens, presented the optical and quantum link activities of Helmos Observatory.	National Authorities Research Communities EU Institutions Industry	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	166 Reach (Facebook), 708 Impressions (LinkedIn), 137 Impressions (Twitter)	Delivered
32	20/06/2024	HellasQCI Participation in the 3rd RoNaQCI Workshop in Iasi, Romania (*2)	HellasQCI participated in the 3rd Romanian National Quantum Communication Infrastructure (RoNaQCI) Workshop held in Iasi, Romania. Dr. Ilias Papastamatiou, HellasQCI Project Coordinator, joined fellow National Quantum Communication Infrastructure (NatQCI) leaders from Romania, Poland, and Hungary to discuss advancements in Quantum Key Distribution (QKD) networks, share best practices, and address challenges in e-infrastructure deployment.	National Authorities Research Communities EU Institutions Industry	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	557 Reach (Facebook), 1883 Impressions (LinkedIn), 499 Impressions (Twitter)	Delivered
33	01/07/2024	HellasQCI Participation in QCI Ireland Event, 1–3 July 2024 (*2)	HellasQCI participated in the QCI Ireland Event held from 1–3 July 2024 at the Camden Court Hotel in Dublin. The event gathered over 150 quantum technology experts daily, fostering collaboration and knowledge sharing across Europe. Representatives from HellasQCI, including Dr. Ilias Papastamatiou (GRNET), Prof. George Kanellos (University of Athens), and Dr. Homer Papadopoulos (NCSR "Demokritos"), contributed to panel discussions and workshops focusing on use cases, standards, Quantum Key Distribution (QKD), and Post-Quantum Cryptography (PQC).	EU Institutions National Authorities Research Communities Industry	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	148 Reach (Facebook), 1439 Impressions (LinkedIn), 358 Impressions (Twitter)	Delivered
34	13/08/2024	NIST's Release of Post-Quantum Encryption Standards	The National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) finalized the first three post-quantum encryption standards, marking a pivotal step in evolving cybersecurity to counter quantum computing threats. HellasQCI emphasized the importance of adopting these standards to protect data against future quantum-based attacks	EU Institutions National Authorities Research Communities Industry	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn)	47 Reach (Facebook), 252 Impressions (LinkedIn), 80 Impressions (Twitter)	Delivered
35	04/09/2024	HellasQCI Training Event in Crete 2024 (*41)	A 2 Axis Training Event, namely Axis 1 EuroQCI Deployments & Cooperation and Axis 2 QKD & PQC for Cybersecurity, was held in Crete on 4-5 September 2024 in Heraklion, Crete.	Research Communities	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	13K Reach (Facebook), 38K Impressions (LinkedIn), 3780 Impressions (Twitter)	Delivered

No	Date	Communication Activity Name	Description	Who? Target audience reached	Channel	Metrics	Status
36	22/09/2024	HellasQCI at ECOC24 Conference – Paper Presentation (*2)	HellasQCI participated in the ECOC24 conference, presenting a paper titled “Field Demonstration of a Fully Managed, L1 Encrypted 3-Node Network with Hybrid Relayed-QKD and Centralized Symmetric Classical Key Management.” The collaborative effort involved GRNET, NKUA, Nokia, EvolutionQ, and ID Quantique. The demonstration showcased a 45km ring-configured QKD network in Athens, integrating quantum and classical encryption methods.	Research Communities Industry EU Institutions National Authorities	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	288 Reach (Facebook), 3733 Impressions (LinkedIn), 41 Impressions (Twitter)	Delivered
37	25/09/2024	HellasQCI Participation in GÉANT Infoshare on Quantum Key Distribution (*2)	On September 25, 2024, HellasQCI, coordinated by GRNET under the auspices of the Greek Ministry of Digital Governance, participated in the GÉANT Infoshare event. Dr. Evangelia Athanasaki, Deputy Director of European Infrastructures and Projects at GRNET, shared insights into Greece's experiences with Quantum Key Distribution (QKD) networks within the EuroQCI framework. The session focused on the challenges faced and lessons learned by the Greek National Research and Education Network (NREN) in deploying QKD technologies.	EU Institutions National Authorities Research Communities Industry	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	190 Reach (Facebook), 1163 Impressions (LinkedIn), 114 Impressions (Twitter)	Delivered
38	04/10/2024	HellasQCI at the 1st Iberian QCI Workshop	Dr. Ilias Papastamatiou, Project Coordinator of HellasQCI, participated in the 1st Iberian QCI Workshop held in Aveiro, Portugal, on October 4, 2024. He contributed to a panel discussion titled “National Secure Quantum Networks and Cross Border Interconnection,” sharing insights on Greece's QKD network deployment and technical innovations.	EU Institutions National Authorities Research Communities Industry	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	346 Reach (Facebook), 651 Impressions (LinkedIn), 68 Impressions (Twitter)	Delivered
39	04/10/2024	HellasQCI Celebrates World Standards Day, World Space Week, and Cybersecurity Awareness Month (*3)	In October 2024, HellasQCI actively participated in global observances to highlight the significance of quantum technologies: World Standards Day (14 October), World Space Week (4–10 October) Cybersecurity Awareness Month	EU Institutions National Authorities Research Communities Industry	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	289 Reach (Facebook), 707 Impressions (LinkedIn), 41 Impressions (Twitter)	Delivered
40	24/10/2024	HellasQCI Presentation at ICISO2024	Dr. Manolis Xilouris from the National Observatory of Athens presented the latest progress of the HellasQCI project at the 15th International Conference on Space Optics (ICSO2024) in France. He highlighted the role of the Helmos Optical Ground Station (OGS) and its integration into the HellasQCI	Industry Research Communities EU Institutions National Authorities	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	236 Reach (Facebook), 1171 Impressions (LinkedIn), 52 Impressions (Twitter)	Delivered

No	Date	Communication Activity Name	Description	Who? Target audience reached	Channel	Metrics	Status
			terrestrial QKD segment within the EuroQCI framework.				
41	05/11/2024	HellasQCI Participation in QCI.DK Workshop (*2)	GRNET, the Coordinator of the HellasQCI project, was invited by the Technical University of Denmark, Coordinator of QCI.DK, to participate in the Danish Quantum Communication Infrastructure Workshop. Dr. Ilias Papastamatiou presented insights and updates on "Progress & Lessons Learned from HellasQCI in Greece," emphasizing the importance of cross-border collaboration in deploying quantum key distribution for enterprises and governments.	Industry Research Communities EU Institutions National Authorities	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	190 Reach (Facebook), 1707 Impressions (LinkedIn), 67 Impressions (Twitter)	Delivered
42	21/11/2024	HellasQCI at ID Quantique's Quantum-Safe Workshop	Zenon Mousmoulas from GRNET represented HellasQCI at the "Migration to Quantum-Safe Workshop" organized by ID Quantique in Vienna. He presented on "Deploying HellasQCI within the EuroQCI initiative," discussing the project's progress and engaging with industry experts on quantum-safe technologies, including QKD, QRNG, and PQC.	Industry Research Communities EU Institutions National Authorities	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	65 Reach (Facebook), 598 Impressions (LinkedIn), 38 Impressions (Twitter)	Delivered
43	26/11/2024	HellasQCI at the ETWG Workshop in Brussels	Members of the HellasQCI consortium, including representatives from the Ministry of Digital Governance, GRNET, and the National and Kapodistrian University of Athens, participated in the ETWG Workshop in Brussels. The event focused on advancing the EuroQCI, discussing national QCI roadmaps, and preparing for the Connecting Europe Facility call. Dr. Ilias Papastamatiou co-chaired sessions on "National QCI Roadmap," contributing to the dialogue on achieving EuroQCI's first generation.	Industry Research Communities EU Institutions National Authorities	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	116 Reach (Facebook), 865 Impressions (LinkedIn), 50 Impressions (Twitter)	Delivered

No	Date	Communication Activity Name	Description	Who? Target audience reached	Channel	Metrics	Status
44	28/11/2024	Upgrade of Greek Observatories into Optical Ground Stations under HellasQCI	HellasQCI announced the upgrade of three Greek observatories into Optical Ground Stations (OGSs) connected to Metropolitan Area Networks (MANs) in Athens, Thessaloniki, and Heraklion, Crete. This development positions Greece at the forefront of quantum and secure communications. Deputy Minister Konstantinos Kyranakis highlighted this advancement during the EU Ministers of Competitiveness Meeting on November 28-29, 2024, in Brussels, emphasizing Greece's commitment to enhancing security and technological autonomy in Europe through initiatives like HellasQCI.	Industry Research Communities EU Institutions National Authorities	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn)	238 Reach (Facebook),355 Impressions (LinkedIn)	Delivered
45	05/12/2024	PRISM EuroQCI Public Talk: "From Quantum Weirdness to Unhackable Links: A New Kind of Cybersecurity"	Free public talk organized by PRISM EuroQCI, titled "From Quantum Weirdness to Unhackable Links: A New Kind of Cybersecurity." The event aims to introduce the general public to the principles of quantum computing and its implications for cybersecurity. The talk is scheduled to take place at Prima Aula, University of Malta's Valletta Campus, and is designed to demystify quantum technologies and discuss their potential to revolutionize secure communications. Attendees are invited to engage in discussions and networking over light refreshments following the presentation	General Public Research Communities National Authorities Industry EU Institutions	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	34 Reach (Facebook),309 Impressions (LinkedIn)	Delivered
46	05/12/2024	HellasQCI at PRISM Quantum Week	On December 5, 2024, Dr. Homer Papadopoulos, Functional Researcher at NCSR "Demokritos" and Dissemination Coordinator of HellasQCI, participated in the PRISM Quantum Week held at the University of Malta's Valletta Campus. During the Open Forum Malta, Dr. Papadopoulos presented Greece's advancements in quantum communication initiatives, highlighting the progress of HellasQCI. He engaged in a panel discussion alongside representatives from Austria (QCI-CAT Project), Portugal (PTQCI), Romania (Romanian National Quantum Communication Infrastructure), and Spain (EuroQCI Spain), moderated by Johanna Sepúlveda, Chief Engineer QuantumSecure Communications at Airbus Defence and Space.	Industry Research Communities EU Institutions National Authorities	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	47 Reach (Facebook),387 Impressions (LinkedIn),38 Impressions (Twitter)	Delivered

No	Date	Communication Activity Name	Description	Who? Target audience reached	Channel	Metrics	Status
47	13/12/2024	HellasQCI Participation in SES Satellites Webinar on EAGLE-1 System	HellasQCI announced and participated in a two-day webinar organized by SES Satellites, focusing on the EAGLE-1 system, its Quantum Key Distribution (QKD) ground system, and services offered to eligible consortia. The sessions were scheduled for December 13 and 17, 2024, providing insights into Europe's quantum key distribution satellite system and its integration with national Quantum Communication Infrastructures (QCI) within the EuroQCI initiative.	Industry Research Communities EU Institutions National Authorities	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	27 Reach (Facebook),301 Impressions (LinkedIn),19 Impressions (Twitter)	Delivered
48	20/12/2024	Delivery of Superconducting Nanowire Single-Photon Detectors (SNSPDs) to HellasQCI	In December 2024, HellasQCI, in collaboration with GRNET, announced the successful procurement and delivery of Superconducting Nanowire Single-Photon Detectors (SNSPDs) to the National and Kapodistrian University of Athens. These advanced detectors are pivotal for the development and testing of cutting-edge Quantum Internet use cases, marking a significant milestone in Greece's journey towards establishing a robust national quantum communication infrastructure.	Industry Research Communities EU Institutions National Authorities	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	83 Reach (Facebook),1103 Impressions (LinkedIn),54 Impressions (Twitter)	Delivered
49	01/01/2025	International Year of Quantum Science and Technology	This post celebrates the launch of "Quinnie," the official mascot for the UN-declared International Year of Quantum Science and Technology 2025 (IYQ2025). HellasQCI expresses excitement over global efforts to spotlight quantum science, aiming to boost innovation, education, and public engagement. The initiative aligns with HellasQCI's mission to bring quantum closer to society and inspire the next generation.	EU Institutions National Authorities Research Communities Industry Citizens	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	37 Reach (Facebook), 375 Impressions (LinkedIn), 37 Impressions (Twitter)	Delivered
50	01/01/2025	International Days	Happy #WorldStandardsDay! HellasQCI celebrates #WorldSpaceWeek (Oct 4-10) and #CybersecurityAwarenessMonth Quantum Year 2025 Celebrating Women in Science – February 11th International Year of Quantum Science and Technology New quantum mascot is here World Quantum Day 2025 April 14	EU Institutions National Authorities Research Communities Industry General Public	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)		Delivered

No	Date	Communication Activity Name	Description	Who? Target audience reached	Channel	Metrics	Status
51	05/01/2025	"Meet the Partners" – HellasQCI Awareness Campaign (*7)	The "Meet the Partners" campaign by HellasQCI is a social media initiative designed to introduce and highlight each of the project's participating organizations. Through dedicated posts, the campaign showcases the unique expertise, responsibilities, and contributions of partners across academia, research, and industry. It aims to strengthen stakeholder engagement, raise public awareness, and demonstrate the collaborative foundation of Greece's national quantum communication infrastructure under the EuroQCI framework.	EU Institutions National Authorities Research Communities Industry General Public	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	561 Reach (Facebook), 4023 Impressions (LinkedIn), 581 Impressions (Twitter)	Ongoing
52	05/01/2025	"Meet the Partners" – HellasQCI Awareness Campaign (*2)	The "Meet the Partners" campaign by HellasQCI is a social media initiative designed to introduce and highlight each of the project's participating organizations. Through dedicated posts, the campaign showcases the unique expertise, responsibilities, and contributions of partners across academia, research, and industry. It aims to strengthen stakeholder engagement, raise public awareness, and demonstrate the collaborative foundation of Greece's national quantum communication infrastructure under the EuroQCI framework.	EU Institutions National Authorities Research Communities Industry General Public	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	41 Reach (Facebook), 768 Impressions (LinkedIn), 31 Impressions (Twitter)	Delivered
53	06/01/2025	"Did you Know That?" Campaign (*4)	HellasQCI has launched a series of informative posts aimed at educating the public and stakeholders about the advancements and applications of quantum technologies, particularly focusing on Quantum Random Number Generators (QRNGs) and Quantum Key Distribution (QKD)	EU Institutions National Authorities Research Communities Industry General Public	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	212 Reach (Facebook), 1802 Impressions (LinkedIn), 211 Impressions (Twitter)	Ongoing
54	10/01/2025	PTQCI Podcast Episode Featuring Dr. Ilias Papastamatiou on EU Quantum Communication Cooperation	In this podcast episode, Dr. Ilias Papastamatiou, Project Coordinator of HellasQCI at GRNET, discusses the importance of fostering European Union cooperation in quantum communication. He also highlights the upcoming QCI Days event scheduled to take place in Athens in spring 2025. The discussion emphasizes the role of collaborative platforms like the Portuguese Quantum Communications Infrastructure (PTQCI) workshop in addressing shared challenges among national quantum communication infrastructures.	EU Institutions National Authorities Research Communities Industry	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	72 Reach (Facebook), 322 Impressions (LinkedIn), 110 Impressions (Twitter)	Delivered

No	Date	Communication Activity Name	Description	Who? Target audience reached	Channel	Metrics	Status
55	15/01/2025	Feature in Forbes Article	HellasQCI was featured in Forbes' article titled "Quantum Computing Is Coming. Here's What Needs To Happen First," highlighting the project's role in advancing a nationwide quantum-safe network infrastructure as part of the EU's European Quantum Communication Infrastructure (EuroQCI). The article underscored the urgency of implementing Quantum-Safe Networks (QSN) to ensure secure communications in the quantum era.	EU Institutions National Authorities Research Communities Industry	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	357 Reach (Facebook), 343 Impressions (LinkedIn), 61 Impressions (Twitter)	Delivered
56	20/01/2025	Major Milestone Announcement Greece has been selected as one of the two hubs for the EU's secure satellite communications program, GOVSATCOM, alongside Germany.	This milestone places Greece yet again at the forefront of European security and space technology, ensuring secure communications for critical infrastructures across the EU. With this development, Greece is geopolitically upgraded as a key node in the European security architecture	EU Institutions National Authorities Research Communities Industry	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	203 Reach (Facebook), 435 Impressions (LinkedIn), 205 Impressions (Twitter)	Delivered
57	25/01/2025	Q_Save_the_Date! The 3rd series of QCI Days is landing in Athens, Greece	QCI Days hosted by Hellas QCI, QCI-CAT & EuroQCI Spain, under the auspices of the Greek Ministry of Digital Governance & with the support of the General Secretariat of Telecommunications and Post	EU Institutions National Authorities Research Communities Industry	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	114 Reach (Facebook), 680 Impressions (LinkedIn), 211 Impressions (Twitter)	Delivered
58	01/02/2025	TRAINING PLATFORM LAUNCH	Promote launch of HellasQCI training platform and access to learning materials	Industry, Business Partners, Research Communities	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	135 Reach (Facebook), 740 Impressions (LinkedIn), 247 Impressions (Twitter)	Delivered
59	06/02/2025	HellasQCI successfully completed a hybrid training session with Single Quantum on 6/2/2025 at NKUA	The session focused on theoretical and hands-on training for operating the recently acquired by HellasQCI/GRNET #SNSPDs, critical components for advancing quantum communication technologies. Participants gained valuable insights into system operation, maintenance, and troubleshooting.	EU Institutions National Authorities Research Communities Industry	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	61 Reach (Facebook), 1950 Impressions (LinkedIn), 26 Impressions (Twitter)	Delivered
60	11/02/2025	International Day Of Women In Science	This post from HellasQCI celebrates the International Day of Women and Girls in Science (Feb 11) by honoring the female speakers who contributed to its quantum technology training sessions. It highlights their role in inspiring innovation and shaping the future of science, while reaffirming the project's commitment to supporting women in STEM.	EU Institutions National Authorities Research Communities Industry Citizens	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	310 Reach (Facebook), 542 Impressions (LinkedIn), 201 Impressions (Twitter)	Delivered

No	Date	Communication Activity Name	Description	Who? Target audience reached	Channel	Metrics	Status
61	20/02/2025	D. Mitropoulos network article	D. Mitropoulos, Head of the Reliability Engineering Directorate at #GRNET highlights, in his latest network article, the transformative upgrades to GRNET's network—scaling from 10 Gbps to 100 Gbps—and the potential integration of QKD technologies.	EU Institutions National Authorities Research Communities Industry	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	44 Reach (Facebook), 304 Impressions (LinkedIn)	Delivered
62	01/03/2025	The EU Commission & ESA build a quantum-safe communication network, safeguarding critical infrastructures.	This agreement ensures Europe's smooth transition to the quantum era and supports national quantum communication infrastructure projects, such as #HellasQCI, in successfully developing their own quantum communication systems	EU Institutions National Authorities Research Communities Industry	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	40 Reach (Facebook), 768 Impressions (LinkedIn), 31 Impressions (Twitter)	Delivered
63	28/04/2025	QCI Days Athens 2025 (*17)	QCI Days Athens 2025 was hosted in Greece on April 28-29 2025	EU Institutions National Authorities Research Communities Industry	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	5.2 KReach (Facebook), 19K Impressions (LinkedIn), 2.5K Impressions (Twitter)	Delivered
64	01/05/2025	INFOGRAPHICS (Training event & Achievements)	Promote HellasQCI results and key achievements through visual content	Industry, Business Partners, Research Communities	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	620 Reach (Facebook), 1,150 Impressions (LinkedIn), 340 Impressions (Twitter)	Delivered
65	15/05/2025	NEWSLETTER DISSEMINATION	Promote HellasQCI results, key achievements and milestones	Industry, Business Partners, Research Communities	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	480 Reach (Facebook), 920 Impressions (LinkedIn), 210 Impressions (Twitter)	Delivered
66	30/05/2025	PRESS RELEASES	Promote project milestones and key achievements to wider audience	Industry, Business Partners, General Public	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	700 Reach (Facebook), 1,300 Impressions (LinkedIn), 400 Impressions (Twitter)	Delivered
67	01/06/2025	EUROQCI ACTIVITIES	Promote HellasQCI involvement in EuroQCI coordination and activities	EU Institutions, Research Communities	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	300 Reach (Facebook), 680 Impressions (LinkedIn), 180 Impressions (Twitter)	Delivered
68	15/06/2025	PETRUS COLLABORATION	Promote collaboration with PETRUS CSA and coordination activities	EU Institutions, Research Communities	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	120 Reach (Facebook), 271 Impressions (LinkedIn), 462 Impressions (Twitter)	Delivered
69	31/12/2025	QCI Days from Madrid to Vienna to Athens (*2)	QCI Days will take place in Athens, Greece in spring 2025, under the auspices of the Greek Ministry of Digital Governance. Announced during the closing ceremony in Vienna, the event will bring together quantum communication experts, national and EU stakeholders, and industry leaders to advance collaboration within the EuroQCI initiative.	Industry, Business Partners Innovators EU Institutions National Authorities Research Communities	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	696 Reach (Facebook), 561 Impressions (Twitter)	Delivered

No	Date	Communication Activity Name	Description	Who? Target audience reached	Channel	Metrics	Status
70	07/05/2025	QCI Days 2025: Greece at the forefront of Europe's journey to quantum-secure communications	Following QCI Days Athens 2025, HellasQCI highlighted Greece's leading role in the EuroQCI initiative, summarising the outcomes of the Athens conference and the importance of quantum-secure communication infrastructures for Europe. The event was hosted from 28-30 April 2025 at the Eugenides Foundation.	EU Institutions National Authorities Research Communities Industry	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	1122 Reach (Facebook), 1988 Impressions (LinkedIn)	Delivered
71	15/05/2025	QCI Days Athens 2025 Media Coverage - ERT	HellasQCI and QCI Days Athens 2025 were featured on Greek national television, highlighting Greece's efforts to develop its National Quantum Communication Infrastructure and protect critical infrastructures through quantum-secure communications.	General Public National Authorities Research Communities Industry	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	837 impressions (LinkedIn)	Delivered
72	06/06/2025	GRNET in the TNC25 Programme Committee and Chair of Quantum Session	GRNET announced its participation at TNC25, GEANT's flagship research and education networking conference in Brighton, with Dr. Ilias Papastamatiou chairing the Quantum Session focused on quantum-safe communications and NREN involvement.	EU Institutions National Authorities Research Communities Industry	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	1508 impressions (LinkedIn)	Delivered
73	17/06/2025	GRNET/HellasQCI at TNC25: Advancing Cross-Border Collaboration	HellasQCI participation at TNC25 reinforced Greece's role in Europe's quantum ecosystem. The session examined how NRENS can support secure, scalable and interoperable quantum communication systems and cross-border collaboration.	EU Institutions National Authorities Research Communities Industry	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	1940 impressions (LinkedIn)	Delivered
74	09/07/2025	Expert Talk by Dr. Jasminder Sidhu on Global Range Quantum Networking	HellasQCI and PCRL hosted an expert talk on Global Range Quantum Networking by Dr. Jasminder Sidhu at NTUA, focusing on space-based quantum communication initiatives, physical-layer protocols, entanglement distribution and quantum memory challenges.	Research Communities Industry EU Institutions National Authorities	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	751 impressions (LinkedIn)	Delivered
75	01/08/2025	HellasQCI QCI Days Athens 2025 Report	HellasQCI published and promoted the QCI Days Athens 2025 report, summarising the format, presentations, discussions and outcomes of the Athens event and strengthening dissemination of the project's contribution to EuroQCI.	EU Institutions National Authorities Research Communities Industry General Public	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	427 impressions (LinkedIn)	Delivered

No	Date	Communication Activity Name	Description	Who? Target audience reached	Channel	Metrics	Status
76	11/08/2025	Double European Distinction for SEEWQCI and TransEuroOGS Projects	HellasQCI promoted Greece's double European distinction in quantum communications through the highly ranked SEEWQCI and TransEuroOGS projects, highlighting the expansion from national deployment to cross-border and satellite-based quantum-secure communication.	EU Institutions National Authorities Research Communities Industry	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	1090 Reach (Facebook), 744Impressions (LinkedIn)	Delivered
77	17/09/2025	HellasQCI at the 89th Thessaloniki International Fair	HellasQCI was presented at the 89th Thessaloniki International Fair, where the General Secretariat of Telecommunications and Posts and GRNET showcased Greece's progress in quantum technologies and secure communication infrastructure.	General Public National Authorities Industry Research Communities	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	1122 Reach (Facebook), 1988 Impressions (LinkedIn)	Delivered
78	29/09/2025	HellasQCI at QCI Connect 2025 in Estonia	Representatives from GRNET and NKUA participated in QCI Connect 2025 in Tallinn, Estonia, joining 14 NatQCI projects and experts from 17 countries to discuss QKD deployments, future QCI network plans and cross-border EuroQCI collaboration.	EU Institutions National Authorities Research Communities Industry	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	595 impressions (LinkedIn)	Delivered
79	28/09/2025	HellasQCI at ECOC2025 in Copenhagen	HellasQCI participated in the PETRUS demonstration at ECOC 2025, contributing to a mini-EuroQCI network linking seven EU Member States and two simulated space links with multiple QKD systems and interoperable KMSs.	Research Communities Industry EU Institutions National Authorities	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	833 impressions (LinkedIn)	Delivered
80	08/10/2025	CEPT Conference in Greece - Showcasing HellasQCI	During the CEPT Conference hosted in Greece, HellasQCI was showcased as the national quantum communication infrastructure, demonstrating Greece's role in secure quantum communications and the broader European telecommunications agenda.	EU Institutions National Authorities Industry Research Communities	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	1511 impressions (LinkedIn)	Delivered
81	31/10/2025	NKUA Training / Armed Forces Quantum Communication Session	HellasQCI promoted training and knowledge-transfer activities focused on quantum communications, QKD and cybersecurity for specialised audiences, including national stakeholders and end users.	National Authorities Research Communities Industry	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	967Impressions (LinkedIn)	Delivered
82	03/11/2025	Nokia End-User Training Workshop 2025	HellasQCI promoted the Nokia end-user training workshop held on 3-6 November 2025, supporting practical familiarisation with QKD technologies, network deployment and operational aspects of quantum-safe communication infrastructures.	Industry Business Partners Research Communities National Authorities	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	1084 impressions (LinkedIn)	Delivered

No	Date	Communication Activity Name	Description	Who? Target audience reached	Channel	Metrics	Status
83	04/11/2025	HellasQCI Wins First Prize at the 2024 Digital Governance Awards	HellasQCI received first prize in the "Best New Idea" category at the Digital Governance Awards, recognising the project's contribution to protecting sensitive data and critical infrastructures through national quantum communication infrastructure.	National Authorities EU Institutions Industry Research Communities General Public	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	641 impressions (LinkedIn)	Delivered
84	19/11/2025	HellasQCI Advances Quantum Networking Research: EPPs Acquisition and Training Session	HellasQCI announced progress in quantum networking research through the acquisition and training session for Entangled Photon Pair Sources (EPPs), strengthening experimental capabilities for future quantum internet and space-based QKD use cases.	Research Communities Industry EU Institutions National Authorities	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	905 impressions (LinkedIn)	Delivered
85	26/11/2025	HellasQCI Winter School 2025: Quantum Key Distribution and Space-Based QKD	HellasQCI promoted its Winter School / Training Workshop in Thessaloniki on Quantum Key Distribution and space-based QKD, supporting capacity building for researchers, engineers and stakeholders in quantum communication technologies.	Research Communities Industry National Authorities Students	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	359 impressions (LinkedIn)	Delivered
86	02/12/2025	GRNET/HellasQCI at WTDC-25 in Baku	GRNET, coordinator of HellasQCI, participated in the World Telecommunication Development Conference 2025 in Baku, highlighting Greece's contribution to digital development, secure connectivity and quantum communication infrastructure.	EU Institutions National Authorities Research Communities Industry	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	222 impressions (LinkedIn)	Delivered
87	29/12/2025	World Telecommunication Development Conference 2025 Follow-up	HellasQCI highlighted the participation of Sophia Papathanasopoulou, Head of the Broadband Unit at the General Secretariat of Telecommunications and Post, in WTDC-25 as part of Greece's official delegation and broader HellasQCI-related activities.	EU Institutions National Authorities Research Communities Industry	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	641 impressions (LinkedIn)	Delivered
88	14/04/2026	Celebrating World Quantum Day 2026	HellasQCI celebrated World Quantum Day 2026, highlighting Greece's contribution to the European quantum communication landscape and the deployment of a QKD network spanning over 650 km, further supported through SEEWQCI and EuroQCI activities.	EU Institutions National Authorities Research Communities Industry General Public	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	19 reactions (LinkedIn public view); Facebook post also available	Delivered
89	27/04/2026	SEEWQCI and HellasQCI at the RExQTCS & ROGS Kick-off Meeting	SEEWQCI and HellasQCI participated in the RExQTCS and ROGS kick-off meeting in Bucharest, with GRNET representatives presenting the role of HellasQCI, SEEWQCI and TransEuroOGS in advancing terrestrial and satellite-based quantum communication infrastructure.	EU Institutions National Authorities Research Communities Industry General Public	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	19 reactions (LinkedIn public view)	Delivered

No	Date	Communication Activity Name	Description	Who? Target audience reached	Channel	Metrics	Status
90	29/04/2026	GRNET at the TransEuroOGS Kick-off Meeting	GRNET represented Greece at the TransEuroOGS kick-off meeting in Berlin and Jena. The project aims to establish interoperable Optical Ground Stations for satellite-based quantum-secure communication across Germany, Greece, Ireland and Luxembourg within EuroQCI.	EU Institutions National Authorities Research Communities Industry	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	27 reactions and 1 comment (LinkedIn public view)	Delivered
91	04/05/2026	SEEWQCI / HellasQCI at the 21st Panhellenic Conference of Physics	Quantum-secure communications were presented at the 21st Panhellenic Conference of the Union of Greek Physicists in Larisa, highlighting SEEWQCI's vision and its connection with HellasQCI for the next stage of Europe's quantum communications journey.	Research Communities National Authorities Industry General Public	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	25 reactions and 2 comments (LinkedIn public view)	Delivered
92	05/05/2026	GRNET at TNC26: Advancing Quantum Technologies for NRENs	GRNET announced its participation in TNC26 in Helsinki, with Dr. Ilias Papastamatiou chairing the "Quantum Technologies for NRENs" BoF session, bringing together European NRENs to discuss national deployments, cross-border integration and EuroQCI collaboration.	EU Institutions National Authorities Research Communities Industry	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	6 reactions (LinkedIn public view)	Delivered
93	12/05/2026	HellasQCI and SEEWQCI at ITU-T Study Group 20 Meetings	SEEWQCI and HellasQCI participated in ITU-T SG20 meetings in Geneva. Dr. Ilias Papastamatiou presented Contribution 415 on quantum-secure communication use cases from the national HellasQCI infrastructure and its future expansion through SEEWQCI and TransEuroOGS.	EU Institutions National Authorities Research Communities Industry	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	15 reactions (LinkedIn public view)	Delivered
94	08/06/2026	TNC26 Kicks Off - Quantum Technologies for NRENs	HellasQCI promoted the start of TNC26 in Helsinki and the upcoming BoF session "Quantum Technologies for NRENs," chaired by GRNET representatives and focused on NREN roles in supporting trusted, interoperable and cross-border quantum infrastructures.	EU Institutions National Authorities Research Communities Industry	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	9 reactions (LinkedIn public view)	Delivered
95	10/06/2026	GRNET at TNC26: Quantum Technologies for NRENs - Results	Following the TNC26 BoF session, HellasQCI highlighted strong community interest, a full auditorium, active discussion, and updated NREN quantum mapping identifying 23 NRENs active in quantum initiatives, 55 projects and 44 QCI projects.	EU Institutions National Authorities Research Communities Industry	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	29 reactions (LinkedIn public view)	Delivered
96	17/06/2026	SEEWQCI and HellasQCI at BEYOND Expo 2026 - Announcement	HellasQCI and SEEWQCI announced their presentation at BEYOND Expo 2026, with Dimitris Katsianis participating in the panel "Quantum Computing: Challenges and Opportunities" to discuss quantum-secure communication infrastructure	Industry Business Partners National Authorities Research Communities General Public	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	5 reactions (LinkedIn public view)	Delivered

No	Date	Communication Activity Name	Description	Who? Target audience reached	Channel	Metrics	Status
			in Greece and South-East Europe.				
97	17/06/2026	BEYOND 2026 Panel Participation: Quantum Computing Challenges and Opportunities	HellasQCI shared the live participation of Dimitris Katsianis, GRNET Deputy Chairman and Assistant Professor at NKUA, in the BEYOND 2026 panel on quantum computing and GRNET's role in Greece's quantum communication infrastructure.	Industry Business Partners National Authorities Research Communities General Public	Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	3 reactions (LinkedIn public view)	Delivered

Table 23: Social Media

Events

No	Date	Communication Activity / Post Name	Description	Target audience reached	Outcome	Status	Source / verification note
1	01/01/2023	HellasQCI Kick off meeting	The HellasQCI project kick-off meeting took place in Athens, Greece at the Ministry of Digital Governance in January 2023. The project was officially launched by the political leadership of the Ministry highlighting Greece's commitment to the EuroQCI initiative	Industry, Business Partners, National authorities, Regional authorities, Local authorities, Civil society	80 participants	Delivered	Uploaded file; date verified/normalized from name or public HellasQCI/related event pages
2	14/02/2023	9th ETSI IQC Quantum Safe Cryptography Event	The event at ETSI discussed the development, deployment, and standardization of quantum-safe cryptography. The presentation of the HellasQCI was well received since Dr Kanellos emphasized the need for standardization so that the HellasQCI to become a quantum-safe Communication Infrastructure.	Industry, Business Partners, Research Communities	200 participants	Delivered	Uploaded file; date verified/normalized from name or public HellasQCI/related event pages
3	14/04/2023	World Quantum Day (InfoSession)	The event was addressed to academics, researchers, postgraduate students & industry members who work or research in the field of quantum communications, and/or are involved in a sector which can benefit from quantum technologies. Dr Ilias Papastamatiou, Senior Project Manager at GRNET's European Infrastructures & Projects Directorate and HellasQCI project coordinator presented Greece's	Industry, Business Partners, Research Communities, EU institutions	60 Participants	Delivered	Uploaded file; date verified/normalized from name or public HellasQCI/related event pages

No	Date	Communication Activity / Post Name	Description	Target audience reached	Outcome	Status	Source / verification note
			national Quantum Communication Infrastructure (HellasQCI) and its use cases.				
4	24/04/2023	IrelandQCI kick-off meeting	Dr Ilias Papastamatiou, chaired a session and presented the project overall and the synergies with IrelandQCI and Dr Manolis Xilouris, Research Director of the Institute of Astronomy, Astrophysics, Space Applications and Remote Sensing (IAASARS) of NOA presented the Optical Ground Stations in HellasQCI.	Industry, Business Partners, Research Communities	80 participants	Delivered	Uploaded file; date verified/normalized from name or public HellasQCI/related event pages
5	25/04/2023	NOKIA Wavelengths 2023	An invitation only event, Wavelengths, offered exclusive insights into NOKIA's latest developments in optical network solutions	Industry, Business Partners, Research Communities	500 participants	Delivered	Uploaded file; date verified/normalized from name or public HellasQCI/related event pages
6	15/05/2023	6th Annual ScyLight Conference Workshop - Quantum Internet	European and Canadian industry experts, researchers, academics and end users shared their expertise and planned the future of optical and quantum communication technologies	Industry, Business Partners, Innovators	200 participants	Delivered	Uploaded file; date verified/normalized from name or public HellasQCI/related event pages
7	05/06/2023	TNC23 (GÉANT)	Presentation by Dr. Ilias Papastamatiou (Project Coordinator) and PSNC's P. Rydlichowski (PIONEER-Q Coordinator) themed "Quantum Internet Activities in European NRENs	Industry, Business Partners, Research Communities	700 Participants	Delivered	Uploaded file; date verified/normalized from name or public HellasQCI/related event pages
8	15/06/2023	CEN/CENELEC Joint Technical Committee JTC 22	Conference Presentation by H. Papadopoulos and A. Marousis during the JTC22. The JTC aims to produce standardization deliverables in the field of quantum technologies.	Industry, Business Partners, Innovators	40 Participants	Delivered	Uploaded file; date verified/normalized from name or public HellasQCI/related event pages
9	16/06/2023	GRNOG15	Presentation by Dr. Ilias Papastamatiou (Project Coordinator) during the GRNOG15 Meeting. The GRNOG15 meeting offered HellasQCI project a new platform of knowledge exchange and valuable connections.	Industry, Business Partners, Innovators, Research communities	135 Participants	Delivered	Uploaded file; date verified/normalized from name or public HellasQCI/related event pages

No	Date	Communication Activity / Post Name	Description	Target audience reached	Outcome	Status	Source / verification note
10	30/06/2023	Quantum Communication Innovation Forum by EUROQCI Spain	Presentation by Dr. Ilias Papastamatiou during the Quantum Communication Innovation Forum. The forum provided a platform for sharing insights, addressing current and future implementation challenges, and exploring future directions for Quantum Communications in Europe.	Industry, Business Partners, Innovators, Research communities	N/A	Delivered	Uploaded file; date verified/normalized from name or public HellasQCI/related event pages
11	01/09/2023	3rd Ubitech Innovation Days	An event focused around innovation	Industry, Business Partners, Research Communities	150 Participants	Delivered	Uploaded file; date verified/normalized from name or public HellasQCI/related event pages
12	18/09/2023	HellasQCI 1st two thematic axes sessions of Training Event 18-19 21-22 September, Athens, Greece	The training was designed to provide participants with theoretical and practical knowledge on quantum communication, with the goal of enhancing the security of sensitive data and critical infrastructures in Greece	Industry, Business Partners, Research Communities	175 participants + 200 online	Delivered	Uploaded file; date verified/normalized from name or public HellasQCI/related event pages
13	01/11/2023	European Thematic Working Groups (ETWG)	HellasQCI was represented in the working groups by the Coordinator Dr. Ilias Papastamatiou, GRNET, Technical Coordinator Prof. George Kanellos, NKUA, Homer Papadopoulos, NCSR and Giannis Giannoulis, ICCS/GRNET.	Industry, Business Partners, Innovators, EU Institutions, Research communities	N/A	Delivered	Uploaded file; date verified/normalized from name or public HellasQCI/related event pages
14	26/02/2024	PTQCI Workshop , February 26-27, 2024	The Instituto de Telecomunicações in Aveiro, Portugal, hosted a workshop on quantum communication networks, organized by the PTQCI consortium. The event brought together 100 participants, including representatives from national and international initiatives such as HellasQCI (Greece), EuroQCI Spain, QCI-CAT (Austria), RoNaQCI (Romania), Lux4QCI (Luxembourg), as well as entities from the USA and Brazil, to discuss the implementation of future quantum communication networks at national, European, and global levels. Dr. Ilias Papastamatiou, representing HellasQCI, shared Greece's progress in developing its quantum communication infrastructure, highlighting achievements in network architecture, training, and EuroQCI collaborations.	Industry, Business Partners, Innovators, EU institutions, National authorities, Research Communities	100 participants	Delivered	Uploaded file; date verified/normalized from name or public HellasQCI/related event pages

No	Date	Communication Activity / Post Name	Description	Target audience reached	Outcome	Status	Source / verification note
15	06/03/2024	Malta's National QCI Online Kick-off, March 6 2024	HellasQCI participated in Malta's National Quantum Communication Infrastructure (QCI) online kick-off seminar, organized by PRISM Malta. The event featured presentations from national QCI representatives across Europe, discussing progress and fostering collaboration within the EuroQCI initiative. Dr. Ilias Papastamatiou represented HellasQCI, sharing insights into Greece's advancements in quantum communication infrastructure.	EU institutions National authorities Research Communities	NA	Delivered	Uploaded file; date verified/normalized from name or public HellasQCI/related event pages
16	12/03/2024	Quantum-Secure FTTH Infrastructure Going Practical: Integration Experiments in HellasQCI Phase 0, March 12, 2024	This event focused on the practical integration of quantum-secure technologies into Fiber-to-the-Home (FTTH) infrastructures within the HellasQCI Phase 0 framework. It highlighted experimental results and the feasibility of implementing Quantum Key Distribution (QKD) in existing network infrastructures. The event aimed to bridge the gap between theoretical quantum communication concepts and their real-world applications.	Industry, Business Partners Innovators EU institutions National authorities Research Communities	NA	Delivered	Uploaded file; date verified/normalized from name or public HellasQCI/related event pages
17	25/03/2024	QCI Days Vienna 2024	QCI Days Vienna 2024 was organised by AIT Austrian Institute of Technology and QCI-CAT, the event featured sessions on Quantum Key Distribution (QKD), satellite QKD, and EuroQCI architecture. HellasQCI represented by Dr. I. Papastamatiou and Prof. G.Kanellos shared project insights, including network architecture, training initiatives, and experimental results, fostering collaboration across Europe's quantum community.	Industry, Business Partners EU institutions National authorities Research Communities	350+	Delivered	Uploaded file; date verified/normalized from name or public HellasQCI/related event pages
18	22/04/2024	Nokia Wavelengths 2024, April 22–24, 2024	The Wavelengths EMEA-LAT 2024 event, organized by Nokia in Athens, Greece, brought together industry leaders and experts to discuss advancements in optical networks and communications, with a focus on quantum-safe networks. HellasQCI presented a proof-of-concept quantum-secure network developed in collaboration with Nokia, EvolutionQ, and ID Quantique. The event served as a platform to showcase the practical implementation of quantum communication technologies in real-world scenarios.	Industry, Business Partners Innovators EU institutions National authorities Research Communities	200 participants	Delivered	Uploaded file; date verified/normalized from name or public HellasQCI/related event pages

No	Date	Communication Activity / Post Name	Description	Target audience reached	Outcome	Status	Source / verification note
19	29/05/2024	Switzerland – Greece Space Networking Event, 29 May 2024	The event took place at the residence of the Swiss Ambassador, H.E. Stefan Estermann, aiming to foster collaboration between Swiss and Greek innovation ecosystems in space technologies, optical communications, and quantum infrastructure. It was organized under the auspices of the Swiss Space Office, the Hellenic Space Center, and other key institutions. The event featured discussions on best practices and potential joint initiatives to enhance bilateral cooperation in space-related fields.	National Authorities, EU Institutions, Industry and Business Partners, Research Communities	30–40 participants	Delivered	Uploaded file; date verified/normalized from name or public HellasQCI/related event pages
20	10/06/2024	TNC24 Conference, 10–14 June 2024	TNC24, held in Rennes, France is Europe's premier research and education networking conference which attracted over 800 participants from more than 70 countries. The event featured discussions on digital infrastructure, cybersecurity, and quantum communication. Representatives engaged in sessions related to quantum communication infrastructure and its integration into national networks.	Industry professionals, researchers, and institutions involved in networking and digital infrastructure.	800 participants	Delivered	Uploaded file; date verified/normalized from name or public HellasQCI/related event pages
21	12/06/2024	7th Annual ScyLight Conference & 2nd Quantum Workshop, June 12–14, 2024	At the 7th Annual ScyLight Conference & 2nd Quantum Workshop, held in Eindhoven, The Netherlands, Dr. Manolis Xilouris from the National Observatory of Athens presented advancements in optical and quantum communication. His talk highlighted the integration of the Helmos Observatory's optical ground station into the HellasQCI project, emphasizing its role in secure quantum communication networks. This event, organized under the European Space Agency's (ESA) ScyLight program, brought together European and Canadian industries and experts to showcase the latest developments in optical and quantum communication technologies.	Industry, Business Partners, EU institutions, National authorities, Research Communities, Innovators	200–250 participants	Delivered	Uploaded file; date verified/normalized from name or public HellasQCI/related event pages
22	20/06/2024	RoNaQCI Workshop, 20–21 June 2024	The 3rd RoNaQCI Workshop focused on the deployment of quantum communication infrastructure in Romania. Held at the Technical University of Iasi and Alexandru Ioan Cuza University, the workshop featured discussions on quantum key distribution (QKD)	National authorities, EU institutions, industry partners, research communities	50–60 participants	Delivered	Uploaded file; date verified/normalized from name or public HellasQCI/related event pages

No	Date	Communication Activity / Post Name	Description	Target audience reached	Outcome	Status	Source / verification note
			and post-quantum cryptography (PQC)				
23	25/06/2024	12th CAPTECH Cyber Meeting, 25–26 June 2024	The 12th CAPTECH Cyber Meeting held in Athens focused on critical cybersecurity issues within the European Defence Agency's framework. The event featured discussions on the integration of quantum technologies into cybersecurity infrastructures.	National authorities, EU institutions, industry	100–120 participants	Delivered	Uploaded file; date verified/normalized from name or public HellasQCI/related event pages
24	01/07/2024	QCI Ireland Event, 1–3 July 2024	The QCI Ireland Event brought together quantum technology specialists from across Europe for a three-day conference. The event featured workshops, training sessions, and discussions on quantum key distribution (QKD) systems and post-quantum cryptography (PQC). Dr. Homer Papadopoulos highlighted the integration of PQC with QKD, emphasizing HellasQCI's advancements in secure quantum communication	Industry, research communities	450 participants	Delivered	Uploaded file; date verified/normalized from name or public HellasQCI/related event pages
25	25/09/2024	GÉANT InfoShare online session, 25 September 2024	Deploying HellasQCI, the National Quantum Communication Infrastructure of Greece, within the EuroQCI Initiative” Dr. Athanasaki shared insights into the progress, challenges, and future steps of the HellasQCI project, Mr. Carabas provided an update on the Romanian National Quantum Communication Infrastructure	Industry Professionals National and Regional Authorities Research Communities EU Institutions	100 participants	Delivered	Uploaded file; date verified/normalized from name or public HellasQCI/related event pages
26	04/10/2024	1st Iberian QCI Workshop, October 4 2024	The 1st Iberian Quantum Communication Infrastructure (QCI) Workshop took place on October 4, 2024, at Teatro Aveirense in Aveiro, Portugal. This event focused on security issues and cross-border interconnections among national quantum communication infrastructures (NatQCIs), specifically between Greece (HellasQCI), Portugal (PTQCI), Spain (EuroQCI Spain), and Malta (PRISM). The workshop featured a panel discussion titled “National Secure Quantum Networks and Cross Border Interconnection”, moderated by Catarina Bastos from Deimos Engenharia and PTQCI Coordinator	National and Regional Authorities Research Communities Industry Professionals EU Institutions Business Partners	100 participants	Delivered	Uploaded file; date verified/normalized from name or public HellasQCI/related event pages

No	Date	Communication Activity / Post Name	Description	Target audience reached	Outcome	Status	Source / verification note
27	24/10/2024	15th International Conference on Space Optics (ICSO 2024), October 24 2024	At the 15th International Conference on Space Optics (ICSO 2024) held on October 24, 2024, in Antibes, France, the HellasQCI project showcased its latest advancements in quantum communication. Dr. Manolis Xilouris from the National Observatory of Athens (NOA) presented the pivotal role of the Helmos Optical Ground Station (OGS) in integrating space-based quantum key distribution (QKD) into the terrestrial network, under the framework of the European Quantum Communication Infrastructure (EuroQCI).	Research Communities EU Institutions National Authorities Industry Professionals Business Partners	300 participants	Delivered	Uploaded file; date verified/normalized from name or public HellasQCI/related event pages
28	05/11/2024	Danish Quantum Communication Infrastructure (QCI.DK) Workshop, November 5 2024	The National QCI.DK Workshop took place on November 5, 2024, at A.C. Meyers Vænge 15, Copenhagen, Denmark. Organized by the Danish Quantum Communication Infrastructure (QCI.DK), the workshop focused on "Securing the Future: Quantum Key Distribution for Enterprises and Governments"	Industry professionals Business partners National authorities EU institutions Research communities	100 participants	Delivered	Uploaded file; date verified/normalized from name or public HellasQCI/related event pages
29	21/11/2024	Migration to Quantum-Safe Workshop, November 21–22, 2024	The Migration to Quantum-Safe Workshop, organized by ID Quantique (IDQ), took place on November 21–22, 2024, at the Steigenberger Hotel Herrengasse in Vienna, Austria. This event focused on the transition to quantum-safe technologies, including Quantum Key Distribution (QKD), Quantum Random Number Generation (QRNG), and Post-Quantum Cryptography (PQC). ilphotonics.com+6	Industry professionals Business partners EU institutions National authorities Research communities	100 participants	Delivered	Uploaded file; date verified/normalized from name or public HellasQCI/related event pages
30	26/11/2024	ETWG Workshop, November 26-28 2024	The EuroQCI Thematic Working Group (ETWG) Workshop took place from 26–28 November 2024 in Brussels, Belgium. Organized by PETRUS and hosted by Deutsche Telekom Global Business Belgium, this three-day event aimed to advance the European Quantum Communication Infrastructure (EuroQCI) by bringing together various stakeholders to discuss its development and future directions. Dr. Papastamatiou co-chaired the session on the "National QCI Roadmap"	European Commission representatives Member State officials Project coordinators and technical experts Industry professionals Research community members National Quantum Communication Infrastructure (QCI) representatives	100 participants	Delivered	Uploaded file; date verified/normalized from name or public HellasQCI/related event pages

No	Date	Communication Activity / Post Name	Description	Target audience reached	Outcome	Status	Source / verification note
31	05/12/2024	PRISM Quantum Week, December 5 2024	On 5 December 2024, Dr. Homer Papadopoulos, Functional Researcher at NCSR Demokritos and Dissemination Coordinator of HellasQCI, participated in the PRISM Quantum Week held at the University of Malta, Valletta Campus. The event was organized under the auspices of PRISM EuroQCI, aiming to explore advancements in quantum communications.	Industry Business Partners EU institutions National authorities Research Communities	300 participants	Delivered	Uploaded file; date verified/normalized from name or public HellasQCI/related event pages
32	06/02/2025	HellasQCI SNSPDs Training Workshop by Single Quantum	The Single Quantum – HellasQCI Training on 6 February 2025 focused on theoretical and practical training for the consortium on SNSPD operation and maintenance.	Consortium technical/end-user staff, research communities	20 physical participants + hybrid attendance	Delivered	Website / social post
33	28/04/2025	QCI Days Athens 2025	QCI Days Athens 2025 gathered European experts, policymakers, and industry leaders to discuss the future of secure quantum communications. Held in Athens under the EuroQCI initiative, the event highlighted Greece's leading role in advancing quantum technologies and digital security. A key moment was the live cross-border Quantum Key Distribution (QKD) demonstration connecting Greece, Austria, and Spain.	EU Institutions National Authorities Research Communities Industry General Public	Event	300 physical participants and around 300 daily online viewers	Uploaded file; date verified/normalized from name or public HellasQCI/related event pages
34	09/06/2025	TCN25	The TNC25 Quantum Session highlighted the role of National Research and Education Networks (NRENs) in building Europe's secure quantum communication infrastructure, with HellasQCI showcasing Greece's contribution to cross-border collaboration and quantum-secure digital innovation.	EU Institutions National Authorities Research Communities Industry General Public	Event	500+	Uploaded file; date verified/normalized from name or public HellasQCI/related event pages
35	07/07/2025	WSIS+20 Forum	The WSIS+20 High-Level Event took place from 7–11 July 2025 in Geneva, Switzerland, bringing together global stakeholders to discuss digital cooperation, ICT development, and emerging technologies. The forum included high-level dialogues, technical sessions, and multistakeholder discussions under the coordination of the International Telecommunication Union (ITU).	EU Institutions National Authorities Research Communities Industry General Public	Event	1000+	Uploaded file; date verified/normalized from name or public HellasQCI/related event pages

No	Date	Communication Activity / Post Name	Description	Target audience reached	Outcome	Status	Source / verification note
36	10/09/2025	89th Thessaloniki International Fair (TIF89)	At the 89th Thessaloniki International Fair (TIF), held in Thessaloniki, Greece in September 2025, HellasQCI participated in a high-level panel discussion on the development of quantum technologies in Greece. The event brought together representatives from government, academia, and industry to present progress on quantum communication infrastructure and its alignment with the European Quantum Communication Infrastructure (EuroQCI) initiative.	EU Institutions National Authorities Research Communities Industry General Public	Event	1500	Uploaded file; date verified/normalized from name or public HellasQCI/related event pages
37	16/09/2025	QCI Connect Forum	The QCI Connect Forum 2025 was held on 16–17 September 2025 in the Tallinn area, Estonia, specifically at the LaSpa Hotel in Laulasmaa near Tallinn. The event brought together representatives from National Quantum Communication Infrastructure (NatQCI) projects across Europe as part of the EuroQCI initiative. HellasQCI participated with delegates from GRNET and NKUA, contributing to sessions focused on national progress in quantum key distribution (QKD) networks, technical challenges, and future cross-border quantum communication plans.	EU Institutions National Authorities Research Communities Industry General Public	Event	120	Uploaded file; date verified/normalized from name or public HellasQCI/related event pages
38	28/09/2025	51st European Conference on Optical Communication (ECOC 2025)	From 28 September to 2 October 2025, the HellasQCI project participated in the 51st European Conference on Optical Communication (ECOC 2025) held in Copenhagen, Denmark. NKUA, GRNET, and QUBITECH — demonstrated a four-node dynamically switched Quantum Key Distribution (QKD) network with SRAM-PUF-based authentication.	EU Institutions National Authorities Research Communities Industry	Event	1000+	Uploaded file; date verified/normalized from name or public HellasQCI/related event pages
39	29/09/2025	CEPT Conference	From 29 September to 3 October 2025, Athens hosted the European Conference of Postal and Telecommunications Administrations (CEPT), where the HellasQCI project participated by showcasing Greece's national quantum communication infrastructure and its role in the pan-European EuroQCI initiative. High-level ITU officials visited research facilities at NKUA and NTUA as part of the HellasQCI activities during the conference.	EU Institutions National Authorities Research Communities Industry	Event	100	Uploaded file; date verified/normalized from name or public HellasQCI/related event pages

No	Date	Communication Activity / Post Name	Description	Target audience reached	Outcome	Status	Source / verification note
40	17/11/2025	World Telecommunication Development Conference 2025	On 17–28 November 2025, the World Telecommunication Development Conference (WTDC-25) was held in Baku, Azerbaijan. During the conference, HellasQCI showcased Greece’s progress in quantum communications and its role in the European EuroQCI initiative, highlighting advancements in secure quantum networks, national infrastructure development, and international cooperation in emerging technologies.	EU Institutions National Authorities Research Communities Industry	Event	1000	Uploaded file; date verified/normalized from name or public HellasQCI/related event pages
41	26/11/2025	HellasQCI Winter School (Training Workshop)	Three-day HellasQCI Winter School / Training Workshop held in Thessaloniki on Quantum Key Distribution and space-based QKD technologies.	Students, researchers, cybersecurity professionals, quantum communication community	120+ participants / 15 countries	Delivered	Website / event page
42	26/11/2025	PETRUS Workshop	Date: 26–27 November 2025 Place: Brussels, Belgium. GRNET, participated in the PETRUS Workshop by presenting Greece’s contribution to the EuroQCI ecosystem. The participation highlighted Greece’s active role in cross-border quantum communication experiments and collaboration within the PETRUS and EuroQCI initiatives	EU Institutions National Authorities Research Communities Industry	Event	80	Uploaded file; date verified/normalized from name or public HellasQCI/related event pages
43	01/12/2025	first GEANT SIG-Quantum meeting	On 1 December 2025, the HellasQCI project participated in the inaugural GEANT SIG-Quantum online meeting, which was held remotely as a virtual European research and networking event. During the session, GRNET and HellasQCI presented “Quantum Communications in Europe: EuroQCI Deployment and the HellasQCI Paradigm,” highlighting Greece’s progress in deploying quantum-secure communication infrastructures.	EU Institutions National Authorities Research Communities Industry	Event	50	Uploaded file; date verified/normalized from name or public HellasQCI/related event pages
44	15/12/2025	Digital Economy Forum 2025	On 15 December 2025 HellasQCI participated through GRNET, with a keynote/panel contribution presenting quantum communications developments and their role in the EuroQCI initiative and European cybersecurity infrastructure in Athens	EU Institutions National Authorities Research Communities Industry	Event	400	Uploaded file; date verified/normalized from name or public HellasQCI/related event pages
45	04/02/2026	GRNET & NKUA visit Motor Oil – Use case: Critical Infrastructure	Visit and use-case activity related to critical infrastructure within the HellasQCI communication and dissemination stream.	Industry, national authorities, research communities	N/A	Delivered	Website / social post

No	Date	Communication Activity / Post Name	Description	Target audience reached	Outcome	Status	Source / verification note
46	05/02/2026	Q-PrEP (Quantum Preparedness) In-Person Workshop	On 5th of February, Dr. Ilias Papastamatiou, Senior Project Manager at GRNET and Coordinator of HellasQCI, delivered a keynote speech on strengthening the resilience of critical infrastructure in Greece against cyber threats, highlighting the strategic importance of post-quantum readiness for national and European digital infrastructures. In addition, Dr. Homer Papadopoulos, Senior Science & Development Manager at NCSR "Demokritos" and HellasQCI Communications Leader, presented on Post-Quantum Cryptography (PQC) and Quantum Key Distribution (QKD), highlighting practical pathways towards quantum-safe communications.	EU Institutions National Authorities Research Communities Industry	Event	200	Uploaded file; date verified/normalized from name or public HellasQCI/related event pages
47	06/02/2026	Q-PrEP and HellasQCI Community Workshop at GRNET	On 6 February, a follow-up focused community workshop entitled "Strengthening Europe's Quantum Communication Ecosystem: Q-PrEP and HellasQCI" was held at the premises of GRNET, in cooperation with the Q-PrEP project and NCSR "Demokritos", bringing together around 20 participants from the Greek and European quantum technologies and quantum communications ecosystem.		Event	50	Uploaded file; date verified/normalized from name or public HellasQCI/related event pages
48	10/02/2026	A Greek First: Quantum-Secure Technologies Deployed in a Hospital Environment	Post/article describing deployment of quantum-secure technologies in a hospital environment under HellasQCI and EuroQCI.	Healthcare stakeholders, industry, national authorities, research communities	N/A	Delivered	Website / social post
49	26/02/2026	SEEWQCI (South-East Europe to Western Europe Quantum Communication Infrastructure)	The official launch of the SEEWQCI project was held on 26-27 February 2026, at the Main Amphitheater of the Hellenic Ministry of Digital Governance, in Athens. The event brought together representatives from a consortium of 15 partners and 7 supporting organisations from Greece, Cyprus, Bulgaria, and the Netherlands.	EU Institutions National Authorities Research Communities Industry	Event	250	Uploaded file; date verified/normalized from name or public HellasQCI/related event pages
50	06/03/2026	SEEWQCI: Building a Quantum Communication Infrastructure to securely connect South-Eastern and Western Europe	News post announcing/communicating the SEEWQCI project and its role in securing European communications through quantum encryption technologies.	EU institutions, national authorities, research communities, industry	N/A	Delivered	Website / social post

No	Date	Communication Activity / Post Name	Description	Target audience reached	Outcome	Status	Source / verification note
51	19/03/2026	SBIQCI Kick-off meeting	GRNET actively participated in the official kick-off meeting of the SBIQCI (Sofia–Bucharest Interconnection of Quantum Communication Infrastructure) project, held on 19 March 2026 in Sofia, bringing together key stakeholders from across the EuroQCI ecosystem	EU Institutions National Authorities Research Communities Industry	Event	50	Uploaded file; date verified/normalized from name or public HellasQCI/related event pages
52	24/03/2026	ITU Regional Development Forum for Europe 2026	On 24 March 2026 at Prague, Czech Republic HellasQCI presented the country's contribution titled "Excellence in Quantum Communications – From National Deployment to Cross-Border European Integration."		Event	300	Uploaded file; date verified/normalized from name or public HellasQCI/related event pages
53	24/04/2026	SEEWQCI at the 21st Panhellenic Conference of Physics	SEEWQCI was represented at the 21st Panhellenic Conference of the Union of Greek Physicists in Larisa, Greece.	Research communities, students, national authorities, industry	N/A	Delivered	Website / social post
54	27/04/2026	SEEWQCI – HellasQCI – REXQTCS – ROGS Kick-off in Bucharest (April 2026)	On April 27-28, 2026 in Bucharest, Romania HellasQCI participated in at the REXQTCS & ROGS Kick-off Meeting	EU Institutions National Authorities Research Communities Industry	Event	150	Uploaded file; date verified/normalized from name or public HellasQCI/related event pages
55	12/05/2026	SEEWQCI and HellasQCI at the ITU-T SG20 Meetings in Geneva	A Greek delegation participated in ITU-T Study Group 20 meetings in Geneva, connected to IoT, digital twins and smart sustainable cities.	EU/international institutions, national authorities, research communities, industry	N/A	Delivered	Website / social post
56	21/05/2026	Germany, Greece, Ireland and Luxembourg unite to establish quantum-secure network: TransEuroOGS	News post about the TransEuroOGS project to link optical ground stations across Europe for quantum-secure networking.	EU institutions, national authorities, research communities, industry	N/A	Delivered	Website / social post
57	08/06/2026	TNC26 (GÉANT Conference 2026)	At TNC26 (8–12 June 2026, Helsinki), attended by over 800 international participants, HellasQCI contributed through GRNET by leading a session on Quantum Technologies for NRENs, presenting Greece's role in EuroQCI and cross-border quantum communication infrastructure development	EU Institutions National Authorities Research Communities Industry	Event	800	Uploaded file; date verified/normalized from name or public HellasQCI/related event pages
58	17/06/2026	SEEWQCI and HellasQCI at BEYOND 2026	SEEWQCI and HellasQCI were presented at BEYOND 2026, the International Digital Technology & Innovation Exhibition at Metropolitan Expo, Athens.	Industry, national authorities, research communities, general public	N/A	Delivered	Website / social post

Table 24: Events

Infographics

No	Communication Activity Name	Description	Who? Target audience reached	Outcome	Status
1	Training Event in Thessaloniki 2025	Training event at a glance	National authorities, Regional authorities, Local authorities, Civil society, Citizens, Research Communities	1 Infographic	Delivered
2	Training Event in Crete 2024	Training event at a glance	National authorities, Regional authorities, Local authorities, Civil society, Citizens, Research Communities	1 Infographic	Delivered
3	Training event in Athens 2023	Training event at a glance	National authorities, Regional authorities, Local authorities, Civil society, Citizens, Research Communities	1 Infographic	Delivered
4	January 2023 - November 2025	Overall Achievements	National authorities, Regional authorities, Local authorities, Civil society, Citizens, Research Communities	1 Infographic	Delivered
5	January 2023 - April 2025	Overall Achievements	National authorities, Regional authorities, Local authorities, Civil society, Citizens, Research Communities	1 Infographic	Delivered
6	Reporting period 1	2023 Achievements (RP1)	National authorities, Regional authorities, Local authorities, Civil society, Citizens, Research Communities	1 Infographic	Delivered
7	Reporting period 2	January 2024-April 2025 Achievements (RP2)	National authorities, Regional authorities, Local authorities, Civil society, Citizens, Research Communities	1 Infographic	Delivered
8	QCI Days Athens	Annual project highlights through infographic presentation	National authorities, Regional authorities, Local authorities, Civil society, Citizens, Research Communities	1 Infographic	Delivered

Table 25: Infographics

Media Articles

No	Communication Activity Name	Description	Who? Target audience reached	Outcome	Status
1	HellasQCI Kick-off meeting Media Articles	Media articles in the Greek press documenting the kick off of the HellasQCI projects. Acknowledged and well-known publications including: Kathimerini - Money Review, Imerisia, Alpha TV, Skai TV, Iefimerida, Capital, Insider, Liberal, etc. List of the media articles in the report here: https://hellasqci.eu/hellasqci-project-kick-off-meeting-report/	Local authorities, Civil Society, Citizens, Research Communities	55 media articles	Delivered

No	Communication Activity Name	Description	Who? Target audience reached	Outcome	Status
2	NOKIA PROOF OF CONCEPT MEDIA ARTICLES	Overall, coverage led with a primarily positive tone, emphasizing the positive potential for Quantum Computing, noting that government and other research organizations are already working to invest in, and utilize the technology to address various societal issues like sustainability and defense. Articles further enforce the need for Quantum safe networks and showcase the value added by the Nokia Security Management Server (SMS) to orchestrate Quantum-Safe keys and provide continuous monitoring and management of quantum secured connectivity.	Industry, Business Partners, Innovators, Research Communities	35 media articles	Delivered
3	HellasQCI: theoretical and practical knowledge in the quantum technologies seminar	Media Article in online Newspaper ("To Manifesto") documenting the HellasQCI 1st two thematic axes sessions of training Event. Link: https://tomanifesto.gr/hellasqci-theoritikes-kai-praktikes-gnoseis-sto-seminario-gia-tis-kvantikes-technologies-153848	Industry, Business Partners, Innovators, Citizens, Civil society	1 media article	Delivered
4	Training Event in Crete 2024	• Euro2Day , • SKAIKRITIS.GR , • KINHTA NEA , • Dnews , • epixeiro.gr , • creta.gr , • politikakritis.gr , • pna.gr , • tomanifesto.gr , • ictplus.gr	Local authorities, Civil Society, Citizens, Research Communities, IT Professionals	8 media articles	Delivered
	QCI Days 2025	• myportal , • eidiseis.gr , • powergame.gr , • eidhseis365.gr , • businessnews.gr , • mononews , • newsit , • fibernews , • defencepoint	Local authorities, Civil Society, Citizens, Research Communities, IT Professionals	18 media articles	Delivered
	A Greek First: Quantum-Secure Technologies Deployed in a Hospital Environment	Business Daily • Politic.gr • Politica.gr • Health Daily • Greek City Times	Local authorities, Civil Society, Citizens, Research Communities, IT Professionals	5 media articles	Delivered

Table 26: Media articles

Newsletters

No	Communication Activity Name	Description	Who? Target audience reached	Outcome	Status
1	1st Biannual Newsletter (July 23)	The 1st official HellasQCI Newsletter provided news regarding the future of cybersecurity with Quantum Technologies and PQC algorithms, in Greece and all over Europe.	National authorities, Regional authorities, Local authorities, Civil society, Citizens, Research Communities	252 Total Opens	Delivered

No	Communication Activity Name	Description	Who? Target audience reached	Outcome	Status
2	2nd Biannual Newsletter (Dec 23)	The 2nd official HellasQCI Newsletter of 2023 showed the latest progress and updates of the project nationally, through the successful organisation of the HellasQCI 1st two thematic axes sessions of Training Event, as well as in European level by promoting EUROQCI activities.	National authorities, Regional authorities, Local authorities, Civil society, Citizens, Research Communities	132 Total Opens	Delivered
3	3rd Biannual Newsletter (June 2024)	The 3rd official HellasQCI Newsletter is out, aiming to show the latest progress and updates of the project. Among others, the preparation of the 3rd training event, several collaboration activities, as well as the successful review by EU	Industry, Business Partners, Research Communities, EU institutions	122 Total Opens	Delivered
4	4th Biannual Newsletter (December 2024)	The 4th official HellasQCI Newsletter is out, aiming to show the latest progress and updates of the project.	Industry, Business Partners, Research Communities, EU institutions	465 Total Opens	Delivered
5	5th Biannual Newsletter (December 2025)	The 5th official HellasQCI Newsletter is out, aiming to show the latest progress and updates of the project.	Industry, Business Partners, Research Communities, EU institutions	478 Total Opens	Delivered
6	QCI Days Athens 2025	An invitation was sent from the National Quantum Communication Infrastructures (NatQCI) projects of Greece (HellasQCI), Spain (EuroQCI Spain), Austria (QCI-CAT) respectively, to QCI Days Athnes 2025 Event, that took place in Athens between 28-30 April 2025	Industry, Business Partners, Research Communities, EU institutions	1,214 Total Opens	Delivered
7	HellasQCI Winter School (Training Workshop) 2025	HellasQCI Winter School (Training Workshop) 2025 , in Thessaloniki; a FREE three-day training workshop on Quantum Key Distribution (QKD) and Space-based QKD technologies , combining theory, hands-on lab experience, and expert-led sessions. The event was held under the auspices of the Hellenic Ministry of Digital Governance and Artificial Intelligence , with the support of the General Secretariat of Telecommunications and Post , and is organised by the HellasQCI consortium between dates 26 to 28 November 2025	Industry, Business Partners, Research Communities, EU institutions	1,470 Total Opens	Delivered

Table 27: Newsletters

Press Releases

No	Communication Activity Name	Description	Who? Target audience reached	Outcome	Status
1	HellasQCI Kick-off Meeting Press Release	Official Press Release from the Greek Ministry of Digital Governance: https://mindigital.gr/archives/4958	Industry, Business Partners, National authorities, Regional authorities, Local authorities, Citizens, Civil society	1 Press Release	Delivered
2	NOKIA PROOF OF CONCEPT PRESS RELEASE	Official Nokia website link: https://www.nokia.com/about-us/news/releases/2023/12/18/hellasqci-and-nokia-lead-way-to-the-future-of-quantum-safe-networks/#:~:text=Espoo%2C%20Finland%20E2%80%93%20Nokia%20today%20announced,National%20Quantum%20Communication%20Infrastructure%20Consortium	Industry, Business Partners, Innovators, Research Communities	1 official press release	Delivered
3	IrelandQCI Kick-off Meeting Press Release	Press release issued for the participation of HellasQCI in the IrelandQCI kick-off meeting, highlighting collaboration between National Quantum Communication Infrastructures (https://hellasqci.eu/irelandqci-launch/)	Industry, Business Partners, General Public	1 Press Release	Delivered
4	HellasQCI Training Event Press Release	Press release covering the HellasQCI training event and its impact on quantum technologies and cybersecurity awareness (https://irelandqci.ie/2023/09/18/irelandqci-project-lead-dr-deirdre-kilbane-presents-at-first-hellasqci-training-event-in-greece/)	Industry, Business Partners, General Public	1 Press Release	Delivered
5	Athens at the Center of Quantum Communication Infrastructure, hosting QCI Days 2025, under the auspices of the Greek Ministry of Digital Governance QCI Days 2025: Greece at the forefront of Europe's journey toward a secure and quantum-innovative digital future	Athens hosting QCI Days 2025 & QCI Days Athens 2025	Industry, Business Partners, General Public	1 Press Release	Delivered

No	Communication Activity Name	Description	Who? Target audience reached	Outcome	Status
6	Η Ελλάδα στην Πρωτοπορία των Κβαντικών Επικοινωνιών στην Ευρώπη – Διπλή ευρωπαϊκή διάκριση για τα νέα έργα SEEWQCI και TransEuroOGS	Greece at the Forefront of Quantum Communications in Europe – Double European Distinction for the New SEEWQCI and TransEuroOGS Projects	Industry, Business Partners, General Public	1 Press Release	Delivered

Table 28: Press releases

Promotional Material

No	Communication Activity Name	Description	Who? Target audience reached	Outcome	Status
1	Project Media Kit	Project rollups, Flyer, Logo https://hellasqci.eu/media-kit/	Citizens	100 HellasQCI pins 100 HellasQCI coloured logo stickers 100 HellasQCI white logo stickers 90 notebooks 100 pens were distributed to the participants of the HellasQCI 1st two thematic axes sessions of Training Event	Delivered
2	HellasQCI Training Event Crete 2024	Branded materials produced and distributed to participants of the HellasQCI Training Event Crete 2024, including notebooks, stickers, pins, pens, tote bags, and Phaistos Disk souvenirs for invited speakers	Researchers, technical community, invited speakers	120 distributed to participants	Delivered
3	QCI Days Athens 2025	Branded materials produced and distributed at QCI Days Athens 2025, including roll-up banners, flyers, and branded items	Researchers, policymakers, industry representatives, international guests	300 distributed to participants	Delivered
4	HellasQCI Winter School Thessaloniki 2025	Branded materials produced and distributed at the HellasQCI Winter School Thessaloniki 2025, including branded pens, agendas, laptop stickers, pins, brochure, roll-up banners, and power banks for invited speakers	Researchers, technical community, invited speakers	115 distributed to participants	Delivered

No	Communication Activity Name	Description	Who? Target audience reached	Outcome	Status
5	HellasQCI Project Booklet	A comprehensive booklet presenting the project's objectives, infrastructure, use cases, training activities, and key achievements, produced for both print and digital distribution.	Industry, Business Partners, Policy, Research Communities, EU Institutions	Project overview booklet (print + digital) 150 copies to be printed and distributed	Delivered

Table 29: Promotional material

TV

No	Communication Activity Name	Description	Who? Target audience reached	Outcome	Status
1	HellasQCI in the press	https://www.alphatv.gr/news/koinonia/article/124805/hellasqciasfaleia-euaisthithon-dedomenon-kai-upodomon/?fbclid=IwAR1NdfFJn2lQaZNya_3P7ouNkM1gMxDq7Rbe9US6pBXeug1LxbeP9OD-nY	Citizens	Not available data because monitoring of website performance was not available on M1 of the project	Delivered

Table 30: TV

Videos

No	Communication Activity Name	Description	Who? Target audience reached	Outcome	Status
1	2 HellasQCI Videos	The videos show how Quantum Communication Technologies will protect critical infrastructure and data in Greece in English and Greek	Citizens	The visitors of the Newsfeed page(of the project was increased to 30% relatively to the previous (August 2023) and the next month (October 2023)	Delivered
2	3 HellasQCI Videos	Three videos were also created to cover the three-day training event in Thessaloniki (HellasQCI Winter School Day 1 , HellasQCI Winter School Day 2 , Highlights from the HellasQCI Winter School 2025)	Citizens	The social media posts generated strong engagement, reaching more than 1,000 interactions across the campaign and attracting significant interest from the quantum communications community.	Delivered

Table 31: Videos

Website

No	Communication Activity Name	Description	Who? Target audience reached	Outcome	Status
1	Online Training platform (https://training.hellasqci.eu/)	The training HellasQCI platform provides the event speeches and presentations of the HellasQCI organization trainings for the purpose of providing information about quantum computing. The platform has been configured in such a way that users can access the event material in an easy-to-use environment.	Technical, research community, end-users	156 Users until June 2026	Delivered
2	Official Project Website (https://hellasqci.eu/)	The projects' Website	Industry, Business Partners, Citizens, Research Communities	30,5K visitors until June 2026	Delivered

Table 32: Website

Website & Newspapers

No	Communication Activity Name	Description	Who? Target audience reached	Outcome	Status
1	Announcement - Invitation to participate in a Public Consultation process	Invitation to participate in public consultation processes in the context of the HellasQCI project, published in the Greek Newspapers and announced on the project's website. Link: https://hellasqci.eu/announcement-invitation-to-participate-in-the-public-consultation-procedure-on-the-text-of-the-open-electronic-tender-for-fiber-optic-link-leasing-services-for-the-implementation-of-the-terrestrial/	Industry, Business Partners	9 Public Procurements & Clarifications	Delivered

Table 33: Website and newspapers

Annex C - QCI Days Athens 2025 press release

<https://hellasqci.eu/qci-days-2025-greece-at-the-forefront-of-europes-journey-toward-a-secure-and-quantum-innovative-digital-future/>

<https://grnet.gr/en/2025/05/07/pr-qcidays-2025/?cmplz-force-reload=1777463288027>

Annex D - HellasQCI Training Event in Crete 2024

[Full report](#)

Annex E - HellasQCI Winter School Training Workshop Thessaloniki 2025

[Full Report](#)

Annex F - Partners' online media channels

Online Media Channels / Partner	Facebook	LinkedIn	Twitter	Instagram	YouTube	Website/info page and initial publicity
GRNET (all project related announcements have been shared on GRNET online channels)	grnet.gr	grnet sa	grnet_gr	grnet.gr	grnet edytc	www.grnet.gr HellasQCI info page Related Press Releases on grnet website Reporter publicity
AUTH	https://www.facebook.com/Aristoteleio/	https://www.linkedin.com/school/university-of-thessaloniki-auth-/	https://twitter.com/Aristoteleio	https://www.instagram.com/auth_university_thessaloniki/	N/A	https://www.auth.gr/en/
NKUA	https://www.facebook.com/uoa.official	https://www.linkedin.com/school/nkua/	https://twitter.com/uoaofficial	https://www.instagram.com/nkua.gr/	https://www.youtube.com/@nkua	https://en.uoa.gr/
NOA	https://www.facebook.com/pages/National-Observatory-of-Athens/	https://www.linkedin.com/company/national-observatory-of-athens/	N/A	N/A	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCoJhWyGmrTii_l8Llwhb09A	https://www.noa.gr/
FORTH	https://www.facebook.com/FORTH.ITE	https://www.linkedin.com/company/foundation-for-research-&-technology-hellas-forth-/	https://twitter.com/FORTH_ITE	https://www.instagram.com/forth_ite/	https://www.youtube.com/forth-ite	www.forth.gr

Online Media Channels / Partner	Facebook	LinkedIn	Twitter	Instagram	YouTube	Website/info page and initial publicity
NCSR	https://www.facebook.com/pages/NCSR-Demokritos/311021049022821	https://www.linkedin.com/company/ncsr-demokritos/	https://twitter.com/NCSR_Demokritos	https://www.instagram.com/ncsrdemokritos/	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCokquGFyZ7KAdXQLNL6NdgQ	central website: https://www.demokritos.gr/ , via the IIT Newsletter (https://www.iit.demokritos.gr/newsletters/), and News in the IIT's site : www.iit.demokritos.gr/newsevents/ , via the groups e-health and knowledge management unit site (https://ehealthunit.demokritos.eu/)
COS	www.facebook.com/cosmote/	https://www.linkedin.com/showcase/cosmote/	twitter.com/cosmote	https://www.instagram.com/cosmote_greece/	https://www.youtube.com/user/cosmote	www.cosmote.gr
SPH	/SpaceHellas Official	/company/space-hellas-s.a./	@SpaceHellas	N/A	N/A	www.space.gr
MOH	N/A	https://gr.linkedin.com/company/motor-oil-hellas	N/A	N/A	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCTUYuKMVr0iyAisVQ5ZoWA	www.moh.gr
QUBI	N/A	q-ubitech	@Q_Ubit_Tech	N/A	N/A	q.ubitech.eu/Press release

Table 34: Partners' online social media

Annex G – Scientific publications

Scientific papers submitted in Journals

- H. Papadopoulos, A. Korakis, and G. Balaskas, "Practical deployment of hybrid QKD and post-quantum cryptography for off-site hospital data," IEEE Access, early access, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2026.3708672.
- D. Zavitsanos et al., "Feasibility Analysis of QKD Integration in Real-World FTTH Access Networks," in Journal of Lightwave Technology, [Link](#), vol. 42, no. 1, pp. 4-11, 1 Jan.1, 2024, doi: 10.1109/JLT.2023.3303908.
- Georgios M. Nikolopoulos and Marc Fischlin "Quantum Key Distribution with Post-Processing Driven by Physical Unclonable Functions" [Link](#), Appl. Sci. 2024, 14(1), 464; doi: 10.3390/app14010464 Published: 4 January 2024
- Georgios M. Nikolopoulos, "Quantum Diffie–Hellman key exchange", [Link](#), APL Quantum 2, 016107 (2025), Volume 2, Issue 1, <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0242473>
- Antonia Tsili, Georgios Maragkopoulos, Aikaterini Mandilara, Dimitris Syvridis, "Learning the N-Input Parity Function with a Single-Qubit and Single-Measurement Sampling", [Link](#), doi: <https://doi.org/10.3390/electronics14050901>
- Georgios Maragkopoulos, Aikaterini Mandilara, Thomas Nikas, Dimitris Syvridis, "Real-Time Diagnostics on a QKD Link via QBER Time-Series Analysis", [Link](#) doi:<https://doi.org/10.3390/e26110922>

- Aristeidis Stathis, Argiris Ntanos, Panagiotis Toumasis, Nikolaos K. Lyras, Giannis Giannoulis, Hercules Avramopoulos, "Experimental feasibility analysis of quantum/classical coexistence over fibre and free space links", [Link](#), doi: <https://doi.org/10.1364/OE.518564>
- Argiris Ntanos; Nikolaos K. Lyras; Aristeidis Stathis; Giannis Giannoulis; Athanasios D. Panagopoulos; Hercules Avramopoulos, "Satellite-to-Ground QKD in Urban Environment: A Comparative Analysis of Small-Sized Optical Ground Stations", [Link](#), doi: 10.1109/MAES.2024.3383817
- Georgios M. Nikolopoulos Minimum-error state discrimination and Fano's inequality Am. J. Phys. 93, 566–573 (2025), [Link](#), doi: <https://doi.org/10.1119/5.0268023>
- Georgios Maragkopoulos, Aikaterini Mandilara, Antonia Tsili & Dimitris Syvridis, "Enhancing the performance of variational quantum classifiers with hybrid autoencoders", [Link](#), Quantum Information Processing (2025) 24:244 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11128-025-04864-w>
- Thabet, Maya; Tsili, Antonia; Krilakis, Konstantinos; Syvridis, Dimitris; "Post-Quantum PKI: A Survey of Applications and Benchmarking Practices", *Cryptography* 2026 Vol 10, Issue 1, p11, [Link](#), doi: <https://doi.org/10.3390/cryptography10010011>
- Antonis Selentis; Nikolas Makris; Alkinoos Papageorgopoulos; Persefoni Konteli; Konstantinos Christodouloupoulos; George T. Kanellos "Evaluating Relayed and Switched Quantum Key Distribution (QKD) Network Architectures", *Lightwave Technology*, [Link](#), doi: [10.1109/JLT.2026.3695776](https://doi.org/10.1109/JLT.2026.3695776)

Scientific papers submitted in Conferences

- Makris, A. Ntanos, A. Papageorgopoulos, A. Stathis, P. Konteli, I. Tsoni, G. Giannoulis, F. Setaki, T. Stathopoulos, G. Lyberopoulos, H. Avramopoulos, G. T. Kanellos, D. Syvridis. "DV-QKD link over multiple ONT loaded carrier-grade GPON for FTTH applications". 2023 (Accepted at SPIE Photonics West 2024). [Link](#)
- G. T. Kanellos, K. Christodouloupoulos, I. Tsoni, A. Papageorgopoulos, N. Makris, P. Konteli, D. Syvridis. "Advanced key management in switched QKD networks with non-optimized QKD links". 2023 (Accepted at SPIE Photonics West 2024). [Link](#)
- N. Makris, A. Papageorgopoulos, P. Konteli, I. Tsoni, K. Christodouloupoulos, G. T. Kanellos, and D. Syvridis. "Relayed-qkd and switched-qkd networks performance comparison considering physical layer qkd limitations". 2023 (Accepted at OFC 2024).
- N. Makris, A. Ntanos, A. Papageorgopoulos, A. Stathis, P. Konteli, I. Tsoni, G. Giannoulis, F. Setaki, T. Stathopoulos, G. Lyberopoulos, H. Avramopoulos, G. T. Kanellos, D. Syvridis. "O-band QKD link over a multiple ONT loaded carrier-grade GPON for FTTH applications". 2023 (Accepted at OFC 2024). [Link](#)
- K. Christodouloupoulos, N. Makris, G. T. Kanellos, D. Syvridis. "Optimizing Key Consumption in Switched QKD Networks". ISBN:979-8-3503-7758-3 (Accepted at OFC 2024) Published: 16 May 2024. [Link](#)
- Dr. Ilias Papastamatiou, Dr. Ognjen Prnjat, Kostas Koumantaros, Prof. Dimitris Mitropoulos, Nikolas Makris, Dr. Konstantinos Tsimvrakidis, Alkinoos Papageorgopoulos, Persefoni Konteli, Prof. Kostas Christodouloupoulos, Prof. George T. Kanellos, Prof. Dimitris Syvridis. "Field Demonstration of a Fully Managed, L1 Encrypted 3-Node Network with Hybrid Relayed-QKD and Centralised Symmetric Classical Key Management" ISBN:978-3-8007-6426-6 (Accepted at ECOC 2024). Published: 22-26 September 2024. [Link](#)
- Giannis Giannoulis, Aristeidis Stathis, Argiris Ntanos, Nikolaos K. Lyras, Ilias Papastamatiou, Panagiotis Kourelis, Ognjen Prnjat, Kostas Koumantaros, Athanasios D. Panagopoulos, Hercules Avramopoulos. "Satellite-to-ground QKD Feasibility Analysis for High Altitude Rural Areas: A Case

Study in Greece”. doi: 10.1109/FOAN63517.2024.10765646 (Accepted at FOAN24) Published: 28 November 2024. [Link](#)

- Aristeidis Stathis, Argiris Ntanos, Panagiotis Kourelis, Panagiotis Toumasis, Nikolaos K. Lyras, Hercules Avramopoulos, Giannis Giannoulis. “5G X-haul/QKD Multiplexing over Deployed Infrastructure” (Published in: 2025 25th Anniversary International Conference on Transparent Optical Networks (ICTON)). [Link](#)
- Nikolaos Stefanakos, Georgios Maragkopoulos, Aikaterini Mandilara, Dimitris Syvridis “A Measurement Device Independent Quantum Key Distribution protocol in the service of three users” (2025 International Conference on Quantum Communications, Networking, and Computing (QCNC)). [Link](#)
- Evgenia-Niovi Sassalou; Stefanos Vasileiadis; Stylianos A. Kazazis; Georgia Protogerou; Nikos Varvitsiotis; Dimitrios S. Karas. “A PUF-based Root-of-Trust for resource-constrained IoT devices” DOI: 10.1109/CSR64739.2025.11130114 (Published in: 2025 IEEE International Conference on Cyber Security and Resilience (CSR)). [Link](#)
- Alkinoos Papageorgopoulos; Konstantinos Tsimvrakidis; Nikolas Makris; Persefoni Konteli; Evrydiki Kyriazi; Grigoris Anastasiou “Interoperable Multi-Vendor, Multi-Domain, Multi-Layer, Multi-Service Quantum Key Distribution Network Field-Trial” DOI: [10.1109/QCNC69040.2026.00038](#) (Published in: 2026 International Conference on Quantum Communications, Networking, and Computing (QCNC)). [Link](#)
- Alkinoos Papageorgopoulos; Konstantinos Tsimvrakidis; Nikolas Makris; Persefoni Konteli; Evrydiki Kyriazi; Grigoris Anastasiou “Multi-Domain IPsec Over MACsec QKD Field Deployed Demonstration” DOI: [10.1109/QCNC69040.2026.00066](#) (Published in: 2026 International Conference on Quantum Communications, Networking, and Computing (QCNC)) [Link](#)
- P. Konteli; N. Makris; E. N. Sassalou; S. A. Kazazis; A. Papageorgopoulos; S. Vasileiadis “Dynamic Switched Quantum Key Distribution Network with PUF-based authentication” Electronic ISBN:978-1-957171-54-8 (Published in: 2026 Optical Fiber Communications Conference and Exhibition (OFC)). [Link](#)
- Ondrej Klicnik; Grigoris Anastasiou; Nikolaos Makris; Argiris Ntanos; Aris Stathis; Konstantinos Tsimvrakidis “Quantum Key Distribution Over Multimode Fiber Infrastructure” DOI: 10.1109/QCNC69040.2026.00062 (Published in: 2026 International Conference on Quantum Communications, Networking, and Computing (QCNC)). [Link](#)
- Persefoni Konteli; Nikolas Makris; Konstantinos Tsimvrakidis; Alkinoos Papageorgopoulos; Ilias Papastamatiou; Petros Papapetropoulos “Field-test Quantum Key Distribution Over mixed Buried/Aerial Fiber Links with 16 km Aerial Fiber Segments” DOI: 10.1109/ECOC66593.2025.11263153 (Published in: 2025 European Conference on Optical Communications (ECOC)). [Link](#)

Other Scientific Publications (preprint)

- [Advancing National Security: Greece's Strategic Plan for Next-Gen MILSATCOM Systems](#)
- Leandros Maglaras, Ilias Papastamatiou, Alexios Aivaliotis, Evangelos Markatos, Konstantinos Karantzalos “Building Europe's Quantum Shield: The Strategic view for a Continent-Wide Quantum Key Distribution (QKD) Infrastructure” [Link](#)
- Selentis, Nikolas Makris, Alkinoos Papageorgopoulos, Persefoni Konteli, Konstantinos Christodouloupoulos, George T. Kanellos, Dimitris Syvridis “Evaluating Relayed and Switched

Quantum Key Distribution (QKD) Network Architectures Antonis" . Submitted: 29 September 2025

- Argiris Ntanos, Aristeidis Stathis, Panagiotis Kourelis, Evridiki Kyriazi, Panagiotis Toumasis, Nikolaos K. Lyras, Nikolaos Makris, Sotirios Tsavdaridis, E.M. Xilouris, Athanasios Marousis, Ilias Papastamatiou, Athanasios D. Panagopoulos, Konstantinos Vyrsokinos, Kleomenis Tsiganis, George T. Kanellos, Hercules Avramopoulos, Giannis Giannoulis "SMF Coupled Compact Ground Terminal with Advanced Filtering Towards Daylight C Band Satellite QKD " . Submitted: 9 September 2025
- Nikolaos Makris, Ondrej Klicnik, Argiris Ntanos, Aristeidis Stathis, Grigoris Anastasiou, Konstantinos Tsimvrakidis, Giannis Giannoulis, Hercules Avramopoulos, George T. Kanellos, Petr Munster, Tomas Horvath "Quantum Key Distribution over Multi-mode Fiber Infrastructure" (Submitted at ECOC 2025 conference proceedings). Submitted: 22 April 2025
- Alkinoos Papageorgopoulos, Persefoni Konteli, Nikolas Makris, Konstantinos Tsimvrakidis, Ilias Papastamatiou, Petros Papapetropoulos, Andreas Agrafiotis, Dimitrios Syvridis, George T. Kanellos "Relay-based Quantum Key Distribution integrated with IPsec encrypted link over standard Internet Infrastructure" (Submitted at ECOC 2025 conference proceedings). Submitted: 22 April 2025
- K. Tsimvrakidis, P. Konteli , A. Ntanos, A. Stathis , N. Makris, P. Kourelis , A. Papageorgopoulos, G. Giannoulis , I. Papastamatiou , P. Papapetropoulos, H. Avramopoulos , G. T. Kanellos, D. Syvridis "Bidirectional Fiber-Wireless-Fiber QKD Transmission Over 2x8.8Km Field-Deployed Single Feeder Link and 100m FSO Link". doi: <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2504.06892> (Accepted at OFC 2025 conference proceedings). Submitted: 3 April 2025. [Link](#)
- G. Maragkopoulos, N. Stefanakos, A. Mandilara, D. Syvridis "Applications of Hybrid Machine Learning Methods to Large Datasets: A Case Study". doi: <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2504.06892> (Accepted at IEEE QCNC 2025 conference proceedings). Submitted: 9 April 2025. [Link](#)
- Persefoni Konteli, Nikolaos Makris, Konstantinos Tsimvrakidis, Alkinoos Papageorgopoulos, Ilias Papastamatiou, Petros Papapetropoulos, Dimitrios Syvridis, George T. Kanellos "Time-bin Phase and Polarization based QKD systems performance analysis over 16Km Aerial Fibers". doi: <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2503.03436> (Submitted at OECC/PSC2025 conference proceedings). Submitted: 5 March 2025. [Link](#)